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Doctoral Program in Mechanical Engineering (37th cycle)

Design Methodology of Electromagnetic Shock Absorbers for Vehicle Suspensions

By

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Declaration

I hereby declare that, the contents and organization of this dissertation constitute my own original work and does not compromise in any way the rights of third parties, including those relating to the security of personal data.

Gennaro Sorrentino
2025

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To my parents, for their humble and constant support.

Abstract

In recent years, electrification has dominated the development of innovative automotive components. Indeed, this trend aims to increase the overall vehicle efficiency, mitigate its emissions, and enable advanced controls by means of smart components. Alongside the well-known transition towards hybrid and electric powertrains, many "by-wire" actuators are replacing usual passive chassis components, such as the one of the steering and braking systems.

In this context, the suspension system plays a key role, as its behaviour strongly affects not only vehicle comfort and handling, but also energy dissipation and recovery. Active suspensions typically replace the conventional hydraulic damper with a mechatronic device capable of exerting both active and passive forces at any force-velocity operating point within its physical constraints. Particularly, electromagnetic dampers complement this feature with the ability to partially recover vibrational energy from road irregularities by converting it into electrical energy. They consist of a controllable electric machine and a proper transmission stage to the suspension.

Both the constant increase of scientific literature and availability of high-segment vehicles equipped with active suspensions demonstrate the strong interest in this field. However, a clear gap can be pinpointed between the academia and the industry. The former mainly focuses on innovative control strategies and energy harvesting capabilities, often producing just proof of concepts for laboratory activities. The latter instead concentrates on integration feasibility, packaging, and active functionalities, such as roll control during cornering.

The present doctoral dissertation aims to align academic research with industrial development by proposing a holistic design methodology for the design of optimal, vehicle-ready electromagnetic shock absorbers. It follows a V-scheme that starts with the investigation of the technology and packaging studies. Then, the definition of the system requirements and the optimal detailed design of the shock absorbers

follow. The demonstrator setup is at the base of the cycle, specifically a D-segment SUV and a naked motorcycle are addressed. From this point, testing, validation, and control tuning finalize the methodology.

The proposed electromagnetic shock absorbers couple a rotary electric machine with either a mechanical or hydraulic transmission. Rotary machines are preferred for their increased torque and power density, while the choice between the two transmissions mainly depends on the packaging constraints. The mechanical transmission under study is a planetary gearbox, chosen for its compactness and high transmission ratio. However, a rotary-to-linear conversion mechanism is required to transform the motor rotary motion into suspension linear motion. This task is performed by a linkage mechanism made of a lever and a push-pull rod. This mechanical layout allows to completely remove the traditional damper. On the contrary, the hydraulic solution requires a hydraulic cylinder for motion linearization; thus, a conventional shock absorber with closed valves can accomplish this task without introducing unwanted damping. The controlled pressure differential is built up by means of a positive displacement pump, i.e., a gerotor pump. For this reason, this kind of damper are also referred as electro-hydrostatic.

In the end, the electromechanical technology is fitted onto the SUV corners while the electro-hydrostatic in the front fork of the motorcycle. Particularly, the electromechanical solution reaches higher efficiencies and control bandwidth but challenges related to fail-safe operations and noise arose. Instead, the electro-hydrostatic one realizes acceptable fail-safe damping at the cost of lower efficiency due to its internal leakages, hydraulic losses, and frictions.

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List of Acronyms

ASIL	Automotive Safety Integrity Level
AWD	All Wheel Drive
BEV	Battery Electric Vehicle
CAN	Controller Area Network
CoG	Center of Gravity
DC	Direct Current
EHA	Electro-Hydrostatic Actuation shock absorber
EU	European Union
FOC	Field-Oriented Control
GMF	Gear Meshing Frequency
GT	Grand Tourer
HEV	Hybrid Electric Vehicle
HIL	Hardware-In-the-Loop
HS	High-Speed
ICE	Internal Combustion Engine
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Lower Control Arm

LS	Low-Speed
MAX	Maximum (Peak)
MISO	Multi-Input Multi-Output
MPC	Model Predictive Control
NVH	Noise, Vibration, and Harshness
OC	Open Circuit
PID	Proportional Integral Derivative
PM	Permanent Magnet
LQR	Linear–Quadratic Regulator
RMS	Root Mean Square
RSA	Rotary Shock Absorber
SC	Short Circuit
SISO	Single-Input Single-Output
SPL	Sound Pressure Level
SPM	surface Permanent Magnet
SUV	Sport Utility Vehicle

List of Symbols

a_f	Front semi-wheelbase
a_{\max}	Acceleration tuning parameter for H_∞ control
a_{pr}	Planet-ring interaxle spacing
a_{ps}	Planet-sun interaxle spacing
a_r	Rear semi-wheelbase
a_y	Vehicle lateral acceleration
b_i	i -th stage face width
b_{hs}	High speed stage face width
b_{ls}	Low speed stage face width
c	Desired damping for suspension velocity
c_a	Shock absorber controlled damping
c_{em}	Desired damping at the motor shaft
c_{em}	Short circuit damping reported at the motor shaft
c_{eq}	Equivalent viscous damping
$c_{g,i}$	Ground-hook damping for the i -th axle
c_i	Desired damping for the i -th suspension velocity
c_l	Leakage damping

c_m	Mount damping
c_{\max}	Short circuit damping
$c_{\max,\text{eha}}$	EHA short circuit damping at wheel center minimum requirement
$c_{\max,\text{rsa}}$	RSA short circuit damping at wheel center minimum requirement
c_{\min}	Open circuit damping
c_p	Controlled passive damping
c_s	Sky-hook damping
$c_{s,i}$	Sky-hook damping for the i -th axle
c_u	Tire radial damping
c_θ	Pitch rate viscous rotational damping
d	Speed bump width
d_1	Shoe dimension 1
d_2	Shoe dimension 2
d_w	Wire diameter
\mathbf{e}	Vector of the performance objectives for the H_∞ control design
f_1	Objective function on kinematic ratio for linkage optimization
f_2	Objective function on transmission angle for linkage optimization
f_{id}	Quarter-car identification function
f_s	Sampling frequency
f_t	Frequency of the reference displacement profile to the test bench
$f_{\text{gm,hs}}$	High-speed stage gear meshing frequency
$f_{\text{gm},i}$	i -th stage gear meshing frequency
$f_{\text{gm,ls}}$	Low-speed stage gear meshing frequency

$f_{sb,i}^h$	Output shaft GMF sidebands of the i -th stage
$f_{sb,i}^k$	Input shaft GMF sidebands of the i -th stage
$f_{in,hs}$	High-speed stage input rotational frequency
$f_{in,ls}$	Low-speed stage input rotational meshing frequency
g	Gravity acceleration
g_{em}	Electric machine air gap
g_i	Linear inequality constraints for linkage optimization
h	Speed bump height
i_{dc}	DC current
i_{gb}	Gearbox reduction ratio
$i_{gb,eff}$	Gearbox effective reduction ratio
i_{st}	Gearbox stage reduction ratio
$i_{st,eff}$	Gearbox effective stage reduction ratio
i_p	Ratio between planet rotational speed and carrier speed
j	Imaginary unit
$k_{cp,max}$	Maximum achievable gross packing factor of the slot
k_d	Roll control derivative gain
k_f	Front axle stiffness
k_h	Experimental correction factor for the contact patch
k_i	Roll control integral gain
k_m	Mount stiffness
k_p	Roll control proportional gain
k_r	Rear axle stiffness

k_s	Suspension stiffness at wheel center
k_{tf}	Front axle tires stiffness
k_{tr}	Rear axle tires stiffness
k_u	Tire radial stiffness
ℓ	Total wheelbase
l_c	Electric machine active length for max damping requirement
l_{cp}	Contact patch length
l_{ct}	Length of the end-turn path
l_{em}	Electric machine active length
$l_{em,max}$	Electric machine maximum allowable active length
l_g	Gerotor gears length
l_m	Permanent magnet thickness
l_{max}	Electric machine active length for peak force requirement
l_{rms}	Electric machine active length for RMS force requirement
l_{AB}	Pushrod length
l_{BC}	Crank length
m	Shock absorber mass
m_{em}	Shock absorber electric machine mass
m_{eq}	Equivalent mass of the shock absorber
$m_{eq,eha}$	EHA equivalent mass
$m_{eq,em}$	Equivalent mass of the shock absorber electric machine
$m_{eq,gb}$	Equivalent mass of the shock absorber gearbox
$m_{eq,max}$	Shock absorber target maximum equivalent mass

$m_{\text{eq,rsa}}$	RSA equivalent mass
m_{f}	Front axle unsprung mass
m_{gb}	Shock absorber gearbox mass
m_{max}	Shock absorber target maximum mass
m_{n}	Gear normal module
m_{r}	Rear axle unsprung mass
m_{rsa}	RSA mass
m_{s}	Sprung mass
$m_{\text{s,tot}}$	Total sprung mass
m_{u}	Unsprung mass
n_{c}	Gerotor number of cycles per revolution
$n_{\text{c},i}$	i -th carrier speed in rpm
$n_{\text{s},i}$	i -th sun gear speed in rpm
$o_{\text{gm,hs}}$	High-speed stage gear mesh order
$o_{\text{gm,ls}}$	Low-speed stage gear mesh order
p	Electric machine pole pair
p_0, p_1	Measured pressure in the EHA test bench
p_{meas}	Recorded pressure by microphone
p_{ref}	Reference pressure for sound pressure in air
q	Generalized degrees of freedom
r_{s}	Suspension stroke weighting coefficient for LQR
r_{h}	Tire deflection weighting coefficient for LQR
r_{Tl}	Electric machine torque-to-length ratio in continuous duty

$r_{\text{TL}} \Big _{J_{\text{max}}}$	Electric machine torque-to-length ratio in peak duty
s	Laplace variable
t_0	Time instant of the bump event
t_{acc}	Sprung mass acceleration settling time
t_{f}	Front track width
t_{r}	Rear track width
t_{rh}	Road holding settling time
u	LQR control action
v, \dot{x}	Shock absorber speed at wheel center (suspension velocity)
v_{c}	Coulomb velocity threshold
v_{car}	Vehicle longitudinal speed
v_{d}	Shock absorber speed at its ends
$v_{\text{max,eha}}$	EHA peak velocity at wheel center requirement
$v_{\text{max,rsa}}$	RSA peak velocity at wheel center requirement
$v_{\text{rms,rsa}}$	RSA RMS velocity at wheel center requirement
v_{si}	Peripheral speed of the sun gear of the i -th stage
w	weighting coefficient
\mathbf{w}	Vector of the disturbances for the H_{∞} control design
w_{bi}	Back iron width
w_{d}	Weighting coefficient for stator diameter in the global optimization
w_{m}	Weighting coefficient for the mass in the global optimization
w_{s}	Slot opening
w_{t}	Shoe width

w_{tb}	Tooth width
x	Shock absorber displacement at wheel center (suspension stroke)
x_{eq}	Shock absorber displacement at the equivalent mass
x_l	Shock absorber displacement before leakages
x_t	Tire deflection
$x_{t,max}$	Tire deflection tuning parameter for H_∞ control
$x[N]$	Displacement time history at fixed sample rate
\dot{x}_{eq}	Shock absorber velocity at the equivalent mass
$\dot{x}_{s,meas}$	Measured suspension velocity at wheel center
y_f	Front axle road displacement
y_r	Rear axle road displacement
z_{eq}	Equivalent vertical displacement of the electromagnetic actuator
z_r	Road vertical displacement
z_s	Sprung mass vertical displacement
z_u	Unsprung mass vertical displacement
\dot{z}_{eq}	Equivalent vertical velocity of the electromagnetic actuator
\dot{z}_s	Sprung mass vertical velocity
\dot{z}_u	Unsprung mass vertical velocity at wheel center
\ddot{z}_{eq}	Equivalent vertical acceleration of the electromagnetic actuator
\ddot{z}_{pp}	Peak-to-peak sprung mass acceleration
\ddot{z}_s	Sprung mass vertical acceleration
\ddot{z}_u	Unsprung mass vertical acceleration at wheel center
\ddot{z}_w	ISO 2631 weighted sprung mass vertical acceleration

A_p	Shock absorber piston cross-section
A_s	Stator slot cross-section
A_w	Wire cross-section
B_{bi}	Stator back iron flux density
$B_{bi,PM}$	Stator back iron flux density only due to PMs
D_c	Carrier pitch diameter
D_{go}	Gearbox diameter
D_{go}	Gerotor outer diameter of the outer gear
D_p	Planet pitch diameter
D_r	Ring pitch diameter
D_{ri}	Inner rotor diameter
D_{ro}	Outer rotor diameter
D_s	Sun pitch diameter
D_{sb}	Back iron diameter
D_{si}	Inner stator diameter
D_{so}	Outer stator diameter
$D_{so,max}$	Maximum allowable outer stator diameter
E	Elastic modulus
F	Shock absorber force reported at wheel center
$F[f_t]$	FFT of the measured force at the testing frequency
F_a	Ideal actuation force
$F_{a,des}$	Desired ideal actuation force from control
F_c	Coulomb friction force

F_{cost}	Cost function for the global optimization
F_{d}	Shock absorber force at its ends
$F_{\text{d},i}$	Desired vertical-dynamics control force on the i -th axle
F_{el}	Suspension elastic force
F_{f}	Friction force
$F_{i,\text{des}}$	Desired ideal actuation force from control on the i -th axle
F_{in}	Inerter force
F_{lt}	Load transfer on quarter car
$F_{\text{m},\text{cost}}$	Cost function for the actuator mass optimization
F_{max}	Actuator effort tuning parameter for H_{∞} control
$F_{\text{max,eha}}$	EHA peak force at wheel center requirement
$F_{\text{max,rsa}}$	RSA peak force at wheel center requirement
$F_{\text{meq},\text{cost}}$	Cost function for the actuator equivalent mass optimization
$F_{\text{p},i}$	Desired pitch-dynamics control force on the i -th axle
F_{ref}	Reference force
$F_{\text{rms,rsa}}$	RSA RMS force at wheel center requirement
F_{s}	Overall suspension force at wheel center
F_{sat}	Tire saturation force
F_{ss}	Steady-state force
F_{t}	Tire vertical force at wheel center
G_{qc}	Quarter-car model state space
$G_{\text{qc}}^{\text{rsa}}$	Quarter-car model with electromechanical actuator state space

G_r	Road roughness coefficient
G_{road}	Road roughness transfer function
G_{roll}	Sprung mass roll model state space
H	Sprung mass CoG distance to roll axis
H_a	Actuation to output force transfer function (actuation bandwidth)
H_v	Free-end speed to output force transfer function (impedance)
I_{em}	Rotational inertia of the electric machine rotor shaft
I_{em+in}	Rotational inertia of the motor shaft coupled to the inner EHA gear
I_{go}	Rotational inertia of the outer gear of the EHA pump
$I_{hs,c}$	Rotational inertia of the gearbox high-speed stage carrier
$I_{hs,p}$	Rotational inertia of the gearbox high-speed stage planet
I_ℓ	Rotational inertia of the linkage mechanism
$I_{ls,c}$	Rotational inertia of the gearbox low-speed stage carrier
$I_{ls,p}$	Rotational inertia of the gearbox low-speed stage planet
I_{out}	Rotational inertia at the output shaft
$I_{out,rsa}$	RSA Rotational inertia at the output shaft
I_{ph}	Motor phase current
$I_{ph,km}$	Kollmorgen servomotor phase current
I_s	Sprung mass roll inertia
$I_{tot,rsa}$	Total rotational inertia of the RSA at its own axis
$I_{tot,eha}$	Total rotational inertia of the EHA at its own axis
I_z	Sprung mass pitch inertia
J	LQR cost function

J_{\max}	Peak duty current density
J_{rms}	Continuous duty current density
K	LQR controller
$K(s)$	H_{∞} controller
K_e	Phase back electromotive constant
K_t	Electric machine torque constant
$K_{t,\text{km}}$	Kollmorgen servomotor torque constant
K_A	Gear overload factor
K_{Vi}	Gear dynamic factor for the i -th stage
L	Direct and quadrature inductance
M_a	Active anti-roll moment
M_p	Step response force overshoot
N	LQR cross-weighting matrix
N_c	Number of coils in series per phase
N_g	Gerotor number of teeth of the inner gear
N_h	Number of wires-in-hand of the coil
N_{ph}	Number of phases
N_s	Number of slots
N_t	Number of turns per coil
$P(s)$	Extended plant for H_{∞} control synthesis
P_e	Electrical power at the DC link
P_h	Hydraulic power
P_m	Mechanical power

P_{PM}	Magnet permeance coefficient
Q	LQR state weighting matrix
Q_{cha}	EHA flow rate
R	LQR control action weighting matrix
R_c	Coil resistance
R_{ext}	External electrical resistance
R_{ph}	Electric machine phase resistance
R_{ph}	Total electrical resistance
R_0	Undeformed tire radius
SPL	Sound pressure level
T_0	Signal length
T_d	Peak-peak time in the step response
T_{em}	Electric machine torque
T_i	i -th stage torque at the carrier
T_{km}	Kollmorgen servomotor servomotor torque
$T_{max,cha}$	EHA peak torque
T_{out}	Torque at the output shaft
T_{ref}	Torque reference
T_{zw}	Transfer function disturbances-performance for the H_∞
V_0	Gerotor unit displacement
V_{dc}	DC link voltage
V_g	Gerotor volumetric displacement
V_{in}	Pump displacement of the EHA test bench

W	Work of a force
$W_{d1}(s)$	Road disturbance function for H_∞ control design
$W_{d2}(s)$	Load transfer function for H_∞ control design
$W_{\text{eff}}(s)$	Actuator effort objective function for H_∞ control design
$W_{o1}(s)$	Acceleration objective function for H_∞ control design
$W_{o2}(s)$	Tire deflection objective function for H_∞ control design
\mathbf{X}	Vector of the design variables for linkage optimization
\mathbf{X}_L	Lower geometrical constraints for linkage optimization
\mathbf{X}_U	upper geometrical constraints for linkage optimization
$X[f_t]$	FFT of the measured displacement at the testing frequency
$X[k]$	DFT of the displacement time history
\mathbf{Y}	Vector of the design variables for electric machine cross-section optimization
\mathbf{Y}_L	Lower bound vector of the design variables for electric machine cross-section optimization
\mathbf{Y}_U	Upper bound vector of the design variables for electric machine cross-section optimization
\mathbf{Z}	Quarter car state vector for LQR design
$Z(s)$	Mechanical impedance
Z_p	Planet gear number of teeth
Z_r	Ring gear number of teeth
Z_s	Sun gear number of teeth
Z_E	Gear elastic factor

Z_H	Gear pressure angle factor
Z_ϵ	Gear contact ratio factor
\mathcal{F}	Dissipated energy
\mathcal{L}	Lagrangian term
\mathcal{T}	Kinetic energy
\mathcal{U}	Potential energy
α	Gear pressure angle
γ	Transmission angle
γ_{nom}	Transmission angle at suspension nominal position
γ_{max}	Transmission angle maximum value
γ_{min}	Transmission angle minimum value
γ_H	H_∞ performance level
$\delta(z_{\text{eq}} - z_u)$	Virtual relative displacement between actuator and unsprung mass
δz_s	Virtual displacement of the sprung mass
δW	Virtual work of a force
ζ	Damping ratio
η_{act}	RSA conversion efficiency in active mode
η_{em}	EHA electromechanical efficiency
η_{reg}	RSA conversion efficiency in regenerative mode
η_{rh}	Road holding index
η_t	EHA total conversion efficiency
η_v	EHA volumetric efficiency
θ	Sprung mass pitch angle

$\dot{\theta}$	Sprung mass pitch rate
$\ddot{\theta}$	Sprung mass pitch acceleration
θ_{BC}	Crank angular displacement
λ_0	Road roughness limit spatial frequency
ν	Poisson's ratio
ρ_{Cu}	Electrical resistivity of copper at ambient temperature
ρ_{Fe}	Steel mass density
σ	standard deviation
σ_{max}	Standard deviation maximum admissible value
σ_H	Allowable contact stress of the material
τ	RSA global transmission ratio
τ_b	RSA test bench kinematic ratio
τ_{cha}	EHA global transmission ratio
$\tau_{cha,eff}$	EHA effective global transmission ratio
τ_ℓ	Linkage kinematic ratio
$\tau_{\ell,nom}$	Linkage kinematic ratio at suspension nominal position
$\tau_{\ell,nom}^{3D}$	Linkage nominal kinematic ratio from multi-body
$\tau_{\ell,max}$	Maximum allowable linkage kinematic ratio
τ_{min}	Minimum allowable RSA global transmission ratio
ϕ_s	Sprung mass roll angle
$\dot{\phi}_s$	Sprung mass roll velocity
$\ddot{\phi}_s$	Sprung mass roll acceleration
χ_f	Front axle roll stiffness

χ_r	Rear axle roll stiffness
χ_{tot}	Total roll stiffness
χ_p^*	Planet gear profile shift coefficient
χ_r^*	Ring gear profile shift coefficient
χ_s^*	Sun gear profile shift coefficient
ω	Angular frequency
ω_0	Road roughness cut-off frequency
ω_e	Electromagnetic pole angular frequency
ω_{eha}	EHA pump rotational speed
ω_{em}	Electric machine angular speed
ω_{km}	Kollmorgen servomotor speed
$\omega_{\text{max,eha}}$	Maximum EHA shaft angular speed
$\omega_{\text{max,em}}$	Maximum electric machine angular speed
ω_n	Natural angular frequency
ω_{out}	Rotational speed at the output shaft
Γ_{out}	Rotational viscous damping at the output shaft
$\Delta\gamma_{\text{max}}$	Maximum admissible transmission angle variation
Δp	Differential pressure
Δp_{max}	EHA maximum differential pressure
Δz	Static tire deflection
ΔF_{af}	Front axle force couple for anti-roll moment
ΔF_{ar}	Rear axle force couple for anti-roll moment
Ω	Electrical speed of the electric machine

Chapter 1

Introduction

As the world moves towards cleaner and intelligent technologies, the automotive industry envisions the future of mobility as electrified, autonomous, shared, and connected [1].

Climate change and global warming, driven by pollutant and greenhouse gas emissions, represent one of the most pressing global crises of our time. The European Union (EU) has positioned itself as a pivotal actor in addressing this challenge, introducing a range of environmentally sustainable policies aimed at achieving climate neutrality by 2050. In the automotive sector, the EU has legislated a ban on the sale of new internal combustion engine (ICE) vehicles starting in 2035, with allowances for vehicles powered by carbon-neutral synthetic fuels, commonly referred to as e-fuels [2]. To accelerate the adoption of zero-emission vehicles, member states have implemented targeted feebate systems, particularly incentivizing the adoption of electric vehicles [3].

Vehicle electrification is transforming both the powertrain and the chassis. Indeed, hybrid and full electric powertrain architectures are already the state of the art for electrified drive systems [4] and widely available on the market. Novel research about hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs) focuses mainly on energy management strategies for the synergy of the electric drive and the internal combustion engine by means of artificial intelligence [5] or model-based predictive controls [6]. Instead, research on battery electric vehicles (BEVs) targets innovative powertrain configurations [7] and novel electric drive technologies [8]. In general, for both HEVs and BEVs, a lot of effort is also dedicated to more efficient electric energy storage systems

and their management [9], more efficient and faster charging [10], and life cycle assessment of the electric components in order to reduce the overall environmental impact of the new vehicles [11]. On the other hand, chassis electrification primarily involves the substitution of the classic mechanical or hydraulic systems with x-by-wire technologies. Those are usually mechatronic devices enabling the reduction of the components, the use of more efficient electric technologies, and the possibility of active controls for assisted and autonomous driving. For example, steer-by-wire systems can adapt to the sensed road friction improving the driving experience [12], brake-by-wire systems can be fundamental in reducing stopping time in emergency manoeuvres, avoiding wheel locking, and regenerating part of the braking power [13], throttle-by-wire systems are also proposed to control driver's torque request and optimise air intake, hence combustion and emissions, especially in motorcycle applications [14]. A great deal of interest is also being paid to suspension actuators, as demonstrated by the constant increase in publications in recent years [15], because suspensions deeply influence ride comfort, vehicle manoeuvrability, and safety, controlling the tire-ground interaction and regulating body motion and vibration. Eventually, the synergistic implementation of these technologies allows integrated chassis controls for enhanced vehicle performance by overcoming the individual limitations of each subsystem, the conflicts among them, and offering redundancy for safety [16].

SAE J3016™ standardizes vehicle automation in six levels, from level 0 grouping vehicles with only warning and momentary assistance to level 5 grouping full autonomous vehicles [17]. Vehicle electrification could be seen as the foundation for the autonomous driving since only more precise and reliable x-by-wire technologies could introduce the action of computerized drivers. Shared and connected vehicles are then strictly related to vehicle automation. Most likely the mobility of the future will rely on interconnected autonomous fleet [18] and shared autonomous vehicles for safety and climate concerns [19].

As already mentioned, in this context, suspensions play a key role because they significantly affect ride comfort, handling, and safety. More deeply, active suspension could mitigate motion sickness [20], benefiting autonomous driving, as the removal of the need to drive will allow passengers to engage in other activities, such as working, relaxing, or enjoying entertainment, transforming the cabin into a multi-functional space. Advances in perception, both in terms of sensors and algorithms, and trajectory planning for autonomous driving enables also predictive controls

for active suspensions [21]. Handling and safety are strongly linked because they depend on the tire-ground forces. For instance, a proper control of the suspension improves braking performance [22] and rollover safety [23], and the coordinated control of suspensions, brakes, and steering further enhances vehicle stability, in terms of handling and rollover propensity reduction [24].

Automotive industry is already proposing different active suspension technologies for high-segment vehicles. Bose Corporation studied novel electromagnetic active suspensions already in 1980s and their patents started to become public from the beginning of the 2000s [25]. In 2009, Levant Power proposed a regenerative shock absorber capable of imposing the desired damping to the suspension and capturing the energy due to its relative motion [26]. Nowadays, they are worldwide known as ClearMotion supplying active shock absorbers to important car makers, as Porsche [27] and NIO [28]. Since 2013, Mercedes S-class vehicles mount electro-hydraulic suspensions, known as Magic Body Control, for the optimal damping tuning as a function of the road surface scanned by a camera in the vehicle front, the travelling speed, and the selected driving mode [29, 30]. ZF portfolio also presents its version of fully active shock absorber [31] and the most recent Ferrari Purosangue and F80 show innovative cutting-edge active suspensions in collaboration with Multimatic [32, 33].

However, research in academia is focusing more on the regenerative potential of active shock absorbers and innovative controls of the involved vehicle dynamics. Abdelkareem et al. [34] reviewed many regenerative shock absorbers proposals and outlined an average recovered power from 10 to 100 W, extremely dependent on the vehicle speed and weight, and the crossed road. Conversion efficiency is the key factor penalizing hydraulic-based shock absorbers (10-40%) to electromechanical shock absorbers (20-70%), and linear solutions (20-50%) to rotary ones (10-70%). Alternatively, control specialists are delving into preview-based strategies because advances in sensors and road estimation techniques enabled classification and estimation of the road profile ahead of the vehicle. Particularly, Model Predictive Control (MPC) techniques seem to reach the best performance, extremely reducing the well-known comfort-handling conflict [35].

In the end, car makers, suspension suppliers, and universities know the potential to actively control the suspension system for superior comfort and driving experience, as well as to increase the overall vehicle efficiency. Nevertheless, costs are strongly

limiting the commercial spread of these technologies, delimiting them to add-on components for very high-segment cars.

1.1 Thesis goal

As introduced in the previous section, even if academia and industries share a common interest in active suspensions, their efforts point to opposite directions. Industries are investing in suspension actuators that can offer advanced body control during manoeuvres, i.e., load transfers, and rough road travelling, i.e., ride comfort. Much attention is also devoted to easy integration in the conventional suspension archetypes; in fact, all the commercial available active shock absorbers take advantage of the classic hydraulic damper to transmit the controlled force. The passive hydraulic component is modified to place an add-on power source, as pumps or mechanical transmissions driven by motors. This translates into a small increase in unsprung mass weight, but the suspension arms, hence the elasto-kinematics, remain the same as the passive archetype.

Instead, academia is focusing more on the energetic aspect related to this technologies and to advanced control techniques. Particular interest arises from the harvesting capabilities, i.e., the possibility of partially recovering the kinetic energy coming from road irregularities. Nonetheless, proposed prototypes are often bulky or require strong modifications in the suspension geometry.

Therefore, a significant discrepancy exists between these two entities. This doctoral thesis aims to bridge this gap, at least partially, by proposing a system-level methodology to design an active electromagnetic shock absorber for any wheeled vehicle. Specifically, (i) vehicle integration and (ii) optimal components design are priorities to build a compact, efficient, controllable shock absorber that can optimally fit into existing suspension archetypes. The proposed component can work in the four force-speed quadrants, hence consuming or regenerating power. Depending on the control strategy, regenerative power can minimize the average power consumption due to active operations, or it can charge the vehicle battery. The latter could be an important advantage for BEVs and HEVs to increase their ranges.

The proposed methodology adopts a V-model approach (Fig. 1.1), with the demo vehicle setup representing the ultimate objective of the entire process. It starts investigating the technology from a theoretical point of view and the suspension

Fig. 1.1 V-model design methodology for electromagnetic shock absorbers.

packaging for the accommodation of the novel component. The latter can be either fully electromechanical or electro-hydrostatic and the choice is guided by the space availability within the suspension. Indeed, the proposed methodology can target both the solutions, although the thesis primarily deals with the electromechanical one due to its more challenging and disruptive nature. Before starting the optimal detailed design, vehicle dynamics simulations set the system requirements in terms of force and speed. The detailed design phase generates the production drawings. Thus, the shock absorber prototypes can be produced, assembled, and fitted to the suspension. An extensive testing campaign on both the prototypes and the vehicle establishes the foundation for validating the proposed technology and evaluating experimentally-tuned innovative suspension controls.

1.2 Thesis outline

The remainder of the work is organized as follows:

- Chapter 2 reviews the state of the art about controllable suspension and electromagnetic shock absorbers. The main focus is the study of the different technological approaches to realize electromagnetic shock absorbers. Both academia and industry are explored.
- Chapter 3 presents the left side of the V-model. The proposed electromagnetic shock absorbers are introduced from a theoretical point of view. An extensive

analysis on vehicle packaging and optimal integration precedes the definition of the system requirements from simple vehicle models and controls. The detailed design of the components and the showcase of the produced prototypes close the chapter.

- Chapter 4 presents the final vehicle setups that are the main output of this doctoral thesis. Then, it provides a complete investigation of the right side of the V-model. The experimental campaign on both prototypes and vehicles is discussed with the goal of validating theoretical models and, in general, the technology. Eventually, some advanced control strategies for the active suspension are studied and tuned for the presented case studies.
- Chapter 5 concludes the manuscript and outlines the future steps of this research.

The present thesis is part of the research on electromagnetic suspensions conducted at LIM Mechatronics Lab (Politecnico di Torino) and CARS (Center for Automotive Research and Sustainable Mobility @ PoliTO) in partnership with Marelli Ride Dynamics and Marzocchi Suspension.

The original contributions with respect to the state of art about electromagnetic shock absorbers for road vehicles are:

- the development of a linear equivalent model to generalize the main mechanical properties of an electromagnetic shock absorber to easily evaluate its dynamic performance;
- the formalization of a rigorous design methodology at vehicle level to optimally design an electromagnetic shock absorber for road vehicle suspensions;
- the validation of the design methodology by installing the designed shock absorbers into the target suspensions and by a proper testing campaign for performance and efficiency assessment;
- the development and validation of a novel quarter-car model including the equivalent linear mechanical behaviour of the deployed electromagnetic shock absorber;
- the design of an H_∞ controller based on the novel quarter-car model;

- the design of a combined sky- and ground-hook predictive control strategy for the bump crossing scenario.

Chapter 2

State of the art

This chapter reviews the state of the art on electromagnetic active suspensions. The first section provides a brief overview about vehicle suspensions, introducing the concept of controllable suspensions. In this macrocategory, electromagnetic shock absorbers represent a possible solution to introduce active and regenerative features. Thus, after introducing their working principle, various designs from industry and academia are described. The goal is to provide a catalogue of possible alternatives to the technologies proposed in the following. In conclusion, the state of research at Politecnico di Torino is introduced, serving as the foundation for this doctoral thesis.

2.1 Vehicle suspensions: categories and features

A vehicle suspension is a deformable mechanism linking the wheel to the vehicle body to allow the simultaneous contact of all the wheels to the ground [36]. The desired compliance is introduced by means of a spring and damper contrasting the relative motion of the two masses. Therefore, the suspension guides both the tire-road interaction, i.e., the generation of the longitudinal and lateral forces, and the insulation of the vehicle cabin from shocks coming from road irregularities. Road holding and comfort are conflicting attributes because the former requires a stiffer suspension to keep a constant vertical force on the tire, guaranteeing a constant contact patch with the ground, while the latter requires a softer tuning to filter uncomfortable vibrations. A trade-off tuning is often reached by properly

Table 2.1 Suspension classification based on its controllability.

Class	Spring control range	Damper control range	Control bandwidth [Hz]	Power request [W]	Control variable
Passive		–	–	–	
Load levelling		0.1-1	100-200	W (static load)	
Adaptive		1-5	10-20	c (damping)	
Semi-active		30-40	10-20	c (damping)	
Slow-active		1-5	$1-5 \times 10^3$	F (force)	
Full-active		20-30	$5-10 \times 10^3$	F (force)	

designing the damping coefficient of the shock absorber, whereas the spring stiffness imposes the natural frequency of the body vertical motion.

Apart from the usual classification based on the different archetypes, a categorization based on the controllability of the system is nowadays spread and summarized in Table 2.1 in terms of control action, bandwidth, and power request [37].

Passive suspensions rely on springs and dampers with fixed characteristics and they are the baseline for normal production. *Load levelling suspensions* deploy low-bandwidth high-power actuators to adjust the spring preload to the vehicle static

load. Manca *et al.* [38] proposed an efficient concept taking advantage of a reversible ball-screw acting on the spring holder.

Adaptive and *semi-active suspensions* discretely adjust the damping coefficient to driving conditions thus still falling into the passivity constraint. Particularly, *semi-active suspensions* are quite widespread in the normal production of high-segment vehicles because they offer a broad and fast controllability (30-40 Hz), e.g., implementing adapted sky-hook or ground-hook control strategies, at acceptable cost and packaging impact [39]. Their technology is usually based on fluids with variable rheology [40, 41], controllable hydraulic pressure loads [42], or solenoid/servo valves [43].

Finally, *slow-active* and *full-active suspensions* can exert forces in all the four quadrants of the force-speed working plane, i.e., they can either introduce or absorb power into the suspension system. As the previous two, they mainly differ in their frequency range because *full-active suspensions* can cover a wider control bandwidth (20-30 Hz) than the *slow-active* ones (1-5 Hz), as also predictable by the names. Thus, the latter are involved in body control [44], while the former can also mitigate comfort-related frequencies for humans (4-8 Hz from ISO 2631 [45]) and wheel resonance frequency range (10-15 Hz [46]).

Xue *et al.* [47] split active suspensions into two groups: hydraulic or pneumatic, and electromagnetic. The former exploit a hydraulic (or pneumatic) actuator, a pump (or a compressor) driven by the vehicular engine or by an electric motor to pressurize the circuit, and some valves to regulate the force provided by the actuator. As a result, they draw continuous power that is subsequently modulated and partially dissipated. A commercial example is given by the first Active Body Control (ABC) system of Mercedes-Benz; each wheel fits a hydraulically-controlled adjusting cylinder in the suspension strut that is supplied by a high-pressure radial piston hydraulic pump. Accumulators and 13 sensors complete the vehicle setup [48]. Nissan also developed its own hydraulic full-active suspension made of hydraulic power cylinders to each wheel, a pump and a reservoir, accumulators, fail-safe, and flow-control valves. Experimental results with this system demonstrated upgrades in both ride comfort on irregular roads and body motion control, i.e., roll, dive, and squat [49]. Electromagnetic active suspensions instead couple an electric machine and a transmission mechanism to actuate the system and they seem to be the future for suspension electrification due to their highest control flexibility and regeneration capability. In

Fig. 2.1 Force-velocity working plane for electromagnetic shock absorbers: regenerative working area (green), active working area (red).

fact, the actual main drawback of active suspensions is the energy consumption, but regeneration can reduce the net required power [50].

For this reason, currently the best power-performance-packaging compromise seem to be given by those suspension systems equipped with both a semi-active damping control and a load-levelling actuator [37]. For example, Koch *et al.* [51] investigated a system joining a slow-active suspension combined to a continuously variable damper. Although high-bandwidth active suspensions still gave the best results in terms of comfort and handling, the proposed system with a proper control strategy significantly improved vehicle performance when compared to passive solutions, remaining competitive in terms of energy, cost, and implementability.

2.2 Electromagnetic shock absorbers

As stated in the previous Section 2.1, electromagnetic suspensions are the utmost development in suspensions electrification. They can enable active features by deploying actuators known as *electromagnetic shock absorbers*; they are basically mechatronic devices coupling an electric machine to a transmission stage, either hydraulic or mechanic. If motion reversibility is guaranteed and a proper power electronics drive the actuator, the electric machine can work as a generator, when the device works as a damper, and as a motor, when it works as an actuator. Therefore, net of losses, all of the energy developed by the electric machine is used to generate forces, unlike other active suspension technologies, which rely on a constant power source that is merely modulated for the task. This working principle is also depicted

in Fig. 2.1, where regenerative (green area) and active (red area) working points are highlighted. It is worth noting that this dissertation adopts the actuator convention. Regenerative working points are tighter than the effective passive quadrants i.e., II and IV. Indeed, mechanical frictions set a lower limit and a constant damping offset, while the intrinsic electrical resistance of the electric machine imposes the regeneration upper limit. More in deep, when the requested force is lower than the minimum damping c_{\min} , active power is needed to overcome the internal frictions. This limit can be experimentally identified testing the shock absorber with open-circuit electric machine and it is fundamental to study fail-safe operations. Contrarily, the maximum damping c_{\max} is identified shunting the electric machine phases; indeed, short-circuited motor phases have the lowest possible resistance that translates into the maximum winding current, hence the maximum braking torque. This limit can be overcome by introducing active power, too.

The first feasibility studies on using electrodynamic dampers for automotive suspensions were conducted by Karnopp [52] in 1989. The basis of this research originates from Lorentz force law and Faraday's law of induction. In fact, relative motion between a uniform magnetic field and a coil connected to an external resistance generates an induced voltage and a force opposing to the magnetic flux variation, hence to the relative velocity. With a good approximation, the induced force F_d is linearly dependant to the relative velocity v_d and the proportionality coefficient is proportional to the inverse of the total electrical resistance R_{tot} , that is the sum of the coil resistance R_c and the external resistance R_{ext} . This relation is made explicit in Eq. (2.1).

$$\frac{F_d}{v_d} \propto -\frac{1}{R_c + R_{\text{ext}}} \quad (2.1)$$

The external resistance R_{ext} can be continuously varied by a controllable power electronics. From Eq. (2.1), open circuit damping c_{\min} ($R_{\text{ext}} \rightarrow \infty$) and short circuit damping c_{\max} ($R_{\text{ext}} = 0$) are also demonstrated.

2.2.1 Industrial applications

As already mentioned in Section 1.1, the very first industrial application of electromagnetic shock absorbers was developed by Bose Corporation. They prototype what Karnopp only formulated in [52] through the use of a linear multipole motor as controllable damper in a suspension system [53]. Substantially, it resembles a normal

Fig. 2.2 Commercial electromagnetic shock absorber: (a) ClearMotion electrotramagnetic shock absorber [54, 55], (b) Ferrari TrueActive™ Spool Valve shock absorber [57, 58].

hydraulic damper but the inner element has permanent magnets while the outer body has field windings. The relative force is generated by controlling amplitude and polarity of the currents in the coils. The arrangement minimizes the moving mass by using salient poles. Nevertheless, this proposal never found a production outlet.

ClearMotion is currently the leader in the production of electromagnetic shock absorbers. Their product incorporates a hydraulic actuator to a conventional shock absorber, as shown in Fig. 2.2a. The actuator consists of a rotary electric machine, a fixed-displacement pump, hydraulic lines and controls by means of check valves, a reservoir, and integrated power electronics [54]. The selected pump typology is a gerotor pump and the selected motor is a surface permanent magnet (SPM) motor [55]. It was initially presented as a regenerative shock absorber with controllable damping, capable of converting the road vibrational energy into electrical energy, but in case of a coupling with a monotube damper, motion reversibility would allow also active features. In fact, the pump feeds independently the two chambers and it can create a differential pressure in order to contrast the damper piston motion or to force it in the desired direction.

The current trend is shifting toward fully electromechanical technologies to enhance efficiency, expand controllable bandwidth, and promote greener, oil-free solutions. As early as 2004, Nissan patented an electromagnetic damper embedding a rotary motor and a ball-screw mechanism [56]. The motor is internally flanged to the shock absorber body and rigidly, concentrically connected to the ball-screw shaft, while the ball-screw nut is mounted on the shock absorber sliding element. As expected, the ball-screw mechanism enables a highly efficient rotary-to-linear conversion. As this kind of systems are characterized by a non-negligible inertia

affecting their dynamic response, Nissan patented also the method to estimate the internal inertia force by using the estimation of the suspension stroke acceleration and the measured motor speed. This force sums up to the desired control force, which serves as reference for the motor. In this way, Nissan claims to reduce overshoots in sprung mass displacement step response and the sprung mass acceleration gain in the comfort frequency range.

Ferrari follows a similar approach in their innovative TrueActive™ Spool Valve suspension (Fig. 2.2b), developed in collaboration with Multimatic. This system also incorporates additional components on a conventional damper tube, including a 48V motor with an integrated electronic control unit and a conversion mechanism that generates forces within the damping element, hence the suspension [57]. The motor is a liquid cooled, 48V three-phase brushless electric machine, while the conversion mechanism is a twin-lead ball screw coupled to gearbox assembly. The motor and the lead screw have parallel axes, and the gearbox compensates for the spacing between the axes. Also in this product, the lead screw is rigidly and coaxially connected to the damper piston rod in order to apply the desired forces. However, hydraulic damping is still present and regulated by two independent spool valves, each controlling one of the two chambers [58].

An unconventional application was presented by Audi AG in 2016; their eRot technology consists in an axle equipped with a rotary electromechanical actuator on each side [59]. A lever arm guarantees the connection to the wheel and the control of the vehicle body motion. The actuator comprises a 48V motor and a gear unit. Further promoted features are the damping control and the energy recovery [60]. A similar concept debuted on the luxury model of Audi A8 in 2019, announced as a predictive active suspension [61]. The system still includes electromechanical actuator but the geartrain is substituted by a belt drive and a harmonic drive. At the front suspension, it acts on the spring strut; while at the rear suspension, on the transverse link. Apart from the previously mentioned features, this system takes advantage of a camera at the front bumper to adjust the vehicle attitude up to 85 mm. The average power consumption predicted by Audi is 10–200 W.

Another intriguing concept was proposed by Michelin in 1996 [62]; they proposed the active wheel concept joining both electric traction and active suspension functionalities inside the wheel hub. Two independent motor would command the two dynamics. Even if this project was interrupted in 2014 due to weight increment,

space requirements, and economic costs [63], the industrial interest toward the smart corner concept for EVs is still strong.

In conclusion, apart from Audi eRot, it is clear that the automotive industry is trying to envelope novel active features in conventional shock absorber bodies in order to avoid any impactful modification to the suspension arms and chassis. Moreover, the actual target is the enhancement in terms of comfort by controlling low-frequency body motion and the suspension damping.

2.2.2 Academic research

In these days, every scientific field concerns for more efficient and sustainable technologies. In academic research on electromagnetic shock absorbers, the emphasis is on their regenerative capabilities to improve vehicle fuel efficiency [34] and extend the range of EVs [64]. The fuel efficiency improvement strongly depends on the vehicle mass, the travelling speed, and the road conditions; it ranges from 2-3% for passenger cars to 7-10% of energy efficiency for EVs [34]. As a result, prototypes emerging from academic studies are primarily optimized for conversion efficiency rather than power and force capacity.

Reviews on the scientific outcomes primarily classify electromagnetic shock absorbers based on their kinetic energy conversion mechanism into *linear*, *hydraulic*, and *rotary* types [65], or more specifically, according to the technology used for this conversion [66].

Linear types

This configuration is based on electromagnetic induction due to the relative motion of a magnetic flux gradient and a conductor, as theorized by Karnopp [52] (Fig. 2.3).

The general idea is to retrofit conventional shock absorbers by adding permanent magnets to the sliding element and placing coils on the damper rod, that is usually fixed to the vehicle chassis, allowing easy integration with power electronics. For instance, Zuo *et al.* [67] utilized 12 rare-earth permanent magnets and high-permeability magnetic loops to design a four-phase linear generator within a conventional damper tube. As shown in Fig. 2.4a, it took advantage of a magnet

Fig. 2.3 Linear electromagnetic shock absorbers working principle with moving magnets [52]. x linear displacement, δ coil thickness, L_c coil length, L_m magnet length, \bar{R} mean radius of the coil.

Fig. 2.4 Examples of linear electromagnetic dampers proposed by (a) Zuo *et al.* [67], (b) Gysen *et al.* [69].

assembly over a guiding rod inside the moving damper body and a hollow stator. Tests on a half-scale prototype highlighted a harvested mean power of 2 and 8 W at 0.25 and 0.5 m/s root mean square (RMS) suspension speed, respectively. Also, Sultoni *et al.* [68] studied an 8-magnets arrangement on the damper rod with coils on the damper cylinder. Quarter-car simulations on C-class road at 50 km/h resulted in a regenerated power of 45 W, but tests on a full-scale prototype excited with an oscillating speed of 0.1 m/s, corresponding to the RMS velocity of the suspension in the previously mentioned scenario, attained an average power of 11.43 W with peak of 45 W. Instead, Gysen *et al.* [69] retrofitted a BMW 530i damper adding hollow magnets on the damper body and a slotted 3-phase stator to the rod, as visible in Fig. 2.4b. Thanks to the regeneration capabilities, a consumption of only 47 W was measured on a quarter-car test rig with a comfort-oriented control.

Many other more complex designs try to increase the conversion efficiency and the power density. Zhang *et al.* [70] applied a rack and pinion mechanism to increase the magnet speed with respect to the coils for higher power output; a maximum of 54 W can be generated with the optimal selection of the coil mass and mechanism amplification factor 3. Duong and Chun [71] studied different arrangements, with 3 or 11 phases and with stainless or magnetic steel cover, of 12-slot 10-pole tubular linear machine with exterior magnets to retrofit a school bus damper. FEM analysis evidenced the best results for the 11 phases topology with magnetic steel cover when excited by a sinusoidal displacement with an RMS speed of 0.25 m/s, reaching 152.99 W of average power, 314.53 W of maximum power, and 2020.76 N of maximum electromagnetic force. Lee *et al.* [72] instead explored the Halbach array on an 8-slot 8-pole linear synchronous machine, reaching 69 W of average mechanical power, with peaks of 225 W, and 92% of conversion efficiency during sinusoidal tests with 0.25 m/s speed. Also Tran *et al.* [73] included a linear electromagnetic damper, combining Halbach array and iron spacers, in a motorbike front fork. Under the design conditions of 0.157 m/s vibration speed, the maximum and average power computed are 626.7 W and 124 W, respectively. Tang *et al.* [74] designed different layouts of the prototype by Zuo, and the double-layer with both axial and radial magnets typology reached a power density up to 5.6 times higher than the original, a potential power regeneration of 33 W when excited at 0.25 m/s, and damping capability comparable to automotive standards. Lastly, a curious design was proposed by Sapiński and Krupa [75] because they coupled a simple linear generator to a magnetorheological damper to null its power consumption.

A serious weakness of linear electromagnetic shock absorbers is represented by the absence of a fail-safe damping when either an external resistance or a power electronics controlling the winding currents is disconnected from the linear electric machine. In fact, fail-safe damping coincides with the open-circuit one and it is fundamental to guarantee a minimum level of driveability. As stated in Section 2.2, open-circuit damping arises just from residual mechanical frictions and cogging phenomena, that however should be both minimized as much as possible to increase conversion efficiency. To overcome this issue, often a hydraulic damper is still included in the proposed suspension. An example is given by Wang *et al.* [76], where the electromagnetic damper is tuned to fulfil comfort or handling targets. However, power consumption arose with those tunings, while efficiency in regeneration configuration reached just a 20%. A more efficient configuration was proposed by Zhou *et al.* [77] adding a 3-phase voice coil damper to a passive suspension. Experimentally, a maximum harvesting efficiency of 67% was reached with a sinusoidal input at 6 Hz and 2 mm amplitude.

Finally, while linear systems can be easily integrated into existing suspension layouts, they exhibit poor damping capability and low force density, resulting in bulky and costly designs.

Hydraulic types

This configuration usually includes a double-acting cylinder, a hydraulic motor, an electrical generator, and possibly accumulators and check valves, with hydraulic oil serving as the working fluid. The hydraulic fluid drives the reciprocating motion of the cylinder, which is connected to a hydraulic motor, either inducing the linear movement of the magnetic coil or rotating the generator to produce electricity. The basic working principle is shown in Fig. 2.5. They offer excellent mechanical robustness and minimal noise, with intrinsic lubrication that addresses the primary tribology concerns. Moreover, hydraulic transmissions achieve very high force and power amplification in affordable spaces.

Many examples are reported in the literature but each case has its own peculiarities. Fang *et al.* [78] translated in hydraulic terms the principle of the Wheatstone bridge; to transform the reciprocating motion of the hydraulic cylinder due external stimulus, into a rectified oil flow into the hydraulic motor, two check valves and one accumulator are located on both the hydraulic lines connecting to the two

Fig. 2.5 Working principle of a hydraulic electromagnetic shock absorber [81].

chambers of the cylinder. They rose the attention on the presence of air or gas in the circuit and on possible external leakages, because the former decrements force capability, the latter gradually reduces the circuit pressure causing cavitation. The energy-regenerative characteristic of this prototype could reach about 200 watts with a 10 Hz-3 mm excitation. However, the energy recovery efficiency was only 16.6% due to the high losses in the hydraulic rectifier, increasing with the excitation frequency. The same hydraulic electromagnetic damper architecture was designed for heavy duty vehicles [79], with experimental results showing that the damping coefficient could range from 32 to 91 kNs/m, covering most of the damping range of 25–50 kNs/m for typical heavy-duty trucks. The average regenerative power reached 220 W and the corresponding hydraulic efficiency reached 30% with a vibration input of 3 Hz frequency and 7 mm amplitude. Test also evidenced a more rectangular force–displacement loops with respect to conventional dampers and that the accumulator force greatly counteracted the inertia force. The latter is a parasitic phenomenon existing in all rotary regenerative shock absorbers, that deteriorates the suspension dynamics when exceeding a certain range. An optimized version was studied by Gong *et al.* [80]; they reduced the number of check valves to one per line and one in between, and the accumulator was connected only to the rebound chamber. Experiments found that the maximum damping force was 4516 N, with a difference of only 3.23% to simulations, and very similar damping characteristics to traditional shock absorbers, making the prototype a reliable example for the automotive sector. This unit could be optimized on the basis of simulation results on quarter-car models, reaching an RMS power saving ranging from 10 to 160 W, depending on road condition and travelling speed, with even a marginally improved ride comfort compared to the traditional damper. Zhang *et al.* [81] integrated a hydraulic generator unit to

a twin-tube damper, which guarantees a unidirectional flow to the hydraulic motor thanks to its typical working principle. A prototype was tested with a maximum excitation speed 0.52 m/s, reaching a peak regenerated power of about 200 W, with an average of 110.6 W. Wang *et al.* [82] reached a recoverable power of 260 W with an efficiency of around 40% under sinusoidal excitation of 1 Hz and 25 mm amplitude. Eventually, Guntur *et al.* [83] added a second hydraulic generator unit in series with the usual one to boost efficiency and increase the output electricity. The second generator showed higher and more stable output voltage.

A different approach was developed by Kim and Kim [84] because they installed a bladed piston into the typical damper structure. The blades suppress vibrations instead of the normal piston orifices, while they also set in rotation a rotary electrical generator enclosed in the shock absorber structure. The architecture was simulated in a CarSim vehicle model running on a rough road, resulting in a mean RMS damper speed over the four corner of 0.21 m/s. This speed could generate approximately 59 W in the optimized damper solution. However, using a continuous average speed to drive the generator in the simulation environment is misleading for a system subjected to alternating motion.

Ultimately, although the conventional use of hydraulic dampers could facilitate the immediate implementation of hydraulic electromagnetic shock absorbers, these systems generally exhibit low conversion efficiencies due to localized hydraulic losses in each additional component. Moreover, the most commonly tested solutions rely on motion rectification, which inhibits the possibility of active control, thereby marginal ride comfort improvements could be obtained even by optimized configurations.

Rotary types

This configuration converts the vertical reciprocating motion of the vehicle suspension into bidirectional rotary motion using different mechanical motion conversion mechanisms (Fig. 2.6).

A straightforward solution is to replace the conventional hydraulic piston with a ball-screw mechanism, thus the ball nut is fixed to the reciprocating element of the damper, spinning the screw and the motor connected to it. This technology shows good packaging possibilities, high reliability, small size, and high conversion

Fig. 2.6 Examples of rotary electromagnetic dampers: ball-screw transmission by Zaho *et al.* [85], (b) rack and pinion transmission by Li *et al.* [88].

efficiency, but wear and tear reduce the durability of the system. Zhao *et al.* [85] manufactured a prototype of this kind (Fig. 2.6a). Tests on a shaker test rig demonstrated an average recovered power ranging from 37 to 80 W for excitation at 0.5 Hz and from 250 to 350 at 1 Hz, depending on the charging voltage. Regeneration is mainly affected by the "zero zone" phenomenon, i.e., the electromagnetic force is null in the vicinity of the speed zero point. Moreover, this kind of damper is affected by a large equivalent inertia (about 147 kg) critical for vibration exciting the actuator natural frequency, reducing the effective desired electromagnetic force. Therefore they considered to introduce an additional vibration-reduction structure between the bottom of the actuator and the unsprung mass to attenuate the vibration acceleration from the wheel, but simulations evidenced that 75% of the recoverable power is absorbed by this element, leaving only a 13% to the motor. The rest is loss due to Coulomb friction in the shock absorber. Liu *et al.* [86] added two one-way clutches to the ball-screw mechanism to realize a mechanical motion rectifier. It achieved high energy-harvesting efficiency because the generator rotates at a relatively steady speed during irregular vibrations, hence the "zero zone" phenomenon is avoided. It also improved system reliability by reducing impact forces deriving from motion inversion. Laboratory tests evidenced total energy harvesting efficiencies ranging from 25 to 52%, depending on the excitation amplitude and frequency, and the added external resistance. Moreover, road tests at 40 mph on a paved road evidenced an average recovery power of 24.7 W per corner. An evolution of the ball-screw mechanism is proposed by Salman *et al.* [87]; they installed a helical pinion shaft with two helix hands that transfer the suspension vibration to helical gears connected to a

generator module. The use of two helix hands and clutches allows the unidirectional motion of the generator. Experiments showed a peak efficiency of 52% and average efficiency of 40%; an average power of 270 W was obtained from the full-scale prototype shock absorber at a vibrational frequency input of 2.5 Hz and an amplitude of 5 mm.

The rack and pinion mechanism operates on the same principle, enclosed within a conventional damper structure. The rack is fixed to the moving component, while the pinion is connected to a motor attached to the constrained component. Also this possibility offers good packaging possibilities and efficiency for small strokes, at the cost of a pronounced sensitivity to wear. Li *et al.* [88] encapsulated a rack and pinion mechanism in a conventional damper structure (Fig. 2.6b); three bevel gears and two roller clutches were added to create a motion rectifier for the generator module. It achieved a mechanical efficiency of over 60%. It also harvested average powers of 40.4 and 25.6 W, depending on the external resistive load, under vibrations of 0.047 m/s RMS velocity. Simulations and experiments demonstrated that a higher recoverable power is reachable with a higher input frequency because the corresponding efficiency is higher. Furthermore, it was tested also on road tests, during which an average power of 15.4 W is recovered at 15 mph on a smooth paved road. A completely reversible, thus active, solution was developed by The University of Texas Center for Electromechanics. It was designed for military vehicles, embodying a brushless servomotor, a gearbox, and a rack and pinion mechanism [89]. Tests on a quarter-car test rig demonstrated a peak force of 11 kN, a continuous force of 2 kN, and a maximum velocity of 1 m/s within an overall stroke of 12.7 cm. Preliminary vehicle tests proved a 2.5 reduction of the sprung mass vertical acceleration and displacement compared to the passive vehicle when crossing a single bump, and a virtually null roll and pitch motion during turning and braking/accelerating, respectively [90].

Cable transmissions are less common, but few examples are still being investigated. For example, González *et al.* [91] developed a prototype of energy harvesting shock absorber for motorcycles, deploying a pulley transmission to power a generator module. On a typical B-class road at 60 km/h an average regenerated power of 19.68 W was estimated. Instead, Bowen *et al.* [92] proposed a quite more complex arrangement of pulleys to power the generator of the electromagnetic damper. Test results showed a square mean value of regenerated power of 105 W, when driving at

Fig. 2.7 Examples of linkage-based rotary electromagnetic dampers proposed by (a) Arana *et al.* [93, 94], (b) Yu *et al.* [95, 96].

a speed between 20 and 30 km/h, and power peaks of 400–500 W, when crossing a speed bump. The system achieved an efficiency of about 60%.

Ultimately, linkage-based solutions require a more disruptive approach, as their installation impacts the entire suspension architecture. However, their straightforward motion reversibility avoids to limit their study for only recovery features. The research group led by Dr. Evangelou developed two possible linkage configurations for active variable geometry suspension systems. The first is a series configuration [93, 94], in which a single link connects the chassis to the spring-damper assembly (Fig. 2.7a). The second is a parallel configuration [95, 96], where a rocker-pushrod linkage acts on the suspension lower arm in parallel to the spring-damper assembly (Fig. 2.7b). As results of simulations on a quarter-car model of the rear suspension of a Grand Tourer (GT) vehicle, the series configuration showed power consumption ranging from 89 W on smooth roads to 141 W on rough roads travelled at 100 km/h with a comfort-oriented control strategy, reaching a 15–23% reduction of the chassis RMS acceleration with respect to the passive case [93]. Even full-car simulations confirm similar percentage in chassis acceleration in the center of mass, together with consistently reduced pitch acceleration [93]. Additionally, further tuning on the constant exogenous lever position led to an average power consumption of 73 W on the smooth road and an acceleration reduction of about 30%, suggesting that a higher-level control could improve vehicle performance and actuator power consumption based on the level of road irregularities, vehicle characteristics and velocity, and actuator characteristics [93]. In contrast, the parallel configuration achieves the same acceleration reduction while consuming only 0.93 kW of total

average power from the four corners, based on full-vehicle simulations on road class C for the GT car [96]. A crank-lever mechanism was explored by Todmal and Melzi [97] to connect a brushless direct current motor with a three-stage parallel spur gear reducer to the suspension. From simulation results, this assembly could reach a maximum overall regeneration efficiency of 87%, with an average generated power between 141 and 358 for a vehicle running on a country road with a velocity ranging from 20 to 50 km/h. Also Gu *et al.* [98] proposed a crank-pushrod to interface an electromagnetic rotary actuator to the suspension; experimental verification proved the regeneration feasibility under different speeds, for example driving over a bump at 1.4 m/s allowed to regenerate an average power of 51.1 W. They also addressed the introduction of additional inertia in the suspension, resulting from the motion transmission ratio and the motor rotating inertia. To account for this effect, they modelled it as an added mass on the unsprung mass. Alternatively, the proposal by Jonasson and Roos [99] took advantage of the upper control arm to convert the vertical motion of the wheel into rotary motion of an electromagnetic damper, including a levelling actuator in parallel on the same rotational axis. While the acceleration of the vehicle body could be affectively reduced, frequencies around the wheel-hop frequency show a more limited controllability. Hence, they proposed to add a small linear passive damper in parallel, allowing to also reduce the motor size. Numerical studies on different pavé roads, including internal losses in the actuator modelling, revealed a tendency for energy regeneration in both handling (-1.4 kJ over 10 s) and comfort (-3.8 kJ over 10 s) control configurations. Finally, more complex linkage mechanism have been also studied, as the four-link system by Gijón-Rivera [100] but challenges arose in ensuring that the mechanism avoids singular positions.

In the end, the absence of any working fluid and the highest efficiency among the presented technologies are making rotary electromechanical solutions much more attractive than the others. The main common drawback is the large equivalent inertia introduced in the suspension and affecting its dynamics. Rack and pinion solutions particularly suffer backlash, hence few solutions can be found in the literature. Instead, ball-screw solutions tend to be bulky due to the additional mechanical components in the damper tube. Linkage-based rotary electromechanical shock absorbers feature very large efficiency, compact and lightweight layout, good mechanical robustness, and moderate equivalent inertia. However, challenges derive from the noise level due to the presence of gearbox stages and from vehicle integra-

Fig. 2.8 Current research lines at PoliTO: electro-mechanical and electro-hydrostatic.

tion because it is no longer a modification within the conventional shock absorber tube.

2.2.3 Research at PoliTO

Research at LIM Mechatronics Lab (Politecnico di Torino) delved into electromagnetic shock absorbers from 2010, specifically for automotive applications. Currently, two main technologies are pursued: a more recent fully electro-mechanical and a more common electro-hydrostatic. As shown in Fig. 2.8, they share the same power input, i.e., a rotary electric machine, but they differ in the transmission system to realize the linear power onto the suspension.

The first studies exploited a ball-screw transmission encapsulated in a damper tube [101]. The proposed technology could replace the shock absorber in a MacPherson front suspension for a C-segment vehicle. A rotary electric motor is housed in the larger-diameter section near the upper strut mounts. A screw is then rigidly connected to the moving piston to realize the linear-to-rotary motion conversion. Additionally, the rotor of the electric motor and the ball-screw nut are directly connected to reduce the axial length of the device by utilizing the space inside the motor rotor. The force-speed characteristic covers all the possible hydraulic damper tunings and it easily reaches a peak power in the range of 2.5 kW i.e., 2500 N at 1 m/s. The impedance frequency response of this device has a typical low-pass filter behaviour and it is influenced by a mechanical resonant frequency of approximately 70 Hz when the motor phases are shunted with high external resistances, whereas it is dominated by the frequency of the electromagnetic pole when low resistances are used. Indeed, the electrical pole depends on the ratio between the total phase resistance and the inductance of the motor, while the mechanical pole depends on the square root of the ratio between the stiffness and the inertia of the actuator. For instance, as already

Fig. 2.9 Prototypes of electromagnetic shock absorbers at PoliTO: (a) electro-hydrostatic solution, (b) rotary electro-mechanical solution.

introduced in Section 2.2, shunting the phases results in the lowest possible phase resistance and, consequently, lowest electrical pole ($= 53 \text{ Hz}$). As it also results in the highest reachable passive damping, the resulting impedance frequency response has the highest static gain and then it cuts out the mechanical resonant peak as the electrical pole frequency is overcome. On the contrary, adding an external resistance of 50Ω brings the electrical pole to 783 Hz and the static gain to the value of the mechanical damping due to internal frictions, thus the mechanical behaviour dominates. Regardless of this, the mean recoverable power is in the range of $200\text{--}300 \text{ W}$. A very similar device was also studied for the aerospace sector, specifically for landers and rover suspensions, because during landing it could work as a damper, assuring a safe landing and energy dissipation, while after landing, it could adjust the attitude [102]. All this studies converged in a prototype for off-road vehicles [103]. The experimental impedance frequency response highlighted a resonant peak at about 40 Hz , but it can be attenuated imposing electromagnetic damping. Overall, the prototype fulfilled the damping requirements inside a bandwidth of 60 Hz and the very low mechanical losses (19.3% at 1 Hz in open circuit) proved the optimal regeneration capabilities.

Subsequent research focused on hydraulic electromagnetic shock absorber by leveraging on hydrostatic transmissions. More specifically, a rotary electric machine is coupled to a gerotor pump directly interfaced onto a hydraulic shock absorber, as shown in Fig. 2.9a. The gerotor could work either as a pump, when driven by the motor, or as a hydraulic motor, driving the electric machine as a generator. Thus, imposing a differential pressure in the chambers of the hydraulic damper, the internal piston exerts active or damping linear forces at the damper top mount. The very

first iteration applied this technology on a twin-tube damper. Its particular working principle allowed only unidirectional rotation of the motor-pump unit because the fluid flow is rectified by the aperture of the base check valve during rebound, and by the piston check valve during compression. As a consequence, only regenerative functionalities were explored. The regeneration area is lower-bounded by the mechanical frictions and upper-bounded by the hydraulic leakages. The optimization of the motor-pump unit, in terms of electromagnetic design, gear and port geometries, and clearances, yielded to a maximum experimental regeneration efficiency of 41.7% [104]. Instead, from numerical analysis, the maximum conversion efficiency was 48.7%. The difference can be mainly attributed to larger hydro-mechanical losses, that are also the most critical design aspect. This phenomenon can be motivated by the pump axial and radial motion within the clearance gaps, that leads to an increased viscous drag. An additional optimization step was performed by Puliti *et al.* [105]. Firstly, the novel design considered a through-rod cylinder to enable also active forces. A genetic algorithm was applied to solve an optimization problem between compactness and efficiency as a function of the shock absorber geometrical properties. The optimal solution highlighted a maximum numerical regeneration efficiency of 56%, but an experimental one of 45% due to manufacturing tolerances, wear of the rotating elements, thermal expansion of the components, and secondary leakages paths. In the following, the hydrostatic damper will be referred to as EHA.

The most recent research interest prioritizes efficiency and oil-free technologies to reduce petroleum-based products and pollution through leaks, disposal issues, and emissions. Therefore, a rotary electromechanical shock absorber was developed [106] (Fig. 2.9b). It is a linkage-based rotary solution characterized by custom-designed electric machine and double-stage planetary gearbox to reduce weight and equivalent inertia. Experimentally, a maximum total conversion efficiency of about 60% was found with a very high maximum damping capability (11.3 kNs/m). Dealing with many rotating gears, an acoustic investigation was also performed, resulting in a maximum sound pressure level of 49.63 dBA, lower than the United States Environmental Protection Agency 24-hour exposure limit of 55 dBA. In the following, the rotary shock absorber will be referred to as RSA.

Both the EHA and the RSA solutions gained industrial interest. A performance comparison based on the produced prototypes is necessary to understand strengths and weaknesses and it is summarized in Table 2.2 [107]. In terms of mechanical robustness and fatigue, the EHA solution offers an advantage due to the intrinsic

Table 2.2 Qualitative comparison among PoliTO electromagnetic shock absorbers

Feature	Electro-hydrostatic (EHA)	Rotary (RSA)
Mechanical robustness & fatigue	●	◐
Efficiency	◐	●
Mass	◐	◐
Equivalent inertia	○	◐
Oil-free	○	◐
Noise	◐	○
Packaging	◐	○

Optimal	Acceptable	Lacking
●	◐	○

lubrication of the rotating components. Additionally, gerotor pumps are known for generating very low relative angular velocities between the contacting parts. In contrast, even if the RSA is lubricated with transmission oil, the compactness targets and the continuous motion inversion make the fatigue design of the gearbox very challenging. When it comes to efficiency, the EHA damper is significantly less efficient and operates within a narrower efficiency range due to the increased friction from tight clearances and hydraulic leakages and losses. In terms of overall mass, they are quite comparable since the EHA shows a very high force density, but its weight sums up with the damper tube. However, the EHA is mounted on the unsprung mass, thereby having a more pronounced impact on vertical dynamics. Instead, the RSA need a slightly larger volume and number of components, i.e., two stages and linkages, to reach the same force targets, but it can take advantage of the removal of the hydraulic shock absorber and the distribution of its weight on both the sprung and unsprung masses. However, implementing a RSA could necessitate a complete redesign of the vehicle suspension. Regarding the dynamic behaviour, the EHA system has an higher equivalent inertia than RSA because of the large moment of inertia of the gerotor gears, that spin jointly with the motor shaft at high speeds. In the RSA instead, the overall inertia decreases because the pitch diameter of the high-speed sun is comparable to that of the motor shaft. All the other rotating elements of the gearbox contribute less due to the several intermediate transmission ratios. This inertia becomes significant at higher frequencies, as it tends to lock

the suspension, eventually requiring active attenuation through the control system. Regarding noise, the presence of fluid helps attenuate sound emissions from gerotor gears meshing in the EHA, while the RSA suffers of higher acoustic emissions due to the number of meshing gears and its rigid connection to chassis.

The research presented up to now primarily focused on actuator optimization and characterization, with the main objective of energy regeneration for fuel savings. However, this doctoral thesis aims to further explore the optimal integration of electromagnetic shock absorbers into vehicle suspensions, emphasizing their active features to enhance vehicle dynamics. By doing so, these technologies could achieve a higher level of maturity and greater appeal for industrial applications. In this direction, a first methodology was developed by Circosta [108] for his doctoral dissertation, proposing a system-level design methodology for the installation of a RSA on rear swing arm of a motorbike.

Chapter 3

Design methodology

The following chapter will describe the design methodology developed to optimally integrate electromagnetic shock absorbers into existing suspension systems. The case studies involve two different types of suspensions: the rear suspension of a D-class sport utility vehicle (SUV) and the front fork of a naked motorcycle.

The approach begins by investigating the two main technologies developed at PoliTO in terms of their dynamic response to understand the expected performance. For each case study, a thorough examination of the packaging constraints is necessary to select the most suitable technology. Specifically, the RSA is chosen for the SUV due to the larger available space, while the EHA is preferred for the motorcycle to ensure compatibility with the existing suspension design. Additionally, the rear suspension of the SUV offers an opportunity for optimizing the linkage mechanism design.

Once the positions of the actuators on the suspensions are determined, simple linear simulations of vehicle dynamics are conducted to establish the key requirements in terms of forces and speeds. These serve as inputs for a global optimization procedure for the actuator, which provides the essential geometrical and performance characteristics required for the detailed design of the individual components.

Fig. 3.1 Equivalent linear mechanical model of an electromagnetic shock absorber.

3.1 Investigation and packaging

The first step of the proposed methodology seeks (i) to understand the dynamic behaviour of the previous RSA and EHA for determining the key design parameters and the expected actuators performance, (ii) to investigate the target suspensions for the installation in order to choose to most suitable technology and optimize its packaging.

3.1.1 Ideal linear model

From Section 2.2.3, an optimal full-active solution is difficult to identify and the final choice often depends on a trade-off between desired performance and available space. A general model could help in lumping the main mechanical features to estimate a priori the main dynamic features characterizing an electromagnetic actuator: its force bandwidth and its impedance. The former determines the actuator capability of applying the desired force in the desired frequency range; the latter describes how its mechanical arrangement determines its passive response to external excitations.

An equivalent linear mechanical model of an electromagnetic damper is the best tool to lump the actuator inertial, dissipative, and elastic characteristics, as shown in Fig. 3.1 [109]. In particular, the equivalent viscous damping c_{eq} accounts for the internal friction of the moving parts, while the equivalent mass m_{eq} represents their inertial properties. The damping coefficient c_l captures leakages in the hydraulic circuit and becomes infinitely large in fully mechanical solutions, as the RSA. Additionally, a parallel spring–damper system models the compliance of the force–motion transmission to the suspension. These devices typically consist of

multiple stiffness contributions-either mechanical or hydraulic-in series, thus the least stiff component dominates the mount stiffness coefficient k_m . The compliant behaviour also introduces a minor viscous loss, represented by c_m . An ideal force actuator applies the desired force F_a to the system, mimicking the behaviour of the controlled electric machine, but without any dynamics introducing delays and amplitude modifications.. In a purely passive configuration, the electric machine can be connected to an external load R_{ext} . The ideal force actuator in the equivalent model is then replaced by a spring-damper series, depending on the phase inductance L and the total resistance $R_{ph} + R_{ext}$ of the electric machine, respectively, where R_{ph} is the phase resistance [103]. This modelling approach allows to take into account of the electromagnetic dynamics of the passive electric machine. However, if the machine operates under current control with a sufficiently high bandwidth, above 1 kHz as forecast for these devices [110], the ideal force actuator assumption remains valid. Ultimately, the model is balanced by the suspension force F applied at its free end, representing the suspension top mount at wheel level. This general model could describe any technology presented in Section 2.2, but for applications with rotary actuators, a rotary-to-linear kinematic ratio must be defined

$$\tau_\ell = \frac{v}{\omega_{out}} \quad (3.1)$$

where v is the suspension linear relative speed and ω_{out} is the output shaft angular speed. For the EHA, ω_{out} coincides with the electric machine speed ω_{em} , since the driven gear of the gerotor pump is rigidly connected to the motor shaft; whereas for the RSA, ω_{out} coincides with the speed of the output shaft of the gearbox. However, for the EHA, the piston mass must be added to the linear term, too. Consequently, all the rotary parameters can be linearized as follows:

$$m_{eq} = \frac{I_{out}}{\tau_\ell^2} \quad (3.2)$$

$$c_{eq} = \frac{\Gamma_{out}}{\tau_\ell^2} \quad (3.3)$$

where I_{out} combines all the rotating inertias at the output shaft and Γ_{out} linearizes the friction torque at the output shaft as a function of the speed ω_{out} . For the EHA, the piston friction must be added to the linear damping c_{eq} , too. Even the mount stiffness k_m and damping c_m are affected by the factor $1/\tau_\ell^2$ as the torsional stiffness

Table 3.1 Lumped parameters of the EHA and RSA.

Description	Symbol	Value		Unit
		EHA	RSA	
Equivalent damping due to friction	c_{eq}	1220	250	Ns/m
Equivalent mass	m_{eq}	45	6.5	kg
Leakage damping	c_l	$2.7 \cdot 10^4$	∞	Ns/m
Transmission compliance damping	c_m	50	50	Ns/m
Transmission compliance stiffness	k_m	$3.2 \cdot 10^4$	$1.08 \cdot 10^6$	N/m

of the gearbox is included in the parameters. Additional contributions come from the connecting flanges to the vehicle chassis and the linkage system itself.

In Table 3.1, the lumped parameters of the first EHA and RSA prototypes are reported. They were determined by previous experimental campaigns on the actuators and offer a realistic dataset for this preliminary investigation.

By applying the Lagrange's equation, the equations of motion of the model in Fig. 3.1 can be derived:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{q}} \right) - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial q} + \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial \dot{q}} = \frac{\partial \delta W}{\partial \delta q} \quad (3.4)$$

where the Lagrangian term \mathcal{L} is the difference between the kinetic energy of the system \mathcal{T} and the potential energy \mathcal{U} , \mathcal{F} is the dissipated energy, and δW is the virtual work. This model has three degrees of freedom with associated generalized coordinates $q = \{x, x_l, x_{eq}\}^T$ and the terms of Eq. (3.4) can be expressed in their terms as follows:

$$\mathcal{T} = \frac{1}{2} m_{eq} \dot{x}_{eq}^2 \quad (3.5)$$

$$\mathcal{U} = \frac{1}{2} k_m (x - x_l)^2 \quad (3.6)$$

$$\mathcal{F} = \frac{1}{2} c_{eq} \dot{x}_{eq}^2 + \frac{1}{2} c_l (\dot{x}_l - \dot{x}_{eq})^2 + \frac{1}{2} c_m (\dot{x} - \dot{x}_l)^2 \quad (3.7)$$

$$\delta W = F_a \delta x_{eq} - F \delta x \quad (3.8)$$

In the end, the model dynamics is described by the following equations:

$$\begin{cases} k_m(x - x_1) + c_m(\dot{x} - \dot{x}_1) = -F \\ k_m(x - x_1) + c_m(\dot{x} - \dot{x}_1) = c_1(\dot{x}_1 - \dot{x}_{eq}) \\ m_{eq}\ddot{x}_{eq} + c_{eq}\dot{x}_{eq} - c_1(\dot{x}_1 - \dot{x}_{eq}) = F_a \end{cases} \quad (3.9)$$

Combining the equations in Eq. (3.9) in the Laplace domain, the model reduces to a multiple-input, single-output (MISO) expression. The output is the force exerted on the suspension mount $F(s)$, and the two inputs are the speed of the free end $v(s) = s x(s)$ and the actuation force $F_a(s)$:

$$F(s) = \underbrace{\frac{c_1(k_m + s c_m)}{D(s)}}_{H_a(s)} F_a(s) - \underbrace{\frac{c_1(k_m + s c_m)(s m_{eq} + c_{eq})}{D(s)}}_{H_v(s)} v(s) \quad (3.10)$$

where

$$D(s) = c_1(k_m + s c_m) + (s m_{eq} + c_{eq})[k_m + s(c_m + c_1)] \quad (3.11)$$

The MISO expression linearly combines two transfer functions to determine the output force F in the frequency domain. First, the transfer function $H_a(s)$ represents the actuation bandwidth and it is a mechanical filter between the actuation and the output. Then, the transfer function $H_v(s)$ is the mechanical impedance of the device, reducing the effective output force F due to the negative sign in Eq. (3.10).

Given $s = j\omega$, the transfer function $H_a(s)$ describing the output force in response to the actuation force can be represented in the frequency domain. The corresponding plot is shown in Fig. 3.2, comparing the two technologies. While the RSA shows a unitary gain at low frequency, the EHA has slightly lower magnitude gain (≈ 0.96) due to the presence of leakage losses, which hinder the effectiveness of the force transmission. However, considering the unitary gain and the null phase, both the technologies are able to perfectly track the actuation force F_a with the output force F at frequencies lower than the resonance. In fact, two resonant peaks arise, respectively, at 3.6 Hz for the EHA and 65 Hz for the RSA. So, the RSA prototype exhibits a broader actuation bandwidth, spanning more than a decade with respect to the EHA. However, higher losses in the EHA help to attenuate the resonant peak

Fig. 3.2 MISO model: actuation force to output force transfer function $H_a(s)$ in the frequency domain. Magnitude (top) and phase (bottom) responses.

more effectively, thereby limiting unwanted magnitude amplification. The resonance denotes the interaction between inertial (m_{eq}) and stiffness (k_m) terms. At higher frequencies, both systems attenuate the output force F . Notably, the EHA stiffness k_m is two orders of magnitude lower than the RSA. In the EHA, transmission stiffness is primarily influenced by the oil bulk modulus and the volume of the damper chambers, whereas in the RSA, gear tooth stiffness plays a crucial role, as well as the crank bending stiffness and the stiffness of the flanges.

The impedance transfer function $H_v(s)$ is depicted in Figure 3.3. At low frequencies, it is primarily influenced by the internal friction lumped in c_{eq} and the output force F is in phase opposition with the speed v . The presence of leakages again lowers the static gain of the EHA impedance relative to c_{eq} . As the RSA approaches the resonant frequency, the systems tends to act as an inerter. This is evident by the increase in mechanical impedance (self-locking effect) and the phase shifting towards -90 deg. Beyond the resonant peak, a significant attenuation occurs because the transmission compliance k_m dominates.

Fig. 3.3 MISO model: free-end speed to output force transfer function $H_v(s)$ in the frequency domain. Magnitude (top) and phase (bottom) responses.

Single Input Single Output model

The actuation force F_a is usually determined by a suspension-level control strategy. Just focusing on the damping functions of these devices, the simplest strategy is to reproduce the behavior of an ideal viscous damper, i.e., $F_a = -c_a v$. It is also the basic strategy for energy regeneration. From a mathematical standpoint, this choice simplifies Eq. (3.10) by dividing both sides by the free-end speed v . The equation simplifies into a single-input, single-output (SISO) mechanical impedance:

$$Z(s) = -\frac{F(s)}{v(s)} = \frac{(k_m + s c_m)(s m_{eq} + c_{eq} + c_a)}{(k_m + s c_m) + (s m_{eq} + c_{eq})[k_m/c_l + s(c_m/c_l + 1)]} \quad (3.12)$$

It is characterized by a second-order mechanical filter multiplying the damping term $(s m_{eq} + c_{eq} + c_a)$, summing the controlled damping c_a and the dynamic mechanical damping of the system $s m_{eq} + c_{eq}$. For full electro-mechanical shock absorbers, as the RSA, Eq. (3.12) can be further simplified because the leakage term obeys $c_l \rightarrow \infty$.

Fig. 3.4 SISO model: mechanical impedance $Z(s)$ varying the actuation damping c_a : (a) EHA, (b) RSA.

Hence,

$$\lim_{c_1 \rightarrow \infty} Z(s) = \frac{(k_m + sc_m)(sm_{eq} + c_{eq} + c_a)}{m_{eq}s^2 + (c_{eq} + c_m)s + k_m} \quad (3.13)$$

From Eq. (3.13), the second-order filtering behavior is much more distinct.

The two case studies are shown in Fig. 3.4. The actuation damping c_a varies from 0 to 3 kNs/m. The shape follows the transfer function $H_v(s)$ both in module and phase. Specifically, the static gain remains equal to the value of the damping $c_{eq} + c_a$, with minor deviations due to the leakages in c_1 , where present. In both, the action of the actuation damping c_a increases the gain at low frequencies and limits the resonant amplification, since the peak becomes flatter in the EHA and less extreme respect to the static gain in the RSA. Focusing on Fig. 3.4(b), the increase of c_a also hinders the inerter effect of the RSA. In fact, for $c_a = 0$ Ns/m, the impedance phase starts shifting towards $+90^\circ$, meaning that the output force would be in phase with the acceleration of the free-end, but as c_a increases, the phase tends to remain

Table 3.2 Main dynamic features of the EHA and RSA.

Description	Value		Unit
	EHA	RSA	
Resonant peak frequency	3.6	65	Hz
Output force static gain	0.96	1	N/N
Output force resonant gain	1.01	8.85	N/N
Static mechanical impedance gain	1168	250	Ns/m
Resonant mechanical impedance gain	1600	$2.35 \cdot 10^4$	Ns/m
Phase lag before resonance	-209	-106	deg

0° for a broader frequency interval. On the contrary, for the EHA, the increase of c_a causes a small phase lag at low frequencies (Fig. 3.4(a)).

Remarks

The resulting dynamic features of both the EHA and RSA are reported in Table 3.2.

Both the MISO and SISO models spotlight the wider actuation bandwidth offered by the RSA. It is a typical feature of most electro-mechanical shock absorbers, as also revised in Section 2.2.2. This allows classifying the RSA device as a full-active system, capable of controlling both the typical sprung mass natural frequency (~ 1 – 1.5 Hz) and unsprung mass natural frequency (~ 10 – 15 Hz). The latter is particularly crucial when implementing road-holding control strategies. At high frequencies, the tendency of the system to behave as an inerter must be carefully considered, as it may introduce very high out-of-phase forces into the suspension, potentially leading to vehicle instability. Additionally, it significantly amplifies excitations within the noise, vibration, and harshness (NVH) frequency range. The limited internal friction lumped in c_{eq} explains the higher conversion efficiency, as stated in Section 2.2.3, and the low open-circuit damping, as also shown in Fig. 3.3.

Despite its more restricted bandwidth, the EHA can still cover the sprung mass natural frequency and effectively control the comfort frequency range (from 4 to 8 Hz) well enough, particularly when a force feedback control is implemented. Moreover, it can fully manage body motion during handling maneuvers involving pitch and

roll. The higher internal friction and leakage effects in the EHA account for its lower conversion efficiency and higher open-circuit damping. However, the latter is a beneficial characteristic, as it ensures safe vehicle manoeuvrability in the event of an electrical failure, when the force response of those devices depends only on their mechanical impedance.

3.1.2 Packaging investigation and optimization

As the main goal is to offer an optimal tool to implement electromagnetic shock absorbers into any vehicle suspension, the suspension architecture must be carefully examined to (i) identify the best location for the actuator and possible small modifications to the existing suspension components, (ii) avoid any clash with the moving arms, the structural frame, and the steered wheel for the front corner.

Soon after, an optimization algorithm seeks to minimize the linear-to-rotary kinematic ratio τ_ℓ , as this results in more compact actuators. In fact, neglecting all possible losses under ideal conditions, Eq. (3.1) can also be expressed as function of the output torque of the actuator T_{out} and force at the suspension level F .

$$\tau_\ell(x) = \frac{T_{\text{out}}}{F} \quad (3.14)$$

For the same force F , small values of kinematic ratio τ requires a smaller output torque T_{out} . The latter means a smaller combination of gearbox and motor for the RSA, and a smaller motor for the EHA. It is important to highlight that the value of τ_ℓ varies with the suspension stroke x in case of a linkage mechanism.

Automotive rear suspension

The SUV under study is equipped with a patented multi-link suspension (Alfa Link™) on the two rear corners. As visible in Fig. 3.5, the peculiarity is the use of a custom aluminium lower control arm (LCA) instead of two independent links.

The available spaces allows to deploy a properly designed RSA prototype. The packaging investigation must pass three fundamental checks: (i) virtual investigation about the actuator location with focus on the attachment to structural elements and potential clashes with other moving suspension components, (ii) verifications on the

Fig. 3.5 D-class SUV case study: normal production rear suspension.

real vehicle to detect interferences with elements not virtually modelled, such as reservoirs, wirings, hoses, etc., (iii) verifications on the possible interface between the selected suspension arm and the lower ball joint of the pushrod in terms of clashes, structural integrity, and suspension elasto-kinematic behaviour. To this end, dummy envelopes are used and 3D printed. Once the actuator location is chosen, an optimization procedure on the rocker-pushrod linkage mechanism can be executed to determine the mechanism geometrical and kinematic properties. The whole procedure is reported in Fig 3.6.

After some iterations, the location of the RSA main axis of rotation is fixed at the vehicle coordinates $[3007.7, Y_C, -20.1]$ mm (Fig 3.7a). This point represents the intersection of the axis with the motion plane of the linkage. The reference frame follows the convention of body engineers: the X axis is contained in the symmetry plane, set horizontally, pointing rearwards, the Y axis is perpendicular to the symmetry plane, pointing to the right with respect to the driving direction, the Z axis is vertical upwards, and the origin is set in in the middle of the front axle and at the height of the front wheels centre at full load [111]. The coordinate Y_C remains a parameter for the following optimization. The RSA main rotation axis is aligned with the LCA hinge axis. Then, the flanges to connect the RSA to the vehicle frame are intended to be welded onto the suspension subframe, and the linkage mechanism is intended to be fixed to the LCA.

Fig. 3.6 Methodology for packaging investigation.

Fig. 3.7 D-class SUV case study: (a) RSA final location, (b) 2D linkage sketch.

The linkage design methodology aims to find an optimal trade-off configuration to realise the lowest possible kinematic ratio τ_ℓ while ensuring an efficient motion transmission. For a crank-pushrod mechanism, efficient transmission is achieved by maintaining the angle between these two components as close as possible to 90° . At this angle, the force transmitted through the pushrod is almost entirely converted into torque. In the following, this angle will be referred as transmission angle γ . Mathematically, these two targets can be expressed by two objective functions.

$$f_1 = w \frac{\tau_{\ell,\text{nom}}}{\tau_{\ell,\text{max}}} + (1 - w) \frac{\sigma(\tau_\ell)}{\sigma_{\text{max}}} \quad (3.15)$$

$$f_2 = (\gamma_{\text{max}} - 90)^2 + (\gamma_{\text{min}} - 90)^2 \quad (3.16)$$

In more detail, Eq. (3.15) seeks to minimize the kinematic ratio in the suspension nominal position $\tau_{\ell,\text{nom}}$ and the standard deviation of the kinematic ratio $\sigma(\tau_\ell)$. They are normalized with the maximum allowed values $\tau_{\ell,\text{max}}$ and σ_{max} , specifically defined for the case study. The parameter w serves merely as a weighting coefficient because the two targets in Eq. (3.15) are conflicting and it can be chosen between 0 and 1. In fact, very low values of $\tau_{\ell,\text{nom}}$ result in a rather large angular range spanned by the crank, leading to significant variability in τ_ℓ throughout the suspension stroke x . The objective function in Eq. (3.16) targets the transmission efficiency by minimizing the error of both the maximum transmission angle γ_{max} and the minimum γ_{min} from 90° [112]. Indeed, values of γ too much deviated from 90° are more sensitive to manufacturing tolerances, clearances in joints, and thermal expansions, hence noise and jerks at high speed. Moreover, values close either to 0° or 180° exhibit self-locking phenomena [113]. As a rule of thumb, the suggested range should be $90^\circ \pm 50^\circ$.

With reference to Fig. 3.7b, in order to solve the optimization problem, a planar reference frame Oxy must be defined: the plane is orthogonal to the LCA rotational axis, the origin O is also centred in that axis, the y axis is parallel to vehicle Z axis, and the x axis is orthogonal to it. In this reference frame, point C figures the RSA rotation axis, point A the fixing point of the pushrod lower ball joint, point B the pushrod upper ball joint, and $\gamma = \hat{A}BC$. In particular, the vector $\mathbf{X} = [x_B, y_B, x_C]$ groups the design variables for the linkage mechanism.

The multi-objective optimization problem is formulated as

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{X}) &= [f_1(\mathbf{X}) f_2(\mathbf{X})]^T \\ \text{subject to:} & \\ g_i(\mathbf{X}) &\leq 0, \quad i = 1, \dots, 6 \\ \mathbf{X}_L &\leq \mathbf{X} \leq \mathbf{X}_U \end{aligned} \quad (3.17)$$

where \mathbf{X}_L and \mathbf{X}_U are expressed by the following geometrical constraints:

- $0 \leq x_B \leq x_A$ m to avoid clashes with the wheel rim ($x_A = 393$ mm) and with the suspension subframe ($x_B \leq 0$);
- $0 \leq y_B \leq 150$ mm to avoid clashes with the vehicle body;
- $0 \leq y_C \leq 150$ mm to avoid clashes with the suspension subframe.

The functions $g_i(\mathbf{X})$ express the following linear inequality constraints:

- $g_1 = \max(|\gamma - 90^\circ|) - \Delta\gamma_{\max}$, where $\Delta\gamma_{\max} = 50^\circ$ to avoid a self-locking mechanism;
- $g_2 = \tau_{\ell, \text{nom}} - \tau_{\ell, \text{max}}$, where $\tau_{\ell, \text{max}} = 400$ mm/rad to avoid too large kinematic ratios;
- $g_3 = \sigma(\tau_{\ell}) - \sigma_{\max}$, where $\tau_{\ell, \text{max}} = 30$ mm/rad to avoid too large variations of kinematic ratio throughout the suspension stroke;
- $g_4 = -\tau_{\ell, \text{nom}}$, to avoid configurations in which point C is located farther outboard than point B;
- $g_5 = \max(O\hat{A}B) - 140^\circ$ and $g_6 = -\min(O\hat{A}B) + 50^\circ$, to avoid a self-locking mechanism, too.

The optimization problem in Eq. (3.17) is solved as a function of the overall kinematics of the four-bars system with hinges in point O and point C. The input is the vertical displacement of the point A $\Delta y_A = [-80, +80]$ mm, that is assumed to move as the wheel for simplicity. $\Delta y_A = 0$ mm represents the nominal position. The vehicle body is assumed to be stationary, thus the motion of the wheel Δy_A coincides

Fig. 3.8 Linkage optimization routine results: (a) Pareto front of the objective functions, (b) nominal values of the kinematic ratio $\tau_{\ell, \text{nom}}$ and of the transmission angle γ_{nom} of the possible configurations.

with the suspension stroke x . Moreover, for this specific case study, the weighting factor w in Eq. (3.15) is set to 1 because the very first iterations consistently yielded small values of $\sigma(\tau_{\ell})$, one order of magnitude below σ_{max} . The process is carried out in MATLAB environment by means of the function *gamultiobj* that implements a multi-objective genetic algorithm (GA). This algorithm considers all the objective functions simultaneously, resulting in multiple optimal solutions, where each solution corresponds to a point on the Pareto front [114]. Moreover, they are usually chosen because they do not need any gradient information and, by evolving a population of solutions rather than a single candidate, they explore multiple regions of the search space simultaneously, improving efficiency and most likely avoiding premature convergence. Afshari *et al.* [114] identified other two possible strategies to solve constrained multi-objective optimization problems. The first strategy involves a linear combination of the objective functions by assigning weighting coefficients. The optimal set that minimizes this linear combination is unique, and the Pareto front is generated by varying the weights. For instance, this strategy is used to define Eq. (3.15). However, the choice of weights remains uncertain, which can affect the results. The other strategy treats all but one of the objective functions as constraints, thereby transforming the problem into a mono-objective optimization. The Pareto front is then constructed by repeating the process for different combinations of objective functions.

The resulting Pareto front is shown in Fig. 3.8a. The selected solution is detected by the red arrow and it favours the kinematic ratio minimization because

Fig. 3.9 Kinematics of the rear linkage selected solution as function of the wheel stroke Δy_A : (a) kinematic ratio τ_ℓ , (b) transmission angle γ , (c) angle $O\hat{A}B$, (d) crank rotation angle θ_{BC} .

the resulting values of γ_{nom} fall in a tiny neighbourhood of 90° , as visible in Fig. 3.8b. The selected solution reflects an engineering-driven choice, as points above the solution in Fig. 3.8a yield comparable values of $\tau_{\ell,\text{nom}}$ in Fig. 3.8b, but the selected solution reaches a value of γ_{nom} closer to 90° . The solution is characterized by the optimized coordinate of the RSA hinge $x_C = 47.6$ mm and the vertical coordinate at $y_C = 70$ mm, a pushrod length $l_{AB} = 203.7$ mm, and a crank length $l_{BC} = 152.7$ mm. The kinematics characteristics are reported in Fig. 3.9. In more detail, the nominal kinematic ratio $\tau_{\ell,\text{nom}}$ is equal to 189 mm/rad with a variation from the nominal value from 178 mm/rad to 193 mm/rad along the whole wheel stroke, and a standard deviation σ_{τ_ℓ} of 4.3 mm/rad (Fig. 3.9a). From Fig. 3.9b and Fig. 3.9c, the functionality is demonstrated by angles never outranging $90^\circ \pm 50^\circ$. Actually, the transmission angle γ presents a nominal value of 92° and a variation from 106° to 83° along the whole wheel travel. The angle spaced by the crank arm θ_{BC} shows a linear trend ranging from -25° to 24° (Fig. 3.9d).

Fig. 3.10 D-class SUV case study: normal production front suspension.

Automotive front suspension

The SUV front corners deploy a high-type double wishbone suspension with virtual steering axis (Fig. 3.10). For this case study, an RSA is going to be employed, too.

The steering functionality and the presence of the semi-axle for the all wheel drive (AWD) limited the possibility of fully optimizing the retrofitting. Indeed, the RSA location is chosen behind the LCA and overlapping the suspension subframe to avoid any interference with the steered wheel and the other moving elements (Fig. 3.11a). Considering the body reference frame defined in the previous Section 3.1.2, the position of the RSA hinge point, i.e., the intersection between the RSA main axis and the crank lever line of action, is $[115, -440.6, -126.5]$ mm. Also in this case, the RSA rotational axis is parallel to the LCA axis. The clash is solved by properly machining the subframe and with the addition of structural reinforcements to the RSA flanges to respect the stiffness characteristics of the subframe. For the same reasons, the pushrod attachment joint is fixed a priori to the damper tube, as it is largely unaffected by the steering motion and the semi-axle passes through its fork. To avoid unwanted radial forces and moments on the damper tube, which can cause self-locking phenomena, the pushrod action line must be parallel to the damper axis in the 2D kinematics plane. Hence, the optimization task focused primarily in keeping an optimal transmission efficiency by imposing $\gamma_{\text{nom}} = 90^\circ$. From this, the lengths of the two links follow, $l_{AB} = 255.3$ mm and $l_{BC} = 142.3$ mm.

Fig. 3.11 D-class SUV case study: (a) RSA final location, (b) 2D linkage sketch.

Fig. 3.12 Kinematics of the front linkage solution as function of the wheel stroke Δy_A : (a) kinematic ratio τ_ℓ , (b) transmission angle γ , (c) crank rotation angle θ_{BC} .

Fig. 3.13 Bike front fork: (a) telescopic legs, (b) leg cross-section and selected space for EHA installation.

Knowing the overall geometry, the 2D kinematics of this mechanism can be directly computed as a slider-crank mechanism since the point A moves as the guiding damper and the point C is the rotational hinge of the RSA (Fig. 3.11b). The results are reported in Fig. 3.12. In more detail, the nominal kinematic ratio $\tau_{\ell, \text{nom}}$ is equal to 226 mm/rad with a variation from the nominal value from 214 mm/rad to 209 mm/rad along the whole wheel stroke, and a standard deviation $\sigma_{\tau_{\ell}}$ of 4.6 mm/rad (Fig. 3.12a). From Fig. 3.12b, the choice of the most efficient transmission is clear since the transmission angle γ presents a nominal value of 90° and a variation from 76° to 111° along the whole wheel travel. The angle spaced by the crank arm θ_{BC} shows a linear trend also in this configuration, ranging symmetrically of about $\pm 20^\circ$ (Fig. 3.12c).

Bike front fork

The naked bike under study installs a typical telescopic upside-down fork as front suspension. Both the two legs implement the elastic and damping action of the suspension (Fig. 3.13a).

For this case study, an EHA is selected as the electromagnetic shock absorber due to the lack of available space in the suspension architecture for linkages. Unlike the technology shown in Fig. 2.9a, the optimal packaging focuses on developing a

coaxial EHA device integrated into the bike leg, eliminating protruding elements from the fork that could hinder steering. Additionally, distributing the electromagnetic action across both legs enhances compactness, allowing the EHA to be fully enclosed within its leg. A cross-section of the leg is shown in Fig. 3.13b. It is characterised by through-rod double acting damper, hence the EHA can exert also active functionalities. To do so, it is mandatory to lock the damping valves on the piston because they would allow unwanted oil flow between the two chambers, hence a strong reduction of the desired force due to hydraulic leakages. The available space for the motor-pump unit is a cylinder with a maximum diameter of 44 mm and maximum axial size of 100 mm.

In the end, in general for the EHA case study, the optimization problem will only involve the motor-pump unit design.

3.2 System requirements

The definition of the system requirements arise directly from vehicle dynamics requested performance by the industrial partners. In this early design stages, analytical models are adopted because (i) they just need the fundamental suspension parameters, i.e., masses and stiffnesses, (ii) they offer an easy and fast tool to compute the design targets in terms of desired forces and speeds at the suspension level.

For both the D-SUV and the bike, monocorner models are developed for each suspension, with simulations evaluating only basic control strategies. Additionally, a linear roll model of the D-SUV sprung mass about its own roll axis is considered to assess the requirements for the slow-active features.

3.2.1 Monocorner model

A monocorner, or quarter-car, model represents the vertical degree of freedom of an individual suspension. To accurately analyse the frequency range involved in ride and shake dynamics [46], the model incorporates two degrees of freedom. The *unsprung mass* m_u represents all suspension components moving with the wheel, e.g., the tire, the knuckle and wheel rim, the brake disc or drum, and the suspension arms, while the *sprung mass* m_s accounts for the portion of the vehicle body mass

Fig. 3.14 Tools for system requirements: (a) monocorner model, (b) simulation scheme with the possibility of switching from the passive damping curves to the LQR controller.

assigned to the corner, based on the overall weight distribution. Consequently, z_u and z_s are the vertical displacements of the unsprung and sprung masses, respectively, and double dots are used to indicate their second time derivatives, i.e., the vertical accelerations. The model assumes that the sprung mass moves vertically above the wheel, suspended over the suspension stiffness k_s , while the tire is represented as a massless spring element k_u . Finally, the road vertical displacement z_r excites the system. The described model is depicted in Fig. 3.14a.

For the study of electromagnetic dampers, the model includes an ideal linear force source F_a that replaces the usual linear damper in parallel to the suspension stiffness (Fig. 3.14a) and the tire-ground contact force F_t . The equations of motion are:

$$\begin{aligned} m_s \ddot{z}_s &= -k_s(z_s - z_u) + F_a \\ m_u \ddot{z}_u &= k_s(z_s - z_u) - F_a - \underbrace{k_u(z_u - z_r)}_{F_t} \end{aligned} \quad (3.18)$$

The weight force is disregarded as it is naturally counterbalanced by the spring preload. Furthermore, a force saturation during the tire extension phase models the tire detachment for a more precise road holding analysis. This saturation sets the limit tire extension force to $F_{\text{sat}} = g(m_s + m_u)$, where obviously g is the standard gravity. This saturation is particularly useful to count the number of tire detachments from the ground during speed bump scenarios. Table 3.3 reports the quarter-car parameters for the three case studies.

Table 3.3 Lumped parameters of mono-corner models under study.

Description	Symbol	Value			Unit
		D-SUV rear	D-SUV front	Bike fork	
Sprung mass	m_s	573.8	469.8	119.6	kg
Unsprung mass	m_u	55	55	20	kg
Suspension stiffness	k_s	33.4	25.5	18.1	kN/m
Tire stiffness	k_u	255	255	130	kN/m

Simulation scenarios

Figure 3.14b highlights the plant $G_{qc}(s)$, which is the state space representation of Eq. (3.18), and the input of the model in purple, i.e., the road vertical displacement z_r . Two scenarios are simulated: (i) a constant speed travel over a rough road for the continuous duty requirements, (ii) a speed bump crossing at constant speed for the transient peak duty requirements. Continuous duty refers to operating conditions under which the electric machine and its power electronics can function without overheating. In contrast, peak duty refers to short periods of increased electrical power that can be thermally managed without modifying the cooling system. For this kind of electromagnetic shock absorbers, air indirect cooling is foreseen.

To reproduce rough roads, ISO 8608 standard [115] is implemented as proposed by Zuo and Zhang [116]. Imposing a constant longitudinal speed of the vehicle v_{car} and a road roughness coefficient G_r based on the road roughness class in the ISO standard, the road vertical displacement can be computed by filtering a unit-intensity white noise signal with the following first-order low pass filter, expressed in the Laplace domain:

$$G_{road}(s) = \frac{2\pi\sqrt{G_r v_{car}}}{s + \omega_0} \quad (3.19)$$

where $\omega_0 = 2\pi v_{car}/\lambda_0$ represents a small cut-off frequency required to obtain finite displacements at vanishingly small frequencies. In this model, λ_0 is set to 100 m, that is a sufficient wavelength to capture full information of the road irregularities ahead of the vehicle.

Fig. 3.15 Damping characteristics at wheel level of the semi-active normal production dampers: (a) D-SUV rear, (b) D-SUV front, (c) bike fork.

The speed bump has a height of $h = 30$ mm and a width of $d = 600$ mm. These dimensions derive from Italian regulations for 50 km/h speed limit [117]. In the time domain, the geometry is approximated with a cosine function:

$$z_r = \frac{h}{2} \left[1 - \cos \left(\frac{2\pi v_{\text{car}}(t - t_0)}{d} \right) \right] \quad (3.20)$$

where t_0 is the time at which the bump hit occurs and $v_{\text{car}} = 13.89$ m/s, to be consistent with the speed limit mentioned before.

Control strategies and key performance indicators

Dealing with controllable devices, the force and speed requirements depend on the chosen control strategy for the suspension system.

To assess the damping capabilities, the semi-active normal production damping curves in minimum and maximum tunings are implemented as 1-D look-up table

giving the force F_a as a function of the suspension speed $v = \dot{z}_s - \dot{z}_u$ (Fig. 3.14b). Figure 3.15 shows those curves for each target vehicle and corner and they are provided by the industrial partners.

Then, to assess the active features, the simulation can switch to a control module deploying a linear quadratic regulator (LQR) in continuous time domain (Fig. 3.14b). It is an optimal state-feedback controller formulated as

$$F_a = -K\mathbf{Z} \quad (3.21)$$

where K is the solution of the associated Riccati equation and \mathbf{Z} is the state vector. For this control design problem, the state vector is $\mathbf{Z} = [z_s - z_u \ z_u \ \dot{z}_s \ \dot{z}_u]^T$. The control law in Eq. (3.21) minimizes a user-defined cost function. For this active suspension case study, the cost function is expressed as [118, 119]

$$\begin{aligned} J &= \int_0^\infty (\mathbf{Z}^T \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{Z} + u^T R u + 2\mathbf{Z}^T N u) dt = \\ &= \int_0^\infty [r_s (z_s - z_u)^2 + r_h z_u^2 + \dot{z}_s^2] dt \end{aligned} \quad (3.22)$$

r_s and r_h are tuning parameters to give minimization priority to suspension stroke or tire deflection, respectively. For this controller design, the monocorner model is simplified into

$$\begin{aligned} m_s \ddot{z}_s &= u \\ m_u \ddot{z}_u &= k_u (z_t - z_u) - u \end{aligned} \quad (3.23)$$

where u is the control action and it is the overall suspension force, i.e., sum of the forces of the spring and of the actuator. In order to define the matrix R in Eq. (3.22), the control action u can be rearranged from Eq. 3.23 as $u = \ddot{z}_s / m_s$. It follows that the matrices Q , R , and N are

$$Q = \begin{bmatrix} r_s & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & r_h & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.24)$$

$$R = 1/m_s^2 \quad (3.25)$$

$$N = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.26)$$

To compare the control strategies, key performance indicators (KPIs) are used as single-value numerical metrics.

For comfort evaluations, the ISO 2631 standard [45, 116] suggests the use of the acceleration perceived by a human passenger, \ddot{z}_w . Equation Eq. (3.27) is a third-order band-pass filter transfer function used to obtain the weighted acceleration by providing the sprung mass acceleration \ddot{z}_s .

$$\frac{\ddot{z}_w(s)}{\ddot{z}_s(s)} = \frac{80.03s^2 + 989s + 0.02108}{s^3 + 78.92s^2 + 2412s + 5614} \quad (3.27)$$

Regarding handling, the road holding index η_{rh} normalizes the dynamic tire vertical force to its static load. Mathematically speaking,

$$\eta_{rh} = \frac{k_u(z_u - z_r)}{g(m_s + m_u)} \quad (3.28)$$

Unitary values point out tire detachments. Conversely, null values depict an undeformed tire, which keep a constant vertical force equal to the corner weight.

In the end, the evaluated quantities are the ideal actuator force $F_a = u + k_s(z_s - z_u)$ and the suspension speed v , as they directly relate to the specifications required by the electromagnetic damper, and \ddot{z}_w and η_{rh} , as they characterize the vehicle dynamics performance.

For continuous simulation scenarios, as the rough road, RMS values of those quantities are determined because they portray their mean values in relation to power. Moreover, the ISO 2631 standard [45] establishes the comfort levels that the human body can withstand, e.g., the utmost comfort level is below 0.315 m/s^2 .

For the speed bump scenario, absolute peak values are instead evaluated, along with the number of instances where the tire loses contact with the ground.

Table 3.4 Simulation RMS results for the rough road scenario.

D-SUV rear	Max damp	Min damp	Comfort LQR	Handling LQR
Tuning	Fig. 3.15a Orange	Fig. 3.15a Blue	$r_s = 5.18 \cdot 10^2$ $r_h = 3.65 \cdot 10^5$	$r_s = 5.69 \cdot 10^6$ $r_h = 7.15 \cdot 10^7$
F_a [N]	1078	207	927	1422
v [m/s]	0.1	0.28	0.52	0.14
\ddot{z}_w [m/s ²]	1.29	0.58	0.18	0.74
η_{rh} [-]	0.16	0.17	0.32	0.11
D-SUV front	Max damp	Min damp	Comfort LQR	Handling LQR
Tuning	Fig. 3.15b Orange	Fig. 3.15b Blue	$r_s = 2.56 \cdot 10^5$ $r_h = 1.54 \cdot 10^4$	$r_s = 5.69 \cdot 10^6$ $r_h = 7.14 \cdot 10^7$
F_a [N]	681	181	1109	1054
v [m/s]	0.12	0.32	0.59	0.15
\ddot{z}_w [m/s ²]	1.19	0.59	0.20	0.85
η_{rh} [-]	0.16	0.23	0.43	0.13
Bike fork	Max damp	Min damp	Comfort LQR	Handling LQR
Tuning	Fig. 3.15c Orange	Fig. 3.15c Blue	$r_s = 3.24 \cdot 10^4$ $r_h = 3.16 \cdot 10^3$	$r_s = 2.02 \cdot 10^6$ $r_h = 7.14 \cdot 10^7$
F_a [N]	416	241	63	222
v [m/s]	0.08	0.13	0.44	0.19
\ddot{z}_w [m/s ²]	3.27	1.83	0.46	1.51
η_{rh} [-]	0.36	0.25	0.53	0.23

Table 3.5 Simulation MAX results for the bump scenario.

D-SUV rear	Max damp	Min damp	Comfort LQR	Handling LQR
Tuning	Fig. 3.15a Orange	Fig. 3.15a Blue	$r_s = 5.2 \cdot 10^2$ $r_h = 3.6 \cdot 10^5$	$r_s = 5.7 \cdot 10^6$ $r_h = 7.1 \cdot 10^7$
F_a [N]	3055	2147	1315	3234
v [m/s]	1.35	1.84	2.39	1.11
\ddot{z}_w [m/s ²]	4.83	3.31	0.82	4.99
no. of detach. [-]	1	1	3	0
D-SUV front	Max damp	Min damp	Comfort LQR	Handling LQR
Tuning	Fig. 3.15b Orange	Fig. 3.15b Blue	$r_s = 2.56 \cdot 10^5$ $r_h = 1.54 \cdot 10^4$	$r_s = 5.69 \cdot 10^6$ $r_h = 7.14 \cdot 10^7$
F_a [N]	2623	1249	1025	3076
v [m/s]	1.45	2.04	2.44	1.19
\ddot{z}_w [m/s ²]	5.13	2.88	0.80	5.97
no. of detach. [-]	1	2	5	1
Bike fork	Max damp	Min damp	Comfort LQR	Handling LQR
Tuning	Fig. 3.15c Orange	Fig. 3.15c Blue	$r_s = 3.24 \cdot 10^4$ $r_h = 3.16 \cdot 10^3$	$r_s = 2.02 \cdot 10^6$ $r_h = 7.14 \cdot 10^7$
F_a [N]	1876	1638	432	1751
v [m/s]	0.9	1.08	3.02	1.65
\ddot{z}_w [m/s ²]	12.0	11.24	3.1	1.19
no. of detach. [-]	1	1	5	1

Results

Simulations are conducted in MATLAB/Simulink environment. The rough road scenario simulates a C-class road ($G_r = 25.6 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ m}^2 \text{ cycles/m}$) run at $v_{\text{car}} = 35 \text{ km/h}$, which is a moderately bumpy road in urban scenarios. The LQR controller has a comfort-tuning, minimizing the RMS weighted acceleration \ddot{z}_s to 0.2 m/s^2 , and a handling-tuning, minimizing the RMS road holding index η_{rh} . For the bike case study, comfort is much more difficult to achieve due the mass ratio, so the comfort target is relaxed to 0.5 m/s^2 . The resulting KPIS are reported in Table 3.4 for the rough road continuous scenario and Table 3.5 for the front bump scenario. The former shows RMS values, while the latter shows MAX values, i.e., the peak absolute values. The final goal is to define an equivalent continuous-operation working point determined by a RMS force value and a RMS velocity value at suspension level useful for the actuator design in continuous duty. Instead, for the peak duty design, two independent values of MAX force and MAX velocity are needed to determine the extreme boundaries of the force-velocity working area of the shock absorber. The methodology that will be presented in the following sections of the thesis requires also a MAX damping value.

For air indirect cooled totally-enclosed motor, a typical wire current density of $J_{\text{rms}} = 5 \div 6 \text{ A/mm}^2$ is used for continuous duty, $J_{\text{max}} = 20 \text{ A/mm}^2$ applies for peak duty with a duration of $\leq 10 \text{ s}$ [120, 121]. As a first approximation, torque is linearly dependent on current. Therefore, in the D-SUV case study, an actuator generating approximately an RMS force $F_{\text{rms,rsa}}$ of 1.1 kN and a peak force $F_{\text{max,rsa}}$ of 3.3 kN maintains the ratio $J_{\text{max}}/J_{\text{rms}} = 20/6 \approx 3$ while also ensuring the performance in Table 3.4 and Table 3.5. The chosen equivalent continuous-operation working point presents a RMS speed $v_{\text{rms,rsa}}$ of 0.1 m/s because the values from the maximum damping simulations in Table 3.4 are selected. Instead, the maximum suspension speed $v_{\text{rsa,max}}$ requirement is set at 6 m/s, as requested by the industrial partner. Finally, the MAX damping requirement is set to $c_{\text{max,rsa}} = 20 \text{ kNs/m}$, based on preliminary simulations indicating that this value is sufficient for both road vibration suppression and roll damping.

For the bike case study, the results in Table 3.5 demonstrate that the damping requirements are much more stringent than the active LQR control requirements and that forces higher than 2 kN and speed higher than 3 m/s are never reached. Consequently, the design prioritizes the damping requirements. The targets are split

Fig. 3.16 Sprung mass roll model: (a) physical scheme, (b) simulation model with PID control.

for the single leg of the fork as an EHA is deployed in each, so the damping and force displayed in Fig. 3.15c are halved, while the speed remains the same. Moreover, The EHA design methodology slightly differs from the RSA one, as will further discussed in the following sections. It requires just MAX performance specifications. These are selected as $c_{\max, \text{eha}} = 2.7 \text{ kNs/m}$, $F_{\max, \text{eha}} = 2 \text{ kN}$ to take into account the significant losses typical of this technology, as noted in Sections 2.2.3 and 3.1.1, and $v_{\max, \text{eha}} = 3 \text{ m/s}$.

3.2.2 Roll linear model

For the D-SUV case study, requirements must take into account the possibility of controlling also slow vehicle body dynamics. To achieve this, a proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controller is implemented on a linear model of the sprung mass roll dynamics $G_{\text{roll}}(s)$ (Fig. 3.16b). Its purpose is to eliminate the roll angle induced by a step lateral acceleration on the vehicle by generating a counteracting active moment M_a using all four active corners.

The equation of motion is

$$I_s \ddot{\phi}_s = -\chi_{\text{tot}} \phi_s + M_a + m_{s, \text{tot}} a_y H + m_{s, \text{tot}} g H \phi \quad (3.29)$$

where I_s is the roll moment of inertia of the sprung mass about its roll axis, $\ddot{\phi}_s$ the roll angle acceleration, ϕ_s the roll angle, $\chi_{\text{tot}} = \chi_f + \chi_r$ is the total roll stiffness applied by the two axles, m_s the sprung mass, H the distance from the centre of gravity (CoG) and the roll axis, and a_y the lateral acceleration of the vehicle. The parameters of the

Table 3.6 Lumped parameters of D-SUV sprung mass roll model.

Description	Symbol	Value	Unit
Total sprung mass	$m_{s,tot}$	2087	kg
Sprung mass roll inertia	I_s	910	$\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^2$
Total roll stiffness	χ_{tot}	198.6	kNm/rad
Front axle roll stiffness	χ_f	135.6	kNm/rad
Rear axle roll stiffness	χ_r	63	kNm/rad
CoG distance to roll axis	H	0.460	m
Front track width	t_f	1.615	m
Rear track width	t_r	1.655	m
Proportional gain	k_p	975.8	kNm/rad
Integral gain	k_i	$5.13 \cdot 10^3$	kNm/rad s
Derivative gain	k_d	43.77	kNms/rad

model and the gain of the PID controller are reported in Table 3.6. The PID is tuned to null the roll angle ϕ_s until a maximum lateral acceleration of 0.6g since for higher lateral acceleration, it is suggested to let the vehicle partially roll to warn the driver about the limit lateral adhesion condition [122].

As anticipated, two force couples ΔF_{af} and ΔF_{ar} on the two axles generate the controlled anti-roll moment M_a . The latter is distributed on the basis of roll stiffness distribution, as follows

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta F_{af} &= \frac{\chi_r}{\chi_{tot} t_f} M_a \\ \Delta F_{ar} &= \frac{\chi_f}{\chi_{tot} t_r} M_a\end{aligned}\quad (3.30)$$

where χ_f and χ_r are the roll stiffnesses of the front and rear axles, respectively. The principle is to exert higher forces on the less stiff axle, as it undergoes greater local suspension deformation; therefore, higher active forces can effectively counteract it. Nevertheless, further investigations into the anti-roll moment distribution, as well as more precise control strategies based on a roll model with four active corners, are necessary before vehicle implementation.

Figure 3.17a shows the simulated event, that is a step lateral acceleration as it happens in case of a step steer manoeuvre, and it demonstrates the effectiveness

Fig. 3.17 Roll control simulation results: (a) input lateral acceleration a_y and output sprung mass roll angle ϕ_s , (b) actuator forces for front and rear axles.

in nulling the roll angle in about 1 s with an imperceptible peak at 0.27° . The actuator force time histories are characterized by peak forces of 1293 N and 2716 N at the front corners and at the rear corners, respectively, with a rise time of 59 ms (Figure 3.17b), which is within the RSA frequency response capability, as demonstrated in Section 3.1.1. The steady-state forces are 1109 N at the front and 2330 N at the rear, with a settling time of 0.9 s (Fig. 3.17b). These forces represent quasi-static loads since, once the roll target is achieved, the suspension speed drops to zero. Additionally, manoeuvres involving strong lateral accelerations typically last only a few seconds. Therefore, the force requirements are adequately covered by the peak force requirement of 3 kN specified in Section 3.2.1. However, even continuous force characteristics would be beneficial in reducing the sprung mass roll angle in case of longer manoeuvres or smaller accelerations. Indeed, smaller lateral accelerations translate into smaller roll angles, which can be controlled by much smaller steady-state forces, as the RMS force requirement of 1.1 kN from Section 3.2.1. Furthermore, in the extreme and rare cases of long-lasting high lateral accelerations manoeuvres, this RMS force can still contribute to reducing the steady-state roll angle.

3.3 Detailed design

This section explores the detailed design of the electromagnetic shock absorber components. The requirements outlined in Section 3.2, along with the nominal linkage configuration from Section 3.1, serve as inputs for an optimization algorithm

Fig. 3.18 Cross-section of SPM electric machine: outer rotor diameter D_{ro} , inner rotor diameter D_{ri} , outer stator diameter D_{so} , inner stator diameter D_{si} , back iron diameter D_{sb} , shoe dimensions d_1 and d_2 , permanent magnet thickness l_m , air gap g_{em} , slot opening w_s , shoe width w_t , tooth width w_{tb} , back iron width w_{bi} .

to determine the initial actuator sizing. Subsequently, both the electric machine and the transmission mechanism are designed in detail.

The D-SUV case study is analysed closely to minimize redundancy, as the final design is also applied to the front suspension to reduce the part numbers. Additionally, details on the EHA for the bike are provided, with a specific focus on the hydrostatic transmission stage.

3.3.1 Global optimization methodology

A global optimization methodology seeks to match the electric machine and the planetary gearbox to find a compromise between size and performance. Specifically, the process adjusts the outer diameter of both the electric machine stator D_{so} and gearbox D_{gb} , the active length of the electric machine l_{em} , i.e., the axial stator and rotor size where electromagnetic interaction occurs, and the gearbox reduction ratio i_{gb} . Part of the methodology derives from Circosta's doctoral thesis [108].

Preliminary electric machine analysis

A surface permanent magnet (SPM) three-phase electric machine is selected due to its high torque density [123]. As the name suggests, the permanent magnets are fixed to the rotor outer surface, creating a constant magnetic field that interacts with the stator electromagnetic field along the active length l_{em} to produce rotation. Of

course, the magnets length must coincide with l_{em} . The stator electromagnetic field arises by energizing and deenergizing the windings. As a consequence, the rotor does not need to be constructed in laminated layers and the magnets can be just glued to the rotor surface, provided that centrifugal forces are properly accounted for. This makes SPM motors also more cost-effective than other permanent magnet motor topologies. Figure 3.18 depicts its typical cross section and key geometrical parameters.

A preliminary study precedes the global optimization process to select the cross-section that maximises the output torque-to-length ratio r_{TI} during continuous operation with air indirect cooling, i.e., the applied current density is $J_{rms} = 6 \text{ A/mm}^2$, while ensuring that the stator flux density due to the permanent magnets (PMs) $B_{bi,PM}$ remains below 1.2 T, to prevent steel saturation when current is then applied, that increases the total flux density B_{bi} . As M-27 silicon steel is typical for stator of this topology and widely used in automotive industry, flux density saturation occurs at around $1.7 \div 1.8 \text{ T}$. For this motor topology, the linear approximation holds validity [124], hence the torque-to-length ratio is defined as the ratio between the motor torque T_{em} and its active length l_{em}

$$r_{TI} = \frac{T_{em}}{l_{em}} \quad (3.31)$$

Finite element electromagnetic simulations are used to investigate four different slot (Ns) and magnet (Nm) configurations typical for this kind of motor [120]: Ns9Nm8, Ns9Nm10, Ns12Nm10, and Ns15Nm10. These configurations guarantee a good compromise in terms of torque ripple, cogging torque, back electromotive force (BEMF) harmonics, and efficiency. Increasing Ns reduces torque ripple and cogging torque as the stator magnetic field is more distributed and makes the BEMF more sinusoidal. However, the increase of copper quantity in the slots would increase the Joule losses. Instead, higher Nm increases the torque density and smooths the BEMF, but it increases the electrical frequency, thus causing higher switching losses in the power electronics and higher iron losses in the stator. Furthermore, these configurations are also classified as fractional-slot winding because the number of slot per pole per phase is not an integer, allowing for shorter winding heads.

The fixed parameters for this preliminary optimization are set as follows:

- Stator Material: M-27 silicon steel, chosen for its low hysteresis and eddy current losses, high magnetic permeability, reduced heating, good mechanical and thermal resistance, and suitability for thin laminations;
- Rotor Magnets: NdFeB magnets, selected for their high magnetic strength, compactness, temperature resistance, and durability;
- Air gap g_{em} : a 0.5 mm gap between the magnets and rotor teeth, ensuring sufficient clearance to prevent rotor-stator interference due to possible eccentricity and manufacturing tolerances;
- Slot opening w_s : a 2 mm slot opening between the rotor teeth, balancing cogging torque, which increases with larger openings, and flux leakage, which increases with smaller openings;
- Magnets permeance coefficient P_{PM} : defined as $P_{PM} \approx l_m/g_{em}$, a value of 5 ensures that the magnet thickness l_m is sufficient to prevent demagnetization at high operating temperatures.

A particle swarm algorithm finds the optimal rotor outer diameter D_{ro} , back iron width w_{bi} , and tooth width w_{tb} for various stator outer diameters D_{so} and for each above listed configurations. Mathematically, the problem is formalized as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \forall D_{so} \in [70, 110] \text{ mm} \\
 & \max_{\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \{r_{TI}(\mathbf{Y})\} \\
 & \text{subject to:} \\
 & B_{bi,PM} \leq 1.2 \text{ T} \\
 & \mathbf{Y}_L \leq \mathbf{Y} \leq \mathbf{Y}_U
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.32}$$

where $\mathbf{Y} = [D_{ro}, w_{bi}, w_{tb}]^T$, B_{bi} is the stator back iron flux density due to the PMs, $\mathbf{Y}_L = [22, 2, 3]^T$ mm, and $\mathbf{Y}_U = [44, 6, 9]^T$ mm. These limits are based on previous experience from the research group in designing custom motors for electromagnetic shock absorbers, considering size and performance.

The results, shown in Fig. 3.19, indicate that the Ns9Nm10 configuration provides the highest torque output. However, as current is applied to the stator windings, it suffers from excessive saturation, exceeding an average stator flux density of 1.4 T. Therefore, the Ns12Nm10 configuration is selected for global optimization, as it

Fig. 3.19 Maximum torque-to-length ratio r_{Tl} as function as function of the stator outer diameter D_{so}

offers a good balance between torque output and an acceptable average stator flux density when current is applied (≈ 1.3 T).

Global design methodology

The global design methodology is shown in Fig. 3.20. Varying the stator outer diameter D_{so} , a proper combination of active length l_{em} and global transmission ratio τ is computed to respect the system requirements. It is worth highlighting that τ links the suspension speed at wheel level v to the electric machine speed ω_{em} as function of the suspension stroke at wheel level x , thus, ideally, in absence of losses also motor torque T_{em} and force at wheel level F , and it is strictly dependent to the previously defined linkage kinematic ratio τ_ℓ and the gearbox reduction ratio i_{gb} :

$$\tau(x) = \frac{v}{\omega_{em}} = \frac{T_{em}}{F} = \frac{\tau_\ell(x)}{i_{gb}} \quad (3.33)$$

For the sake of simplicity, the kinematic ratio τ_ℓ is considered constant as its nominal value $\tau_{\ell, nom}$, thus also τ is considered constant during the suspension stroke. This assumption holds validity as the variation of τ_ℓ is limited along the suspension stroke x , as reported in Section 3.1.2.

First, the locus of solutions of the proposed optimization methodology is bounded by the following constraints:

- Maximum allowable active length $l_{em, max}$: for compactness and to avoid too slender rotor for rotordynamics issues, it is set to 70 mm;

Fig. 3.20 Global optimization methodology for the RSA design.

- Minimum allowable global transmission ratio τ_{\min} : it is defined as the ratio between the maximum suspension speed $v_{\max} = 6$ m/s, as required in Section 3.2, and the maximum rotor allowed speed $\omega_{\text{em,max}}$, set to 2618 rad/s to avoid excessive centrifugal forces on the rotor magnets. So, $\tau_{\min} = 2.29$ mm/rad.

The procedure starts selecting a diameter D_{so} . It is varied from 80 mm to 115 mm with a discretization of 5 mm and each value is characterized by a constant continuous torque-to-length ratio r_{Tl} , resulting from the cross-section optimization on Ns12Nm motor configuration in Section 3.3.1 (Fig. 3.19). Then, the global transmission ratio τ is varied from τ_{\min} to 10^4 mm/rad with a discretization of 10 mm/rad. For each combination of the two, the active lengths respecting the RMS force requirement l_{rms} , the MAX force requirement l_{max} , and the MAX damping requirement l_{c} from Section 3.2.1 are first computed.

In particular, those lengths can be linked to the force requirements as follows by

combining Eqs. (3.31) and (3.33):

$$l_{\text{rms}} = \frac{F_{\text{rms}}}{r_{\text{Tl}}} \tau \quad (3.34)$$

$$l_{\text{max}} = \frac{F_{\text{max}}}{r_{\text{Tl}}|_{J_{\text{max}}}} \tau \quad (3.35)$$

By assuming the motor linearity, the relationship $r_{\text{Tl}}|_{J_{\text{max}}} = r_{\text{Tl}} J_{\text{rms}}/J_{\text{max}}$ holds validity since the motor configuration is chosen to avoid flux saturation in nominal condition, ensuring almost linear behaviour also in peak duty conditions. Repeatedly, both the conditions consider air indirect cooling, thus $J_{\text{rms}} = 6 \text{ A/mm}^2$ and $J_{\text{max}} = 20 \text{ A/mm}^2$, as reported in Section 3.2.1.

About the damping requirement, it assigns the desired maximum regenerative damping for the RSA. Galluzzi *et al.* [106] provides a formulation to compute the short circuit damping $c_{\text{em,max}}$ for a shunted SPM motor. For $p\omega_{\text{em}} \ll \omega_{\text{e}}$, where p is the number of pole pairs in the motor, ω_{em} the motor speed, and $\omega_{\text{e}} = R_{\text{ph}}/L$ is the angular frequency of the electromagnetic pole, computed as ratio of the phase resistance R_{ph} and the machine inductance in d-q axes L , $c_{\text{em,max}}$ can be expressed as

$$c_{\text{em,max}} = \frac{T_{\text{em}}}{\omega_{\text{em}}} = \frac{2K_{\text{t}}^2}{3R_{\text{ph}}} \quad (3.36)$$

where K_{t} is the torque constant. In nominal continuous operation condition, considering Eq. (3.31), K_{t} is computed as

$$K_{\text{t}} = \frac{T_{\text{em}}}{I_{\text{ph}}} = \frac{r_{\text{Tl}} l_{\text{em}}}{\sqrt{2} J_{\text{rms}} A_{\text{w}} N_{\text{h}}} \quad (3.37)$$

where I_{ph} is the phase current amplitude, A_{w} is the stator copper wire cross-section, and N_{h} the number of wires-in-hand of the coil. The coefficient $\sqrt{2}$ transforms the RMS of the current density into an amplitude value. The phase resistance R_{ph} can be then calculated as

$$R_{\text{ph}} = 2(l_{\text{em}} + l_{\text{et}}) \frac{\rho_{\text{Cu}} N_{\text{c}} N_{\text{t}}}{A_{\text{w}} N_{\text{h}}} \quad (3.38)$$

where l_{et} is the length of the end-turn path and it is a function of the slot geometry previously optimized and equal to 16.8 mm, $\rho_{\text{Cu}} = 1.68 \cdot 10^{-8} \Omega\text{m}$ the electrical resistivity of copper at ambient temperature, N_{c} the number of coils in series per phase, that is the ratio between the number of slots $N_{\text{s}} = 12$ and the number of phases

$N_{ph} = 3$, and N_t the number of turns per coil.

In the end, combining and manipulating Eqs. (3.36), (3.33), (3.37), (3.38), the active length l_c respecting the MAX damping requirement c_{max} is

$$l_c = \frac{1 + \sqrt{1 + 4l_{et} \frac{\alpha_{em}}{c_{max} \tau^2}}}{2 \frac{\alpha_{em}}{c_{max} \tau^2}} \quad (3.39)$$

where the coefficient α_{em} lumps all the constant term with respect to the active length as follows

$$\alpha_{em} = \frac{r_{T1}^2}{6N_c \rho_{Cu} N_t N_h A_w J_{rms}^2} \quad (3.40)$$

Since N_t and N_h will be defined in the detailed design of the electric motor to find the best compromise for manufacturing, Eq. (3.40) is rearranged as function of the slot area A_s and the target maximum gross packing factor $k_{cp,max}$, as follows

$$\alpha_{em} = \frac{r_{T1}^2}{6N_c \rho_{Cu} k_{cp,max} A_s J_{rms}^2} \quad (3.41)$$

The factor $k_{cp,max}$ indicates the slot fraction occupied by copper conductors and it should be maximised for performance optimization. Hand-made windings usually achieve values of $k_{cp,max} \approx 0.3$.

In the end, l_{em} is selected as the maximum between l_{rms} , l_{max} , and l_c .

$$l_{em} = \max\{l_{rms}, l_{max}, l_c\} \quad (3.42)$$

Once the required length l_{em} from Eq. (3.42) is determined for each combination of outer stator diameter D_{so} and global transmission ratio τ , according to the methodology in Fig. 3.20, the approximate values of the mass m and equivalent mass m_{eq} of the RSA need to be computed. They are both the sum of the contributions of the electric machine and the gearbox.

Approximate values of the electric machine mass m_{em} and equivalent inertia $m_{eq,em}$ can be computed as

$$m_{em} = \frac{\rho_{Fe} \pi D_{so}^2 l_{em}}{4} \quad (3.43)$$

$$m_{eq,em} = \frac{\rho_{Fe} \pi D_{ro}^2 l_{em}}{8 \tau^2} \quad (3.44)$$

where $\rho_{\text{Fe}} = 7800 \text{ kg/m}^3$ is the mass density of the steel. Hence, Eq. (3.43) approximates the electric machine to a cylindrical steel body equal to the stator envelope, while Eq. (3.44) approximates its inertia to a rotating cylindrical steel body equal to the rotor envelope. The rotor outer diameter D_{ro} derives from previous analysis on the optimal electric machine cross-section from Section 3.3.1.

Reformulating Eq. (3.33), a gearbox reduction ratio i_{gb} is associated to each value of τ . The gearbox mass and inertia properties are obtained by the scaling laws proposed by Saerens *et al.* [125], as follows

$$D_s = D_r \frac{1}{i_{\text{st}} - 1} \quad (3.45)$$

$$D_p = D_r \frac{i_{\text{st}} - 2}{2(i_{\text{st}} - 1)} \quad (3.46)$$

$$D_c = D_r \frac{i_{\text{st}}}{2(i_{\text{st}} - 1)} \quad (3.47)$$

where $i_{\text{st}} = \sqrt{i_{\text{gb}}}$, as it is a double-stage planetary gearbox with equally split reduction ratio, D is the pitch diameter, and the subscripts "s", "p", "c", and "r" stand for sun gear, planet gear, carrier, and ring gear. In particular, $D_r = 0.95D_{\text{so}}$ to propose a compact RSA design. To compute the overall mass and inertia, a cylindrical approximation is still considered and the gear face width, i.e., the gear thickness, determines the axial size of each stage. Its computation derives from pitting fatigue resistance [125], so the RMS force-velocity working point from Section 3.2.1 is considered. The gears face width of the i -th stage b_i is then computed as

$$b_i = \frac{T_i/3}{\left(\frac{\sigma_{\text{H}}}{Z_i}\right) \frac{i_{\text{st}} - 2}{[2(i_{\text{st}} - 1)]^2} D_r^2} \quad (3.48)$$

where the torque on the carrier of the first stage is $T_1 = F_{\text{rms}}\tau$, while for the second one is $T_2 = T_1/i_{\text{st}}$, the coefficient 1/3 is due to the torque split on the three sun-planet mesh points, $\sigma_{\text{H}} = 1600 \text{ MPa}$ is the allowable contact stress, and Z_i a factor depending on the material properties, gear geometry, and application factors. In more detail, the allowable stress $\sigma_{\text{H}} = \sigma_{\text{H0}}/cs$ and σ_{H0} derives from ANSI/AGMA 2101 standard [126]. Selecting a Steel Grade 3 HRC58-64 AGMA, $\sigma_{\text{H0}} = 1895 \text{ MPa}$, thus the used σ_{H} presents a safety factor $cs \approx 1.2$.

Then, the factor Z_i is determined as

$$Z_i = Z_E Z_H Z_\varepsilon \sqrt{K_A K_{V_i}} \quad (3.49)$$

where $Z_E = \sqrt{E/[2\pi(1-\nu^2)]}$ is the elasticity factor depending from the elastic modulus E and the Poisson's ratio ν of the gear material, in this case steel where $E = 210$ GPa and $\nu = 0.3$, $Z_H = \sqrt{2/(\cos \alpha \sin \alpha)}$ with the gear pressure angle $\alpha = 20^\circ$, Z_ε is a contact ratio factor set equal to 1 as worst case assumption, K_A is the overload factor set to 1.5, and finally the dynamic factor K_{V_i} depends on the sun gear peripheral speed v_{si} of the i -th stage, as follows:

$$K_{V_i} = \frac{5.6 + \sqrt{v_{si}}}{5.6} = \frac{5.6 + \sqrt{\frac{i_{st}^2 v_{rms} D_r}{2\tau_\ell}}}{5.6} \quad (3.50)$$

Finally, the inertia properties of the double-stage planetary gearbox are computed as [125]:

$$m_{gb} = \frac{\pi}{2} \rho_{Fe} (b_1 + b_2) [D_r^2 + 3D_p^2 + D_c^2 + (D_{so}^2 - D_r^2)] \quad (3.51)$$

$$m_{eq,gb} = \frac{1}{\tau_\ell^2} \left[\frac{\rho_{Fe} \pi D_r^4 i_{st}^2}{128(i_{st} - 1)^4} (i_{st}^2 - 3i_{st} + 7) (b_1 + i_{st}^2 b_2) \right] \quad (3.52)$$

In the end, the proposed methodology computes the cost function F_{cost} for the different stator diameter D_{so} and transmission ratio τ . This function is defined for the optimal matching between the electric machine and the gearbox as

$$F_{cost} = w_d \frac{D_{so}}{D_{so,max}} + \underbrace{w_m \frac{m}{m_{max}}}_{F_{m,cost}} + \underbrace{(1 - w_m) \frac{m_{eq}}{m_{eq,max}}}_{F_{meq,cost}} \quad (3.53)$$

where $m = m_{em} + m_{gb}$ is the overall approximate mass of the RSA, $m_{eq} = m_{eq,em} + m_{eq,gb}$ is the overall approximate equivalent inertia, $D_{so,max}$ is the maximum allowable stator outer diameter for packaging set to 125 mm, m_{max} the target maximum RSA mass set to 5 kg, $m_{eq,max}$ the target maximum RSA equivalent inertia set to 20 kg. These latter limits are established to add a negligible mass m to the sprung mass of the vehicle and keep a good force bandwidth as it depends on the equivalent mass m_{eq} , as discussed in Section 3.1.1. w_d and w_m are two weighting coefficients for design choice. The former prioritises compactness, the latter shifts the optimization toward minimizing the mass or the equivalent inertia. It is set to 0.5 to find the

Fig. 3.21 Results of the optimization methodology for $D_{so} = 90$ mm: (a) selection of the l_{em} , (b) cost function F_{cost} .

optimal compromise between motor and gearbox sizes. Indeed, the overall mass linearly depends on the motor active length l_{em} , hence its torque output, see Eqs. (3.42) and (3.43); while the equivalent inertia quadratically depends on the overall transmission ratio τ , hence the gearbox reduction ratio i_{gb} , see Eqs. (3.2) and (3.33).

For instance, considering $D_{so} = 90$ mm, Figure 3.21 shows the optimization results. In this case, the most stringent requirement is related to F_{rms} in the feasibility domain bounded by the constraints on $l_{em,max}$ and τ_{min} , as shown in Fig. 3.21a. In fact, the requirements about F_{max} (yellow curve) and c_{max} (blue curve) are below this line, so they would need even a shorter motor. The red cross evidences the optimal configuration that is the minimum of the cost function F_{cost} , shown in Fig. 3.21b.

The results of the described design methodology for each D_{so} are stored and plotted together in Fig. 3.22. More in detail, Figure 3.22a shows the computed cost function F_{cost} and a red arrow points the selected $D_{so} = 90$ mm, that is the configuration minimizing F_{cost} . Consequently, the resulting active length l_{rm} is 49.4 mm, that is rounded to 50 mm, and the gearbox ratio i_{gb} is 74.8. These values are the input for the detailed design of the electric machine and of the transmission stage.

EHA global design procedure

For the EHA prototype to be deployed on the bike front fork, the global design procedure is much more constrained due to the strong packaging requirements in Section 3.1.2 that does not leave so much optimization space.

Fig. 3.22 Results of the global design methodology: (a) cost function F_{cost} , (b) motor active length l_{em} , (c) gearbox reduction ratio i_{gb} for each stator outer diameter D_{so} .

The global transmission ratio τ_{cha} is set directly from the speed requirement

$$\tau_{\text{cha}} = \frac{v_{\text{max,cha}}}{\omega_{\text{max,cha}}} = \frac{V_g}{A_p} \quad (3.54)$$

where $v_{\text{max,cha}} = 3 \text{ m/s}$ comes from Section 3.2.1 and $\omega_{\text{max,cha}} = 2618 \text{ rad/s}$ is set to avoid excessive centrifugal forces on the rotor, hence $\tau_{\text{cha}} = 1.15 \text{ mm/rad}$. Consequently, as the piston cross-section A_p is fixed at 3.89 cm^2 , the gerotor volumetric displacement V_g is $2.8 \text{ cm}^3/\text{rev}$.

In ideal conditions, as the pump is rigidly connected to the motor, the required maximum torque can be defined from the maximum force requirement $F_{\text{max,cha}}$ from Section 3.2.1, rearranging Eq. (3.14).

$$T_{\text{max,cha}} = \tau_{\text{cha}} F_{\text{max,cha}} = 2.3 \text{ Nm} \quad (3.55)$$

The maximum differential pressure Δp_{max} supplied by the pump derives from the same considerations, too.

$$\Delta p_{\text{max}} = \frac{F_{\text{max,cha}}}{A_p} = 51.4 \text{ bar} \quad (3.56)$$

3.3.2 Electric machine design

The electric machine detailed design aims to define motor performance and characteristics for the production. The electromagnetic shock absorbers under study are low-voltage 48V actuators to comply with less stringent safety regulations for human health. Furthermore, the growing adoption of HEVs has made the 48V direct current (DC) link readily available.

Taking into account the RSA case study, the main geometrical input comes from the methodology exposed in Section 3.3.1 to achieve the target torque. Those data are summarized in Table 3.7, according to Fig. 3.18.

The winding consists of copper wires with 0.5 mm diameter d_w and insulation thickness of about $30 \mu\text{m}$. The three phases are arranged in a wye configuration. The number of turns per coil N_t and the number of wires in hand N_h need to be specified. These parameters can only take integer values and must satisfy the

Table 3.7 Geometrical parameters of the electric machine for the RSA and EHA.

Description	Symbol	Value		Unit
		RSA	EHA	
Stator outer diameter	D_{so}	90	40	mm
Stator inner diameter	D_{si}	31.8	19.8	mm
Active length	l_{em}	50	76	mm
No. of slots	N_s	12	9	—
Air gap	g_{em}	0.5	0.5	mm
Rotor outer diameter	D_{ro}	30.8	18.8	mm
Rotor inner diameter	D_{ri}	6	3	mm
No. of poles	N_m	10	10	—
Back iron width	w_{bi}	3.4	2.2	mm
Tooth base width	w_{tb}	6.5	3.5	mm
Slot opening	w_s	2	1.8	mm
Slot cross-section	A_s	213.3	45.8	mm ²
Magnet thickness	l_m	1.82	2.36	mm
Shoe width	w_t	6.8	5.3	mm
Shoe dimension 1	d_1	1.5	0.5	mm
Shoe dimension 2	d_2	1.5	0.6	mm

following constraint:

$$N_t N_h \frac{A_w}{A_s} \leq k_{cp,max} \quad (3.57)$$

From Eq. (3.57), it is straightforward that N_t and N_h are inversely proportional. Increasing N_h raises the phase current demand, requiring more expensive power electronics and bulkier cabling. Conversely, a higher N_t increases the BEMF. Therefore, the motor reaches the DC bus voltage limit at a lower rotational speed, thereby reducing the base speed.

Electromagnetic simulations are computed by means of the finite element software Altair FluxMotor. After some iterations, the following parameters are selected: $N_t = 7$ and $N_h = 22$, reaching a gross packing factor $k_{cp} = 0.2835$. With this winding, the theoretical phase resistance is $R_{ph} = 18.14 \text{ m}\Omega$, and the direct and quadrature inductances are $L = 195 \text{ }\mu\text{H}$. The resulting electric machine achieves a peak electrical power of 2.6 kW, a peak torque of 6.8 Nm, a base speed of 3022 rpm, and an average machine efficiency of 83%. Instead, for continuous operations, it delivers a peak electrical power of 1.3 kW, continuous maximum torque of 2.6 Nm, base speed of 4365 rpm, and a machine efficiency of 94%. Figure 3.23a illustrates the map of the power losses in peak operations, i.e., computed with the current density $J_{max} = 20 \text{ A/mm}^2$, along with the maximum torque curve for peak operation (black line) and continuous operation (red dashed line).

Similar considerations apply for the EHA motor. Its main geometrical parameters are reported in Table 3.7, too. The target torque computed in Section 3.3.1 presents a significant challenge due to the highly constrained space. To maximize torque output, a SPM configuration with 9 slots and 10 magnets (Ns9Nm10) is selected. However, manufacturing constraints significantly reduced the maximum performance. In particular, the wire diameter d_w had to be reduced to 0.45 mm, with $N_t = 5$ and $N_h = 9$. As a result, the achieved gross packing factor k_{cp} is 0.3125. As clear from Fig. 3.23b a peak torque of 1.3 Nm can be maintained up to the base speed of 10.57 krpm, which is 1 Nm lower than the target. However, given this motor and the selected τ_{eha} , a peak total force of 3 kN can be applied to the fork up to the motor base speed, meeting the maximum damping requirements. Beyond this point, the fork peak action would gradually decrease due to motor power limitations. This reduction may be acceptable, as degressive damping is preferable at higher suspension speeds. The peak electrical power is about 1.4 kW with an average efficiency in peak working

Fig. 3.23 Power loss map of the electric machine: (a) RSA for the D-SUV, (B) EHA for the bike.

condition of 91%, while in continuous operations, a maximum torque of 0.4 Nm is reachable and a maximum power of about 480 W.

3.3.3 Transmission design

The detailed design of the transmission stage must be divided between the RSA and the EHA due to their distinct technological characteristics.

The RSA deploys a fully electromechanical speed reducer; in the D-SUV case study, a double-stage planetary gearbox is designed, though alternative technologies, such as cycloidal drives, can also be implemented.

In contrast, the EHA incorporates a gerotor volumetric pump stage to supply fluid to the two chambers of the monotube damper, which is housed within both the fork legs.

Mechanical transmissions

As mentioned in Section 3.3.1, the RSA features a double-stage planetary gearbox with fixed ring, three planet gears per stage, and equally distributed reduction ratio $i_{st} = \sqrt{i_{gb}} = 8.65$, as schematized in Fig. 3.24a. The choice is driven by its very high torque density, efficiency, reduced backlash, and optimal load distribution, even for shock loads as typical for a damper, due to the higher number of meshing gears. For compactness, the sun gear of the high-speed (HS) stage is machined onto the electric machine rotor shaft, its carrier also integrates the sun gear of the

Fig. 3.24 Gearbox reference schemes: (a) double-stage planetary gearbox scheme, (b) spur gears, (c) gear profile shift.

Fig. 3.25 Comfort-oriented LQR control strategy on a ISO-C road at 35 km/h: (a) suspension-level working points, (b) duty cycle at RSA output shaft.

low-speed (LS) stage, and the output carrier features a spline shaft for coupling to the crank lever of the linkage. Being also the ring pitch diameter constrained to $D_r = 0.95D_{s0} = 85.5$ mm, the two stages must have the same gear normal module m_n , i.e., the ratio between the pitch diameter of the gear and the number of teeth (see Fig. 3.24b), which is a design variable. This planetary arrangement has a single degree of freedom, meaning it operates with a fixed reduction ratio, defined as follows:

$$i_{st} = \frac{D_r + D_s}{D_s} = \frac{-Z_r + Z_s}{Z_s} \quad (3.58)$$

where Z represents the number of teeth, and the negative sign is necessary because the ring gear is an internal gear. Moreover, it ensures full motion reversibility. The face widths are other design variables, properly sized for structural strength. The gearbox must withstand both overloads and fatigue cycles. The former correspond to the maximum torque condition from the motor $T_{em,max} = 6.8$ Nm, the latter are chosen to be derived from the ISO-C road travelled at 35 km/h with the comfort LQR described in Section 3.2.1. The RSA fatigue duty cycle is represented by a cloud of force-velocity working points (Fig. 3.25a). This data is converted into torque-speed duty cycles for fatigue life estimation by multiplying the forces and dividing the speed by $\tau_{\ell,nom}$ and counting the frequency of occurrence for each discrete torque-speed pair (Fig. 3.25b)

The design procedure is executed by means of the commercial software KISSsoft. A rough sizing calculation defines the module m_n , the number of teeth of the gears Z_i , and the stage face width b_i to realise i_{st} in the available space and sustain the peak

load. The intended material is Steel Grade 3 HRC58-64 AGMA and ISO-VG 68 oil lubrication. The selected solution must respect also the following constraints [127]:

- $6 < b_i/m_n < 20$, to guarantee acceptable strength, uniform meshing, and small elastic deformations;
- $b \leq 1.6m_nZ_s$, to avoid stocky gears that could lose tolerances during manufacturing.

The fine sizing calculation then adjusts the tooth geometry and the stage face width for reaching the best safety factors. The final geometrical output is reported in Table 3.8. Figure 3.24a help visualize the face widths of both stages b_{hs} and b_{ls} and the planet-sun interaxle spacing a_{ps} . The planet-ring one a_{pr} is not sketched as in the ideal gearbox scheme it would coincides with a_{ps} . Figures 3.24b and 3.24c help define the pressure angle α and the gear profile shift coefficient χ^* . Particularly, the effective reduction ratio $i_{st,eff}$ slightly changes with respect to the design target due to the profile modifications. This design leads to the following static safety factors against permanent deformations:

- LS stage with a maximum torque from the sun gear of 58.62 Nm: sun gear 1.72, planet gears 1.67, ring gear 2.24;
- HS stage with a maximum torque from the sun gear of 6.8 Nm: sun gear 5.31, planet gears 5.15, ring gear 6.91.

The fatigue life estimation follows next and is conducted according to the ISO 6336 standards [128], exploiting once again the commercial software KISSsoft. Under the duty cycle shown in Fig. 3.25, the estimated lifespan is approximately 144 hours, equivalent to around 5000 km. Since this is a prototype for a demo vehicle, achieving infinite life is not the primary objective. Additionally, the tested control strategy is highly demanding, and the duty cycle is derived from an ideal model that does not account for realistic force and power saturation, either for the RSA and the control design, that could cut out extreme force-velocity points that negatively affect the fatigue life estimation. Nonetheless, this estimation serves as an initial reference for future industrial development that must extend the fatigue life before proceeding to series production.

Table 3.8 Geometrical parameters of the double-stage planetary gearbox for the RSA.

Description	Symbol	Value	Unit
Normal module	m_n	0.75	mm
Pressure angle	α	20	deg
Sun gear number of teeth	Z_s	15	—
Planet gear number of teeth	Z_p	48	—
Ring gear number of teeth	Z_r	-114	—
HS face width	b_{hs}	5	mm
LS face width	b_{ls}	14	mm
Planet-sun interaxle spacing	a_{ps}	23.625	mm
Planet-ring interaxle spacing	a_{pr}	24.75	mm
Sun gear profile shift coefficient	χ_s^*	0.5491	—
Planet gear profile shift coefficient	χ_p^*	0.5032	—
Ring gear profile shift coefficient	χ_r^*	0.0071	—
Effective stage reduction ratio	$i_{st,eff}$	8.62	—

In the end, the output carrier spline shaft to connect the crank lever is designed according to the DIN 5480:2006 standards [129] and to resist to the maximum output torque $T_{out,max} = 505.2$ Nm. The resulting spline has 28 teeth, a normal module equal to 1 mm, a pressure angle of 30° , and a face width of 20 mm. The coupling hub is machined on the crank lever of the linkage.

Hydrostatic transmission

The EHA damper for the bike front fork incorporates a gerotor pump, which is essential for converting the motor electromagnetic torque into differential pressure. A gerotor gear pump was chosen due to its low tooth wear and adaptability to various fluids [130, 131], in this case the typical oil of passive dampers used by the industrial partner. Its working principle is based on the ideal pure relative rolling motion between the inner gear with N_g number of teeth and outer gear with $N_g + 1$ number of teeth, minimizing mechanical friction and noise. The gears meshing create $N_g + 1$ chambers that reduce their volume each pump revolution, squeezing the fluid. The gears feature trochoidal profiles, making the pump well-suited for

low-to-mid pressure applications up to 100 bar, as well as motion inversion, meeting the specific requirements of this application.

As computed in Section 3.3.1, the target volumetric displacement is $V_g = 2.8 \text{ cm}^3/\text{rev}$. It is strictly dependent to the pump geometry, particularly to the number of chambers $N_g + 1$, to the number of cycles per revolution n_c , and to the unit displacement V_0 , i.e., the difference between the maximum and minimum volume of a chamber [132]. Particularly, for crescent pumps as gerotor ones, $n_c = 1$ because each chamber returns in the same position after a revolution of the driving shaft [132].

$$V_g = n_c V_0 (N_g + 1) \quad (3.59)$$

The variation in chamber volume generates pressure due to the incompressibility of oil. Additionally, the number of inner teeth N_g strongly affects both the performance and the size of the gerotor pump. Given that the external gear has $N_g + 1$ teeth, selecting a lower number of teeth minimizes the pump overall radial size but leads to higher contact stresses and increased flow ripple. This occurs because stresses are distributed over fewer contact points, and larger chambers are needed for the same V_g . Conversely, increasing the number of teeth reduces pressure ripple and contact stress but results in poorer chamber filling and a more restrictive flow passage. Therefore, an optimal design must balance these factors. A commonly used guideline suggests selecting an outer gear with 5 to 11 teeth [133]. For this application $N_g = 6$.

Additional constraints come from packaging. Considering the available space highlighted in Section 3.1.2 and the motor designed in Section 3.3.2, the outer diameter of the outer gear D_{g0} is set to 30 mm as the remaining radial space is needed for a drum with the outlet ports. In the axial direction, there is a total available space of 24 mm. However, the space allocated for the pump is limited to $l_g = 17.5 \text{ mm}$ to axially accommodate also the winding heads, the drum, and the shadow plate. An optimization procedure, incorporating fluid dynamics simulations, is used to determine the optimal tolerances, balancing hydraulic performance and mechanical friction. Specifically, the axial tolerance between the gears and their housing is set to $50 \mu\text{m}$, while the radial tolerance between the outer diameter and the housing is 0.1 mm to provide hydrostatic support for the gears. Additionally, the tooth tip tolerance ranges from a minimum of $40 \mu\text{m}$ to a maximum of $60 \mu\text{m}$.

Fig. 3.26 EHA gerotor pump: (a) 2D profile of the gears (black) and line of contact per revolution (red), (b) displaced volume per revolution (blue) and mean displacement (red).

With an eccentricity of 1.4 mm, the 2D profile of the gears is generated, as shown in Fig. 3.26a. The outer gear features epitrochoidal teeth, as they offer an optimal balance between size, flow ripple, adhesive wear, and subsurface fatigue wear [134]. The resulting displacement has a mean value of 2.92 cc/rev, as depicted in Fig. 3.26b. Hence, the effective EHA transmission ratio $\tau_{\text{cha,eff}}$ is 1.2 mm/rad.

Also in this case, a spline coupling guarantees the torque transmission between the motor shaft and the pump inner gear. By means of the DIN 5480:20006 standards [129], a coupling with 15 teeth, a normal module of 0.5 mm, a pressure angle of 30° , and a face width of 17.5 mm is properly designed.

3.4 Design outcome

In this section, the final outcomes of the two designs are showcased as 3D drawings and manufactured prototypes.

3.4.1 Rotary shock absorber for the D-SUV

As stated in Section 3.3, the designed RSA is common for both the axles of the D-SUV to reduce the part numbers, with levers being the only components that are specific.

Fig. 3.27 RSA prototype for the D-SUV: (a) isometric view of the 3D assembly; (b) cross-section of the 3D drawing: (1) crank lever, (2) LS stage carrier, (3) gearbox cover, (4) gearbox case, (5) HS stage carrier, (6) ring gear, (7) stator, (8) angular position sensor, (9) connector for position sensor, (10) sensor cover, (11) position sensor board, (12) motor phase, (13) motor cover, (14) motor case, (15) rotor, (16) HS stage planet, (17) LS stage planet; (c) manufactured components and final assembly: (1) LS carrier and planets, (2) HS carrier and planets, (3) ring gear, (4) stator and motor case, (5) rotor, (6) pushrod.

The proper choice of bearings, seals, screws, and rotor position sensor, along with the modelling of the external casing, completes the RSA mechanical design. The final outcome is showcased in Fig. 3.27.

The estimated weight is 6.2 kg and the inertia at the output shaft is $I_{\text{out,rsa}} = 0.2 \text{ kgm}^2$ and, considering also the linkage mechanism $I_{\text{tot,rsa}} = 0.227 \text{ kgm}^2$, leading to an ideal equivalent mass $m_{\text{eq,rsa}} = I_{\text{tot,rsa}}/\tau_{\ell,\text{nom}} = 6.35 \text{ kg}$, with nominal τ_{ℓ} . The overall axial size is 203 mm, while the maximum diametrical one is 120 mm. The total rotating inertia is computed as follows:

$$I_{\text{tot,rsa}} = I_{\ell} + I_{\text{ls,c}} + 3i_{\text{p}}^2 I_{\text{ls,p}} + i_{\text{st}}^2 (I_{\text{hs,c}} + 3i_{\text{p}}^2 I_{\text{hs,p}}) + i_{\text{gb}}^2 I_{\text{em}} \quad (3.60)$$

where I_{ℓ} is the inertia of the linkage mechanism in nominal configuration about the RSA axis, I_{em} is the inertia of the rotor shaft about its rotational axis, and all other inertias I are identified by the subscripts "ls" and "hs" for the two stages, and "c" and "p" to distinguish the carrier and the planet gears. In detail, $I_{\ell} = 2.67 \cdot 10^4 \text{ kgmm}^2$, $I_{\text{ls,c}} = 3.93 \cdot 10^2 \text{ kgmm}^2$, $I_{\text{ls,p}} = 13.8 \text{ kgmm}^2$, $I_{\text{hs,c}} = 16.6 \text{ kgmm}^2$, $I_{\text{hs,p}} = 5.18 \text{ kgmm}^2$, and $I_{\text{em}} = 33.87 \text{ kgmm}^2$. Furthermore, i_{p} is the ratio between the rotational speed of the planet and the one of its carrier, $i_{\text{p}} = \omega_{\text{p}}/\omega_{\text{c}} = -Z_{\text{s}}/Z_{\text{p}} - 1$.

3.4.2 Electro-hydrostatic shock absorber for the front bike fork

Two identical EHAs are designed and manufactured to be deployed onto the two legs of the bike front fork. Indeed, the fork originally presents two linear monotube damper acting in parallel. The two EHAs are then connected to them to impose a controllable differential pressure in the two chambers of the dampers, hence force into the suspension.

Also in this case, the proper choice of bearings, seals, screws, and rotor position sensor, along with the modelling of the external casing, completes the EHA mechanical design. A custom purge screw adds to the bill of materials useful to fill the whole EHA with oil and purge the circuit. In fact, trapped air would act as an air spring in the force transmission chain dramatically reducing the actuator force capability and bandwidth. The final outcome is showcased in Fig. 3.28.

For the single motor-pump unit not connected to the fork leg, the estimated weight is 1 kg and the inertia at the output shaft is $I_{\text{tot,cha}} = 13.2 \text{ kgmm}^2$, leading

to an equivalent mass $m_{\text{eq,cha}} = I_{\text{tot,cha}}/\tau_{\text{cha,eff}} = 9.17$ kg. The overall axial size is 151 mm, while the maximum diametrical one is 44 mm. The total rotating inertia is computed as follows:

$$I_{\text{tot,cha}} = I_{\text{em+in}} + \frac{N^2}{(N+1)^2} I_{\text{go}} \quad (3.61)$$

where $I_{\text{em+in}} = 8.12$ kgmm² is the rotating inertia of the rotor shaft coupled to the inner gear of the pump about their rotational axis, and $I_{\text{go}} = 6.93$ kgmm² is the rotating inertia of the outer gear about its own rotational axis.

Fig. 3.28 EHA prototype for the bike front fork: (a) isometric view of the 3D assembly; (b) cross-section of the 3D drawing: (1) shadow plate, (2) outer gerotor gear, (3) inner gerotor gear, (4) case, (5) rotor, (6) stator, (7) angular position sensor, (8) motor phase, (9) position sensor board, (10) purge screw, (11) sensor cover, (12) motor cover; (c) manufactured components and final assembly: (1) gerotor gears, (2) motor cover, (3) sensor board, (4) stator, (5) rotor, (6) case.

Chapter 4

Experimental and numerical validation

This chapter will investigate the actual performance of the designed electromagnetic shock absorbers both at component and vehicle level.

First, the demo vehicles will be introduced, as their setup with active suspension features forms the foundation of the methodological framework of this doctoral thesis (Fig. 1.1). This will be followed by an extensive testing campaign on the prototypes, focusing on efficiency and performance evaluation. The test results from both the component and vehicle levels will be used to validate the models presented in Chapter 3. Finally, advanced control strategies will be proposed and fine-tuned on the basis of the validated models.

4.1 Demo vehicles setup

At the end of the design phase, two vehicle demonstrators have been successfully realized. A D-SUV with four RSA at its corners and naked bike with two EHAs at its front fork. It also installs a RSA prototype at its rear fork but it is out of the scope of this dissertation. Both demonstrators equip a 48V LiFePO4 battery and custom drive electronics for the current control of the electric machines. They also install proper sensors for vehicle states measurements and estimation: potentiometers to measure the suspension strokes, accelerometers on both the sprung and unsprung

masses of the corners, and inertial measurement units (IMUs) to measure the vehicle body motion states.

4.1.1 D-SUV

The final installation on the D-SUV vehicle is shown in Fig. 4.1 and in Fig. 4.2 for the rear and front axles, respectively. Both the final 3D drawings and vehicle photos confirm the validity the packaging investigation and design procedure. Figure 4.1a also illustrates the two steel flanges needed to secure the RSA casing to the suspension subframe, as well as the aluminium bracket used to attach the pushrod to the LCA. Figure 4.2a instead illustrates the connecting bracket to the damper tube and the installation cradle that mounts the RSA to the subframe. This aluminium frame guarantees that the front suspension subframe matches the normal production target torsional stiffness.

Fig. 4.1 D-SUV rear suspension equipped with rotary electromechanical shock absorbers: (a) 3D drawing, (b) vehicle implementation side view, (c) vehicle implementation side view close-up.

Fig. 4.2 D-SUV front suspension equipped with rotary electromechanical shock absorbers: (a) 3D drawing, (b) vehicle implementation side view, (c) vehicle implementation side view close-up.

4.1.2 Naked motorcycle

The final electromagnetic leg and its installation on the naked motorcycle are shown in Fig. 4.3. In more detail, the original leg casing encloses the EHA, a drum with the hydraulic ports and lines, the conventional monotube damper with closed dissipative valves, and the spring assembly, as shown in Fig. 4.3a. The conventional damper is useful for converting the pressure differential produced by the EHA into a linear force as a double-acting through-rod piston and the closed valves avoid unwanted passive damping action. The EHA is screwed onto a printed aluminum drum where the pump seat, the hydraulic ports and lines are obtained. Then, this drum is fitted on the linear damper, as shown in Fig. 4.3c.

Fig. 4.3 Naked motorcycle with electrohydrostatic shock absorbers: (a) active front fork leg with EHA, (b) vehicle setup, (c) damper with EHA close-up.

4.2 Experimental campaign

Both the technologies have undergone an extensive experimental campaign with the objectives of assessing (i) their total efficiency, especially in regeneration working conditions, and (ii) their capability of developing the imposed damping laws. During those tests, the actuators are torque-controlled by their power electronics, which implement a field-oriented control (FOC) strategy to impose the desired current bandwidth to the electric machine [110]. In these applications, the controller sets a bandwidth of 1500 Hz well above ten times the vehicle control loop (100 Hz). As usual in the automotive field, these electronic units communicate with a master node by means of Controller Area Network (CAN) standards.

Moreover, dynamic characterization tests involved the RSA prototype with the aim of identifying the actuator model in Section 3.1.1.

4.2.1 Actuator model identification

In the following sections, two tests on the RSA are presented: (i) a step response test to assess its active force dynamics, (ii) an impedance test in uncontrolled configuration both with open-circuit phases and short-circuit phases to assess its impedance. The results of these tests serve as the basis for parameter estimation of the model presented in Section 3.1.1, and for refining it with non-linear considerations.

Step response test

To analyze the actuation dynamics without any motion input to the system, the free end of the crank lever must be fixed relative to the reference frame. The test bench setup is illustrated in Fig. 4.4. The RSA is mounted on a seismic mass bench by securing it to two test flanges that are rigidly attached to the bench. This setup rigidly connects the RSA to a much larger mass, effectively approximating a constraint to an infinitely stiff wall. A load cell (Gefran TU K5C) is interposed between the crank lever and an additional flange to measure the force generated by the RSA. This configuration also effectively restrains the lever movement and presents a different linkage ratio equal to the lever length $\tau_b = 0.1527$ mm/rad. A dSpace MicroLabBox manages the CAN network between the user-machine interface

Fig. 4.4 Test bench for actuation characterization: (A) RSA, (B) crank lever, (C) load cell, (D) testing flanges, (E) seismic mass bench.

and the power electronics of the RSA. Specifically, the reference torque setpoint is updated at a frequency of 1 kHz. In return, the electronics transmit motor speed and estimated motor torque at 1 kHz, along with DC current measurements at 20 Hz. Additionally, the MicroLabBox acquires the analog signal from the load cell conditioning system (MGCplus Data Acquisition) at a sampling rate of 4 kHz.

The test results are shown in Fig. 4.5. An initial preload of 100 N is applied to the system to eliminate any mechanical clearance. Then, a step reference F_{ref} of 600 N is commanded. As visible in Fig. 4.5a, the motor torque generation delays of exactly 1 ms from the command due to the CAN baud rate. It is an estimate of the actual mechanical torque provided by the motor because the power electronics directly measure the phase currents and then compute the torque knowing the torque constant K_t . The torque trend follows the typical profile of a first-order system as expected and reaches a steady-state torque of 1.2 Nm. This matches the theoretical estimate $T_{\text{em}} = F_{\text{ref}} i_{\text{gb,eff}} / \tau_b = 1.23$ Nm. In contrast, the measured force exhibits the characteristic response of an underdamped second-order system. However, the sudden convergence after the second peak highlights a non-linearity in the mechanical domain. The steady-state value $F_{\text{ss}} = 650$ N slightly exceeds the reference. Actually, the angle between the crank lever line of action and the load cell axis is not 90° , as preferable to perfectly measure the effective force, but it has been

Fig. 4.5 RSA step response from 100 N to 600 N: (a) reference force (dashed blue), measured force (blue), motor torque estimate (orange); (b) measured motor speed.

measured of about 120° (Fig. 4.4). Thus, the load cell would measure a lower force, that is the projection of the effective force along the load cell axis. The discrepancy between the actual measurement and the theoretical one is attributed to the load cell hysteresis and drift, and additional axial load induced by an unwanted bending moment. In fact, ideally, the load cell should be mounted between two ball joints to isolate axial loads. However, in this setup, one end is rigidly fixed to the flange due to limitations in available instrumentation, as visible in Fig. 4.4. Despite this, the RSA dynamic behavior is effectively captured. The system parameters for dynamic estimation rely primarily on response time and overshoot percentage. Moreover, from Fig. 4.5b, the motor shaft oscillations during the transient phase clearly indicate the elastic nature of the system. A steady-state DC current of approximately 0.5 A is drawn by the electronics due to internal losses, with a peak of around 2 A occurring during the transient. Additional detailed results are summarized in Table 4.1.

Impedance test

For these tests, the RSA is actuated using an electro-hydrostatic test rig, depicted in Fig. 4.6. This setup applies alternating displacement profiles to the RSA, with its crank lever connected to a hydraulic actuator, hence the kinematic ratio τ_b remains valid. The test rig actuator comprises a double-acting cylinder powered by a positive-displacement pump (Parker MGG20030). Line pressures are monitored via two membrane pressure sensors (Gefran TK). A pre-charge pressure of approximately

Table 4.1 Step response results for the RSA.

Feature	Value	Unit
Rise time	3.5	ms
Peak-peak time	17	ms
Settling time	35.5	ms
Overshoot	59.2	%
Max force	1034.5	N
Max motor speed	-652	rpm
Max DC current	2.1	A
Actuation delay	1	ms
Steady-state motor torque	1.25	Nm
Steady-state force	650	N

Fig. 4.6 Test bench for damping tests: (A) crank lever, (B) RSA, (C) testing flange, (D) test bench actuator, (E) MEMS accelerometer, (F) load cell.

20 bar is fed into the circuit before the test begins to prevent cavitation under high pressure differentials. The pump shaft is mechanically linked to a driving motor (Kollmorgen DBL5 1700 brushless PM motor) via a bellows expansion joint, enabling inherently bidirectional motion. Motor control is handled by a dedicated inverter unit (Kollmorgen Servostar S748). The hydraulic piston is equipped with a magnetostrictive position transducer (Gefran RK2) to track its stroke. A load cell (Gefran TU K5C), positioned between the piston head and the load lever tip, measures the applied force. The signal is conditioned by a MGCplus Data Acquisition system and converted to analog, as in Section 4.2.1. A dSpace MicroLabBox still serves as the central control unit, acquiring all measurement data at a sampling frequency f_s of 4 kHz. It also sets the reference torque to the driving motor control unit via CAN communication to realize a closed-loop angular position control [135]. The MicroLabBox is further connected to a PC, which functions as the human-machine interface.

The PID controller for the position control of the hydraulic actuator is properly tuned before the testing procedure. This procedure consists in applying a sinusoidal motion to the crank lever tip. Discrete frequencies are span from 0.5 to 30 Hz due to test bench bandwidth limitations. The displacement amplitude is properly selected for each tested frequency to avoid instabilities between 5 and 10 Hz, since a test bench resonance was found in this frequency range, and too large attenuation at higher frequencies. An additional feedforward harmonics is added to the reference displacement at 70 Hz with a very small amplitude to contrast stick-slip phenomenon.

Tests are conducted in both open circuit (OC) phases configuration, i.e., phases disconnected from any power electronics or external resistance. and short circuit (SC) one, i.e., phases shorted together, to estimate the RSA impedance in the two extreme regenerative configurations. Representative results from a 1 Hz test are presented in Fig. 4.7. The measured crank angle exhibits noticeable irregularities in both configurations, highlighting the test rig limited bandwidth and its inability to accurately impose the desired displacement profile on the RSA. The maximum force generated by the RSA occurs at zero displacement, i.e., the peak velocity instant, indicating that, at low frequencies, the RSA primarily behaves as a damper. Figure 4.7a demonstrates the limited damping force output of the RSA in fail-safe (OC) conditions, where meshing vibrations largely dominate the force signal. Instead, Figure 4.7b highlights the presence of backlash, with distinct dead bands visible at motion reversals instants.

Fig. 4.7 RSA impedance test at 1 Hz: (a) open circuit configuration, (b) short circuit configuration.

In order to estimate the impedance of the RSA in the two configurations, the acquired force and displacement data undergo a frequency analysis. Specifically, time domain signals can be expressed in frequency domain by applying the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) algorithm to compute their Discrete Fourier transforms (DFTs). Considering a time history of the imposed displacement acquired at a fixed sample rate $x[n]$, its DFT is computed as

$$X[k] = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x[n] \cdot e^{-2\pi j \frac{kn}{N}}, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, N-1 \quad (4.1)$$

where $N = T_0 f_s$ and T_0 is the length of the signal. The FFT is also applied to the load cell signal and the magnitude of the impedance for each test is computed as

$$Z[f_t] = \frac{F[f_t]}{2\pi f_t X[f_t]} \quad (4.2)$$

where f_t is the frequency of the reference displacement profile.

The resulting impedance is plotted in Fig. 4.8. The open circuit one shows a decreasing gain from 0.5 Hz to 2 Hz, highlighting a non-linear friction contribution. The peak at 5 Hz demonstrates the experienced resonance of the test bench. Then, the increasing gain from 7 Hz detects the increasing inertial effect of the RSA approaching its resonance. In contrast, the short circuit impedance shows much higher low frequency gain due to the induced back-electromotive force. The impedance bandwidth is dominated by the angular frequency of the electromagnetic pole of the electric machine [103, 101], which cuts out the RSA resonant amplification at high

Fig. 4.8 Estimated RSA impedance: open circuit (blue) and short circuit (orange) configurations.

frequency. The resonance of the test rig in the 5–10 Hz range remains noticeable, marked by a disruption in the expected decreasing trend.

Model identification

On the basis of the previous tests, the lumped parameters in Eq. (3.10) can be estimated. To reduce the number of variables, the equivalent mass m_{eq} is computed from the 3D drawings of the RSA with only the crank lever and it is equal to 8.68 kg. Assuming a second order system, the damping ratio ζ can be estimated from the following equation

$$M_p = 100 e^{\frac{-\pi\zeta}{\sqrt{1-\zeta^2}}} \quad (4.3)$$

where M_p is the overshoot of the step response and it is equal to 59.2% as reported in Table 4.1. The resulting ζ is equal to 0.16 highlighting a strongly underdamped system as expected.

Then, knowing the peak-peak time T_d from Table 4.1, the natural frequency of the system ω_n can be computed as

$$\omega_n = \frac{2\pi}{T_d \sqrt{1-\zeta^2}} \quad (4.4)$$

Table 4.2 Estimated parameters for the RSA.

Parameter	Value	Unit
m_{eq}	8.68	kg
k_{m}	$1.22 \cdot 10^6$	N/m
c_{m}	50	Ns/m
c_{eq}	991	Ns/m
c_{l}	∞	Ns/m
ω_{n}	374	rad/s
ζ	0.16	—

From the natural frequency ω_{n} , the estimation of the mount stiffness k_{m} and the equivalent damping c_{eq} follows

$$k_{\text{m}} = \omega_{\text{n}}^2 m_{\text{eq}} \quad (4.5)$$

$$c_{\text{eq}} = 2\zeta \sqrt{k_{\text{m}} m_{\text{eq}}} - c_{\text{m}} \quad (4.6)$$

with the mount damping $c_{\text{m}} = 50$ Ns/m. This mount damping value is based on previous works on this technology [108], and is considered reasonable since the RSA features a rigid steel transmission chain from the motor to the lever tip. The estimated parameters and dynamic characteristics are summarized in Table 4.2.

However, as non-linear frictions emerge from the step response, a Coulomb friction model is added to the viscous friction $c_{\text{eq}}\dot{x}_{\text{eq}}$ [136]. In detail, the friction force F_{f} is expressed as non-linear function of the speed \dot{x}_{eq}

$$F_{\text{f}} = F_{\text{c}} \cdot \tanh\left(\frac{\dot{x}_{\text{eq}}}{v_{\text{c}}}\right) + c_{\text{eq}}\dot{x}_{\text{eq}} \quad (4.7)$$

where F_{c} is the Coulomb friction that represents a constant offset and v_{c} is the Coulomb velocity threshold. In this case study, F_{c} is set to 20 N as the amplitude of the force response during the OC impedance test at 0.5 Hz and v_{c} to 0.001 m/s.

The modelling results for the step test are shown in Fig. 4.9. Regarding the force response (Fig. 4.9a), both models accurately capture the rise time and the peak-to-peak period, effectively representing the systems resonant behaviour. The linear model exhibits additional oscillations due to its underdamped nature, whereas the

Fig. 4.9 Comparison among step test results, linear model, and model with Coulomb friction model: (a) force response, (b) electric motor speed.

non-linear model closely reproduces the force time history because it flattens to the steady-state value soon after the second peak after the initial overshoot. Remaining discrepancies in magnitude are attributed to improper load cell installation and unmodelled nonlinear phenomena, such as mechanical backlash and a frequency-dependent Stribeck-like effect, as highlighted by the impedance profile in Fig. 4.8. Backlash has also a significant influence, as it leads to impact loads within the gearbox. This is evidenced in Fig. 4.9b, where constant velocity segments appear at the speed peaks. As the gearbox and rotor shaft cover backlash gaps during motion reversal, larger speed peaks occur following the first overshoot. The velocity magnitude is further influenced by the aforementioned unmodelled Stribeck effect.

Figure 4.10a presents the comparison between the linear impedance transfer function in Eq. (3.10) and the OC experimental curve. It demonstrates that the use of a linear equivalent damping overestimates frictions.

Passing to the SC impedance, neglecting the leakage damping as valid for the RSA, it can be linearly modelled by the following transfer function in Laplace domain [103, 101]

$$Z(s) = \frac{s + \frac{1}{m_{eq}} \left[c_{eq} + \frac{c_{max}}{(s\omega_e + 1)} \right]}{s^2 + \frac{1}{m_{eq}} \left(c_{eq} + c_m + \frac{c_{max}}{\omega_e + 1} \right) + \omega_n^2} (s c_m + k_m) \quad (4.8)$$

where $c_{max} = \frac{3K_e^2}{2\tau^2 R}$ is the short circuit damping, with K_e being the phase back electromotive constant, and $\omega_e = R_{ph}/L$ is the angular frequency of the electromagnetic pole, with L being the inductance in the direct and quadrature synchronous coordi-

Fig. 4.10 Comparison between impedance test results and models: (a) open circuit configuration, (b) short circuit configuration.

nates. This model differs from Eqs. (3.10) and (3.12) because the short-circuited phases introduce the electromagnetic dynamics of the actuator in the impedance response. From preliminary measurements on the produced stator following the design methodology in Chapter 3, the phase back electromotive constant K_e is equal to 42 mVs/rad, the phase resistance $R_{ph} = 17 \text{ m}\Omega$, and the inductance $L = 245 \text{ }\mu\text{H}$, hence these values slightly differ from the one reported in Section 3.3.2 deriving from electromagnetic simulations. Looking at the magnitude in Fig. 4.10b, it is clear that the electric machine is experiencing a strong amplitude reduction of the SC braking torque with respect to the linear model. As described by Tonoli [137], eddy current brakes, as for example shunted electric machines, exhibit a clear deviation from the linear behaviour typically associated with the torque constant K_t as their electrical speed approaches the electromagnetic pole frequency. The braking torque reaches its maximum when the electrical speed matches the pole frequency, beyond which it non-linearly decreases with further increases in speed. For example, during the test with crank lever displacement amplitude of 2° at 0.5 Hz, the measured rotor speed amplitude is $\omega_{em} \approx 7 \text{ rad/s}$. Being the pole pair $p = 5$, the electrical speed reaches about $\Omega = p\omega_{em} = 35 \text{ rad/s}$, that is almost the 50% of the electromagnetic pole $\omega_e = 70.1 \text{ rad/s}$. From [137], the developed braking torque would result about 20% lower than the expected with a linear model. Considering the linear model and the estimated SC impedance, the latter results about 36% lower, confirming the non-linear phenomenon occurrence. The marginal discrepancy between these two reduction values can be attributed to measurement errors and test bench limitations, as the resonance between 5 and 10 Hz demonstrates.

In conclusion, linear models predicts the main dynamic characteristics of an electromagnetic shock absorbers, but real implementations highlight a strong influence of non-linear phenomena, particularly frictions and electromagnetic torque saturation, that need further modelling steps.

4.2.2 Efficiency tests

Efficiency estimation from experimental tests defines the actual regeneration capabilities in steady-state conditions. Although those systems work in highly dynamic conditions, steady-state efficiency still represents their upper limit in terms of energy performance.

Under dynamic conditions, SPM motors experience increased copper losses due to rapid current variations and high-peak currents. Iron losses also rise, driven by hysteresis from continuous magnetic polarity reversals in the stator core, as well as eddy currents generated by time-varying magnetic fields. Additionally, rapid changes in the stator field can induce eddy currents within the magnets themselves, and torque ripple becomes more pronounced.

In the RSA, gearbox efficiency is reduced by micro-slip between gear teeth, backlash, inertial effects, lubricant churning, localized heating, and micro-oscillations.

Finally, in the EHA, the main contributors to efficiency degradation include cavitation, increased internal leakage due to varying clearances, fluid inertia and compressibility effects, non-uniform flow, and pressure pulsations.

In the following, both active and regenerative steady-state efficiencies for the RSA are reported, while only the regenerative one for the EHA. The custom test benches are described, too.

Electromechanical

The efficiency testing campaign is conducted on a custom-built test bench with a previous smaller version of RSA, as illustrated in Fig. 4.11. This smaller RSA was designed to fit a smaller vehicle, so it still deploys a high-reduction, double-stage planetary gearbox with 1:87.35 reduction ratio but paired with a smaller motor, capable of delivering a peak torque of 1.9 Nm and a peak power of 0.97 kW. The prototype was replaced due to the need to couple a pulley to the output shaft, which

Fig. 4.11 Test bench for the RSA steady-state characterization.

is not feasible with the D-SUV RSA because of its casing design. Centralized control is achieved CAN communication from a human-machine interface. A constant speed reference is sent to the servomotor control unit, while a linearly increasing torque reference is applied to the RSA electronic control unit. The servo motor (Kollmorgen DBL5-1700) operates as a dyno load to counteract the RSA control strategy. Both machines are mechanically coupled through a 2:1 ratio belt transmission using a preloaded toothed belt (HTD 8M). The servo motor is driven by a dedicated inverter (Kollmorgen Servostar S748), while the RSA is powered by the inverter designed for the vehicle installation and supplied by the expected 48V battery. Both inverters measure phase currents and voltages, supply current and voltage, and motor angular speed. These current measurements allow for torque estimation of both electric machines.

As previously mentioned, a constant speed setpoint is applied to the driving servomotor during the tests. At the same time, the RSA operates under current control to generate a quasi-static torque ramp, with either a positive (active) or negative (regenerative) slope of $\pm 0.1 \text{ Nm/s}$. Torque is limited to $\pm 1.5 \text{ Nm}$ due to test bench constraints. Throughout this process, all necessary measurements are collected to enable a comprehensive efficiency evaluation. The procedure is repeated for various servomotor speeds, ranging from 500 to 3500 rpm in 500 rpm increments of the RSA motor. The speed of 3500 rpm is approximately the 71% of the motor base speed and the 14% of the maximum speed. This limitation comes from the need

Fig. 4.12 Measured and fitted (solid line) power at RSA power supply (blue), RSA electric machine mechanical power (orange), and servomotor mechanical power (green) for the active test at 2000 rpm.

to avoid overspeed errors in the servomotor power electronics, which could trigger a shutdown and cause unstable acceleration of the RSA under test.

The overall conversion efficiency of the RSA is evaluated in two of the four operating quadrants, corresponding to active and regenerative modes, as defined by Eqs. (4.9) and (4.10), respectively.

$$\eta_{\text{act}} = \frac{T_{\text{km}} \omega_{\text{km}}}{V_{\text{dc}} I_{\text{dc}}} \quad (4.9)$$

$$\eta_{\text{reg}} = \frac{V_{\text{dc}} I_{\text{dc}}}{T_{\text{km}} \omega_{\text{km}}} \quad (4.10)$$

where ω_{km} and T_{km} are the torque and speed of the driving motor, while I_{dc} and V_{dc} are the voltage and current of the battery. In active operation, the RSA delivers mechanical power to the load. In contrast, passive operation refers to the regeneration of electrical power over a broad region of the torque-speed plane while the RSA brakes the servomotor torque.

The driving motor torque T_{km} is estimated from the measured phase current amplitude $I_{\text{ph,km}}$, considering a fixed torque constant $K_{\text{t,km}}$.

$$T_{\text{km}} = K_{\text{t,km}} I_{\text{ph,km}} \quad (4.11)$$

The driving motor torque T_{km} and speed ω_{km} , along with the RSA power electronics measurements, i.e., the DC current I_{dc} and voltage V_{dc} , are directly used to compute power at both ends of the system. The electrical quantities are used to determine the power at the RSA DC link. Although the presence of the toothed belt

transmission slightly affects the efficiency estimation since it typically operates with an efficiency of about $95 \div 98\%$, the driving motor quantities are the only measurements that account for the gearbox losses. In fact, the only mechanical measurements available for the RSA are the electric machine torque and speed. The power data are then fitted to second-degree polynomial function to estimate efficiency along the entire torque ramp, as shown in Fig. 4.12.

The resulting efficiency maps are shown in Fig. 4.13 with normalized torque and speed with respect to the maximum torque and speed values of this smaller RSA version in order to provide more general insights on the RSA solution. Indeed, a similar efficiency behaviour is expected for any RSA sharing the same mechanical arrangement. In the tested active quadrant (Fig. 4.13(a)), the RSA achieves a maximum efficiency of 72% and, overall, it is characterized by quite high efficiencies. It should be noted that these efficiency values include the contributions of the RSA power electronics, RSA motor and gearbox, toothed belt transmission, and servo motor. Therefore, the actual efficiency of the RSA alone is expected to be slightly higher. The reduction in efficiency at higher torque levels is primarily attributed to copper losses in the electric machine, whereas the efficiency drop near zero torque is mainly due to mechanical friction. Predictably, the regenerative efficiencies (Fig. 4.13(b)) are lower than the active ones due the lower efficiency of the electric machine in generator mode, as well as in the power electronics when converting alternate current. The mechanical efficiency remains the same as it depends on the normal forces at the contact points and on the friction coefficients of the bodies in relative motion, apart from possible deviations from the normal working condition, e.g., misalignments. A maximum value of 66% is attained. As above, the regenerative efficiency of the RSA alone is expected to be slightly higher. The regenerative map is more constrained in torque and speed than the active one due to the larger mechanical power involved in the tests and the consequent limitations of the test rig. Indeed, during regenerative operation, the servomotor must maintain the target speed by overcoming the resistance of the RSA and all the mechanical losses involved in the test bench. In contrast, during active tests, these mechanical losses help to brake the torque imposed by the RSA, helping to maintain the target speed.

Table 4.3 reports a summary of the results. Quantitatively, they are common to this kind of electromechanical scheme of electromagnetic shock absorber, so the tests are valid even if executed on smaller RSA than the one designed in Chapter 3 for the D-SUV.

Fig. 4.13 RSA efficiency maps: (a) active, (b) regenerative.

Table 4.3 Efficiency test results for the RSA in steady-state conditions.

Feature	Value	Unit
Active peak efficiency	72	%
Active average efficiency	60	%
Active peak current	12.3	A
Regenerative peak efficiency	66	%
Regenerative average efficiency	49	%
Regenerative peak current	-6.7	A

Fig. 4.14 Test bench for the EHA steady-state characterization.

Electro-hydrostatic

The custom test bench used for EHA testing is shown in Fig. 4.14. A motor-pump unit (Kollmorgen AKM42G motor coupled to a Casappa PLP10 pump) provides a constant flow rate Q_{eha} , which corresponds to a virtual constant damper velocity given by $v = Q_{\text{eha}}/A_p$. The two hydraulic lines are connected to a custom-designed steel flange that replicates the inlet–outlet configuration of the motorcycle leg system. On the low-pressure side, an accumulator (FOX GR2) is positioned at the highest point of the hydraulic circuit to provide volume compensation, heat dissipation, and purging during tests. The EHA generates a braking differential pressure $\Delta p = p_1 - p_0$, which results in a virtual linear damper force $F = \Delta p A_p$. Braking torque is applied by controlling phase currents through a dedicated power stage powered by a 48V battery, consistent with the vehicle configuration described in Section 4.1.2. The DC link current i_{dc} is measured using an amperometric clamp.

The test procedure applies a constant speed ω_{km} to the driving motor, varied from 300 to 6000 rpm. Pressures p_0 and p_1 are measured using two membrane pressure sensors (Gefran TK), while the flow rate Q_{eha} is measured via a turbine-based flow meter (KEM HM11). The EHA rotational speed ω_{eha} is directly obtained from its built-in sensor on the electric machine rotor shaft. All measurements are simultaneously acquired using a SIEMENS Simcenter SCADAS Lab data acquisition system.

Considering a steady-state driving speed, the input hydraulic power is computed as

$$P_h = \Delta\tilde{p}\tilde{Q}_{\text{cha}} \quad (4.12)$$

where the symbol \sim refers to the mean value of the acquisitions.

The EHA mechanical power and the output electrical power can be computed, too:

$$P_m = \Delta\tilde{p}_m V_g \tilde{\omega}_m \quad (4.13)$$

$$P_e = V_{\text{dc}} \tilde{i}_{\text{dc}} \quad (4.14)$$

where V_g is the EHA pump displacement as in 3.3.3. Efficiencies can be computed as a consequence

$$\eta_v = \frac{P_m}{P_h} \quad (4.15)$$

$$\eta_{\text{em}} = \frac{P_e}{P_m} \quad (4.16)$$

$$\eta_t = \frac{P_e}{P_h} = \eta_{\text{em}} \eta_v \quad (4.17)$$

where η_v is the EHA volumetric efficiency, η_{em} is the EHA electromechanical efficiency, and η_t is the EHA total conversion efficiency in regenerative mode.

The test results are presented in Fig. 4.15. Efficiencies are evaluated at discrete operating points of interest, spanning the range between the minimum and maximum damping requirements. This is done by current-controlling the EHA electric machine imposing the following quadrature axis current $i_{q,\text{ref}} = [0 \ 5 \ 10 \ 15 \ 20 \ 30]$ A and null direct axis current.

The electromechanical efficiency is significantly affected by high friction losses (Fig. 4.15a). In particular, the absence of roller bearings on the outer gear due to packaging constraints [104] severely limits the mechanical efficiency of the pump. Additionally, the increased gear length makes manufacturing tolerances much less constant, resulting in challenging gear meshing conditions. The overall efficiency trend aligns with the electric machine efficiency map, showing peak performance about 40% in the medium-torque, medium-speed region.

Instead, the volumetric efficiency map shows much optimal values, with peak values around 90% (Fig. 4.15b). Predictably, it markedly falls at high torques due to increased leakages.

Finally, the total conversion efficiency is clearly a combination of the two, as visible

Fig. 4.15 EHA regenerative efficiency maps: (a) electromechanical efficiency, (b) pump volumetric efficiency, (c) total conversion.

Table 4.4 Efficiency test results for the EHA in steady-state regenerative conditions.

Feature	Value	Unit
Electromechanical peak efficiency	42	%
Electromechanical average efficiency	31	%
Volumetric peak efficiency	98	%
Volumetric average efficiency	77	%
Total peak efficiency	35	%
Total average efficiency	24	%

in Fig. 4.15c. The electromechanical efficiency dominates the overall regeneration performance, thus the 35% peak efficiency is reached in the medium-torque, medium-speed region. A summary of the efficiency test on the EHA is reported in Table 4.4. In general, higher efficiency levels can be achieved with gerotor pumps; however, this requires greater packaging flexibility than the one offered by this application.

This test also confirmed compliance with the damping requirements outlined in Section 3.2.1, as both damping curves were successfully achieved in regenerative operation. To reach force–speed points beyond the regenerative region defined by these curves, active power input is required.

4.2.3 Controlled damping

Controlled damping tests are performed to assess the RSA and EHA performance when controlled as dampers under dynamic conditions, i.e., subjected to sinusoidal input displacement. To this end, the RSA needs a custom test bench due to its uncommon working principle for automotive dampers, while the EHA is tested on a shaker test bench put at the disposal by the industrial partner.

Electromechanical

Damping tests for the RSA are also performed on the custom test bench in Fig. 4.6. The hydraulic actuator is position-controlled to impose sinusoidal displacement profiles to the crank lever tip. Speed amplitudes discretely span from 0.05 m/s to 0.5

Fig. 4.16 RSA damping tests: (a) force experimental points and fitted curve, (b) average DC power experimental points and fitted curve.

m/s. Conversely, the RSA is torque-controlled with the following control law

$$T_{em} = -c \underbrace{\left(\frac{\tau_b}{i_{gb,eff}} \right)^2}_{c_{em}} \omega_{em} \quad (4.18)$$

where c is the desired mechanical damping at the crank tip, while c_{em} is the equivalent damping at the motor shaft. The decision to directly brake the RSA motor speed ω_{em} stems from in-vehicle observations of instability caused by non-collocated control when attempting to damp the suspension speed v directly.

Figure 4.16 displays the main results; cross markers denote actual measured force-speed points following the damper convention, i.e., positive forces oppose velocity, while dashed lines the fitted curves. Experimental points in Fig. 4.16a derive from the same post-processing procedure described in Section 4.2.1. Force-speed experimental data are perfectly fitted by linear curves demonstrating the system capability of acting as a controllable damper.

DC power experimental points result from the product of the constant battery voltage $V_{dc} = 53$ V and the mean value of the measured current I_{dc} during the test. Predictably, the DC power trends as function of the speed are well fitted by quadratic curves (Fig. 4.12). Negative power values prove the regeneration capability of the device. Table 4.5 evidences the results of the fitting procedures on the force-speed points,

Table 4.5 Damping test results for the RSA under sinusoidal excitation.

Test damping	Slope [Ns/m]	Offset [N]	Force R^2	Power R^2
200 Ns/m	344	20	0.9972	0.9753
500 Ns/m	625	27	0.9997	0.9998
857 Ns/m	989	27	0.9999	0.9999
1 kNs/m	1140	26	0.9999	0.9998
1.5 kNs/m	1657	27	0.9997	0.9996
2 kNs/m	1943	63	0.9890	0.9952

Fig. 4.17 Force-displacement curves of a 2 kNs/m damping test for the RSA prototype for all the tested speeds ($v_1 = 0.05$ m/s, $v_2 = 0.1$ m/s, $v_3 = 0.2$ m/s, $v_4 = 0.3$ m/s, $v_5 = 0.4$ m/s, $v_6 = 0.5$ m/s)

i.e., the slope and offset of the fitting straight line; the coefficient of determination R^2 is well above 0.9 for both the force and power demonstrating the goodness of fit. Force slopes almost follow the imposed damping with a small difference ranging from 125 to 157 Ns/m due to internal mechanical frictions. Instead, offsets capture the Coulomb friction contribution because it is a constant force value that adds to the speed-dependent component determined by the slope multiplied by the speed magnitude.. Small discrepancies can be found in the 2 kNs/m test, where the smaller slope than the expected one is compensated by a higher offset value. Indeed, the test with 2 kNs/m damping reaches torque amplitudes of about 2.4 Nm at 0.5 m/s, hence motor continuous torque limit is approached.

Fig. 4.18 Time history of a 2 kNs/m damping test at 0.2 m/s for the RSA prototype measured force (blue), estimated motor torque (orange).

Figure 4.17 the force-displacement curves of the 2 kNs/m test. The tests present different displacement amplitudes since frequencies can not exceed 3 Hz to avoid a test bench resonance that would invalidate the measurements. Since in sinusoidal displacement the amplitude of the speed depends on both the test frequency f_t and displacement amplitude x , i.e., $v = 2\pi f_t x$, these two parameters are adjusted together to avoid resonance while still achieving the target speed. The results demonstrate the symmetry of the device, as well as the force oscillations induced by gear meshing. Additionally, at higher speeds, the flattening of the curve evidences the force/torque saturation above mentioned.

Figure 4.18 presents the time history of the measured force and motor torque during the test conducted at 0.2 m/s with a required damping of 2 kNs/m. The flat regions around motion inversion are attributed to gearbox backlash, forming noticeable dead bands. The close overlap between the force and torque curves highlights the high bandwidth of the system; however, an accurate time delay cannot be quantified from these measurements due to differences in the dSpace sampling frequency and the CAN bus baud rate. Furthermore, a clear gain of approximately $i_{gb,eff}/\tau_b$ is observed between the force and the motor torque, indicating that the motor is operating within its constant-torque region. It is also worth noting that the force measurements are influenced by the dynamic behaviour of the RSA, with pronounced spikes at peak velocity resulting from its mechanical impedance. Indeed, according to Eq. (3.10), negative actuation F_a , as occurs when the RSA is controlled as a damper, would sum with the speed-dependent contribution from H_v .

Fig. 4.19 Test bench for damping tests: (A) damper with EHA, (B) battery pack electronics, (C) 48V battery, (D) test bench actuator, (E) load cell, (F) test bench control panel.

Ultimately, the damping test validated the RSA as a regenerative damper; however, implementing a feedforward controller to compensate for its dynamic behaviour, especially its inerter-like characteristic, could further improve overall force tracking performance. Feedback control is trickier to be implemented as a real-time load sensing device should be added downstream crank lever.

Electro-hydrostatic

The electromagnetic damper, shown in Fig. 4.3c, is tested using an MTS shaker test bench (Fig. 4.19). The bench is capable of delivering peak forces exceeding 20 kN and peak velocities up to 4 m/s. It allows the application of arbitrary displacement profiles to the damper rod, while the corresponding reaction force is measured by a load cell mounted on the opposite end of the damper.

For the following tests, sinusoidal displacements with an amplitude of $X = 25$ mm and variable frequencies are applied, resulting in peak velocities ranging from 0.1 to 0.5 m/s. These velocities correspond to typical damper behaviour on uneven road

Fig. 4.20 EHA damping tests: (a) passive controlled damping experimental force-speed points and fitted curve, (b) active controlled damping experimental force-speed points and fitted curve.

surfaces without lumped obstacles. Each frequency test is repeated five times to obtain an average of the measured peak forces. The EHA is torque-controlled to reproduce a fixed-damping law, as explicit in Eq. (4.18). Both passive (positive) and active (negative) electromagnetic damping coefficients c are imposed, ranging from 200 to 2000 Ns/m. An open circuit (OC) test is also performed to assess the minimum damping due to mechanical frictions c_{\min} .

Figure 4.20 presents both the discrete measured forces with cross markers and the interpolated damping curves with dashed lines. The plots follow the damper force convention due to the test bench settings, i.e., positive force for passive damping. A simple linear regression accurately fits all damping curves, all achieving a coefficient of determination of $R^2 = 0.99$, with the exception of the two highest active damping cases at -1.5 and -2 kNs/m, where a quadratic regression provides a better fit. This deviation is attributed to force saturation effects caused by power limitations in both the EHA and the test bench, as shown in Fig. 4.20b. A nearly null damping curve can be obtained by imposing a negative active damping of 750 Ns/m, i.e., counteracting the OC damping, while passive damping curves start above the OC damping and the active ones below, as expected.

Test results are reported in Table 4.6. The 750 Ns/m test reaches a very low value of R^2 due to the strong instability of the undamped test. As already explained, fitted

Table 4.6 Damping test results for the EHA under sinusoidal excitation.

Test damping	Slope [Ns/m]	Offset [N]	Force R^2
200 Ns/m	1033	-6.8	0.9987
500 Ns/m	1550	-51	0.9987
750 Ns/m	1650	-37	0.9969
1 kNs/m	2112	-95	0.9975
1.5 kNs/m	2418	-104	0.9933
2 kNs/m	2304	-16	0.9960
OC	805	4	0.9957
-250 Ns/m	592	10	0.9949
-500 Ns/m	235	31	0.9954
-750 Ns/m	0.96	15	0.0032
-1 kNs/m	-488	9.8	0.9975
-1.5 kNs/m	-	-	0.9933
-2 kNs/m	-	-	0.9960

slopes are increased by the system internal friction, that can be approximated to an additional damping coefficient equal to the OC damping c_{oc} .

Figure 4.21 shows the force-displacement curves from the test at 2 kNs/m. The EHA exhibits a symmetric response, with fluctuations primarily caused by pump gear meshing and flow ripples, particularly noticeable at higher pressures, such as at 0.5 m/s. Compared to the RSA (Fig. 4.17), the EHA curves appear smoother, indicating greater internal damping due to friction and leakage effects. This is further supported by the force time history in Fig. 4.22, which displays a more sinusoidal pattern. As expected, the peak force occurs at zero stroke. The actively controlled forces, however, exhibit a more nervous behaviour, indicating a less stable interaction between the shaker and the prototype. This is likely due to the reduced passive resistance from the EHA. Since the active force exerted by the EHA assists the imposed motion, the shaker exerts less driving effort, which in turn reduces the overall mechanical damping of the system and may amplify dynamic instabilities.

In conclusion, the EHA damping tests validate the use of this system as regenerative and active suspension. As the force response is more affected by the

Fig. 4.21 Force-displacement curves of a 2 kNs/m damping test for the EHA prototype at 0.1 m/s (blue), 0.2 m/s (orange), 0.3 m/s (yellow), 0.5 m/s (purple).

Fig. 4.22 Time history of a 2 kNs/m damping test at 0.2 m/s for the EHA prototype: measured force with regenerative damping (blue), measured force with active damping (orange), imposed stroke (yellow). The test bench outputs braking forces with positive values as dampers convention.

pump hydraulics, a pressure feedback controller could be implemented for a more precise force tracking. This is already a common practice in industrial hydraulic electromagnetic shock absorbers by adding a pressure sensor in the component.

4.2.4 NVH tests

Acoustic performance plays a key role for new automotive components due to the transition toward quieter electrified drive modules. In parallel with the efficiency characterization of Section 4.2.2, an NVH analysis is carried out on the RSA smaller prototype. To this aim, three accelerometers (PCB Piezotronics) are placed on the prototype, two on the gearbox housing and one on the electric machine cover (Fig. 4.11), and two free-field microphones (AVM MI 17) are positioned at one-meter distance from the RSA. One is placed behind the motor, while the other faces the gearbox. Noise and vibration data are recorded using a Siemens LMS SCADAS III data logger.

Despite tests are not conducted inside an anechoic chamber (reverberating environment condition), the acoustic data remain valuable. They highlight noise trends under varying operating conditions and reflect vibrational behaviour. The presented NVH analysis focuses only on the RSA in active modes, as regenerative modes evidenced similar trends. Furthermore, this activity is part of a broader study that the research group is conducting to compare an RSA equipped with a planetary gearbox to one with a cycloidal drive. As long as the boundary conditions remain consistent, the comparative analysis retains its validity.

In general, the vibrational spectrum of an electric machine coupled to a gearbox exhibits some relevant frequencies [138]: the gear meshing frequency (GMF) and its sidebands, the electric motor frequency due to electromagnetic forces arising in the air gap, and bearing frequencies due to geometrical defects on rollers and rails. Particularly, for each i -th stage, the GMF can be computed as

$$f_{gm,i} = Z_r \frac{n_{c,i}}{60} = \frac{Z_r Z_s}{Z_r + Z_s} \frac{n_{s,i}}{60} \quad (4.19)$$

where $n_{c,i}$ and $n_{s,i}$ are the rotational speeds of the carrier and sun, respectively, expressed in rpm. For the smaller RSA under test, $Z_r = -134$, $Z_s = 16$, and the index i refers to the HS stage, $i = \text{hs}$, or to the LS stage, $i = \text{ls}$. The nomenclature

ω_{em} [rpm]	$f_{gm,hs}$ [Hz]	$f_{in,hs}$ [Hz]	$f_{gm,ls}$ [Hz]	$f_{in,ls}$ [Hz]
500	119.1	8.3	12.7	0.9
1000	238.2	16.7	25.4	1.8
1500	357.3	25.0	38.1	2.7
2000	476.4	33.3	50.8	3.6
2500	595.6	41.7	63.5	4.4
3000	714.7	50.0	76.2	5.3
3500	833.8	58.3	88.9	6.2

Table 4.7 Theoretical computation on the RSA gearbox vibrational spectrum.

follows the conventions outlined in Section 3.3.3.

Then, GMF sidebands can be computed by adding integer multiples of the input and output shaft frequencies of the i -th stage.

$$f_{sb,i}^k = f_{gm,i} \pm k \underbrace{\frac{n_{in,i}}{60}}_{f_{in,i}} \quad (4.20)$$

$$f_{sb,i}^h = f_{gm,i} \pm h \underbrace{\frac{n_{out,i}}{60}}_{f_{out,i}} \quad (4.21)$$

with $k, h \in \mathbb{N}$ sideband order, while $n_{in,i}$ is the i -th stage input shaft speed in rpm, and $n_{out,i}$ is the i -th stage output shaft speed in rpm. For the HS stage, the input shaft coincides with the electric motor shaft and the output shaft with the carrier of the gearbox. For the LS stage, the input shaft coincides with the carrier of the HS stage, as the sun gear is directly machined on it, and the output shaft is the LS stage carrier. Frequencies can be generalized in terms of harmonic orders just dividing them by the rotation frequency of the i -th stage input shaft. Gear mesh orders quantify how often the teeth of the gears mesh relative to the input shaft rotation. For the smaller RSA, the HS stage presents a gear mesh order $o_{gm,hs} = 14.3$, while for the LS stage $o_{gm,ls} = 1.52$.

The theoretical computations on the tested motor speeds are listed in Table 4.7 and are useful to understand the following experimental results on the RSA prototype.

Fig. 4.23 RSA NVH tests: (a) acoustic emission map, (b) vibrational spectrum during 2000 rpm active test, (c) waterfall diagram of the active mode test.

Passing to the acoustic analysis, the main performance parameter is the sound pressure level (*SPL*) expressed in dB, defined as

$$SPL = 20 \log \left(\frac{p_{\text{meas}}}{p_{\text{ref}}} \right) \quad (4.22)$$

where p_{meas} is the recorded pressure by the microphone and $p_{\text{ref}} = 20 \mu\text{Pa}$ for sound pressure in air. Before determining the *SPL*, raw acoustic data can be filtered through the A-weighting continuous-time transfer function to better correlate with human ear frequency sensitivity, as described in the DIN EN 61672 standard [139].

Test results are summarized in Fig. 4.23. The acoustic map shown in Fig. 4.23a represents the *SPL* RMS values in dB(A) recorded by the side microphone. At peak mechanical power, *SPL* reaches 82 dB(A), significantly exceeding the 55 dB(A) limit set by the United States Environmental Protection Agency for 24-hour

exposure [140]. The overall noise emitted by the RSA follows a power-law trend, in agreement with previous findings in the literature [141]. Taking the test at 2000 rpm as a reference, Figure 4.23b shows the full spectrum captured by the accelerometer mounted on top of the gearbox. A prominent broadband region between 2 kHz and 12 kHz emerges, attributed to high-frequency tonal noise generated by both the RSA electric machine and the test bench driving motor [142]. As suggested by the frequency range, this tonal content is primarily associated with the switching frequencies of the power electronics controlling the motors.

Additional vibrational components originate from the mechanical domain and are more pronounced at lower frequencies. Figure 4.23c provides a waterfall plot of the vibration signals throughout the overall test campaign within the mechanical frequency range. The GMF of the HS stage and its first harmonic are clearly distinguishable by comparing the experimental results with the analytical ones in Table 4.7. The GMF amplitudes significantly increase with the RSA motor speed. A peak acceleration of 1.1 g is detected during the test at 3500 rpm. Several other spectral components also appear, as the RSA is neither acoustically nor mechanically isolated from the test bench.

In conclusion, since the vibrational data are significantly influenced by the test bench setup, further NVH investigations should be carried out on the isolated RSA in an anechoic chamber, preferably under controllable load conditions. Nevertheless, the presented results highlight inherent NVH criticalities of the RSA technology, which remain relevant given that, in vehicle application, the RSA is rigidly mounted to the vehicle frame. Considering the widespread adoption of BEVs, where high acoustic standards are reached for passengers, RSA installations may require the use of rubber bushings, as common for the other suspension components.

4.3 Controls and tuning

On the basis of the test results on the electromagnetic actuator, vehicle models and controls can be properly adjusted to include physical limitations of the active device.

To this end, a novel linear quarter-car model is proposed and validated through bump tests conducted on the D-SUV equipped with the RSA. Subsequently, a more advanced H_∞ controller, compared to the LQR presented in Section 3.2.1, is designed using the new model as the plant, aiming to reject both low-frequency load transfer

on the sprung mass and random road excitations within a unified control strategy and using only measured variables. The controller is then tested on a non-linear suspension model under different external perturbations. About H_∞ control for active suspension, a lot of studies are already reported in literature. For instance, Kruczek *et al.* [143] presented a quarter-car based H_∞ controller to control a linear electromagnetic shock absorber for passenger comfort and driving stability, adding also a controller deterioration to control energy consumption. Arana *et al.* [93] also developed a quarter-car based H_∞ controller for the series active variable geometry suspension presented in Section 2.2.2; the goal was to achieve comfort enhancement by controlling the position of the actuator rigid link based on the measurements of the sprung and unsprung masses accelerations, the suspension speed, and the link angular position. A similar control design on the series active suspension was proposed by Cheng *et al.* [144], adding also an inner position-control loop on the rigid link to respect operational limits and limit the electric power consumption. Then these works were extended on the full-car case study [145, 146]. Similar H_∞ controllers were designed for the parallel active variable geometry suspension and tested on a quarter-car test rig [95, 94]. Also for this case study, a inner position-control loop was added to compensate backlash [147] and a full-car based controller design was developed [96]. Further back in time, Palmeri *et al.* [148] experimentally validated the benefit of a H_∞ controller with respect to a more classical sky-hook damper on a Lancia Thema equipped with hydraulic actuators at its corners, highlighting the discretization procedure, the matrix optimization, and the scaling procedure needed to implement the controller on a vehicle control unit.

As the bump scenario results as a critical control problem both from simulations and feedback from industrial partners, also a specific control strategy is studied. More specifically, the active suspension is typically tuned with a comfort-oriented focus at the bump impact to reduce the sharp acceleration peaks experienced by the sprung mass. However, this soft tuning results in high relative suspension velocities, well above the base speed of the motor of the RSA presented in this dissertation. This makes it difficult to generate the high damping forces required to quickly control the unsprung mass dynamics after the bump, which is essential for maintaining good road holding. The proposed control strategy modulates between sky-hook and ground-hook controls over time on the basis of the bump profile estimation from the front axle of the vehicle. Then, the rear axle can be even predictively controlled.

Fig. 4.24 Novel linear quarter-car model including a mechanical equivalent model of an electromechanical shock absorber (blue window).

4.3.1 Novel quarter-car model

Traditional scientific literature on active suspension control largely relies on linear quarter-car models featuring an ideal force source in parallel with the spring-damper assembly [149]. However, fewer studies incorporate a mechanical model of the actuator within the vehicle dynamics framework. For instance, Galluzzi *et al.* [119] combined a linear quarter-car model with a realistic mathematical representation of the actuator, similar to the one presented in Section 3.1.1, but just to evaluate LQR control strategies.

An interesting approach is presented by Kawamoto *et al.* [150], where the ideal force source is placed between the unsprung mass and an additional mass representing the equivalent inertia of the electromagnetic damper. This mass is connected to the sprung mass via a spring-damper system, which models the equivalent stiffness of structural elements and connecting shafts, and to the unsprung mass through both the actuator and an additional damper, capturing the equivalent viscous friction of the electromagnetic unit. However, in the author's opinion, this model fails to accurately reflect the true inertial contribution of the damper, as it experiences relative motion at both ends. As a result, the actuator equivalent inertia is perceived by the two corner masses more akin to an inerter element [151].

The proposed novel model is displayed in Fig. 4.24. The variables in purple are the external disturbances: a force on the sprung mass due to the load transfers F_{lt} and the vertical displacement of the tire-ground contact point z_r . Instead, the variables in green represents the degrees of freedom, in particular z_{eq} is a massless degree of freedom. The controllable input F_a is highlighted with red arrows.

The model includes an equivalent model for an electromechanical shock absorber derived from the linear model presented in Section 3.1.1. Indeed, the lumped parameters k_m , c_m , and c_{eq} still represent the overall compliance between the actual force input and the suspension and the mechanical viscous frictions, respectively. The inertial properties are lumped in an inerter element acting in parallel to the frictions and the ideal force source. It produces a force opposite to the relative acceleration $F_{in} = -m_{eq}(\ddot{z}_{eq} - \ddot{z}_u)$. As these lumped parameters depend on the linkage kinematic ratio τ_ℓ , see Eqs. (3.2) and (3.3), hence on the suspension stroke, the model is linearized in the static equilibrium point $\tau_\ell(x=0) = \tau_{\ell,nom}$. Gravity force is neglected because it is balanced by the primary suspension spring preload. The equations of motion are derived by applying Eq. (3.4) to the following terms

$$\mathcal{T} = \frac{1}{2}m_s\dot{z}_s^2 + \frac{1}{2}m_{eq}(\dot{z}_{eq} - \dot{z}_u)^2 + \frac{1}{2}m_u\dot{z}_u^2 \quad (4.23)$$

$$\mathcal{U} = \frac{1}{2}k_s(z_s - z_u)^2 + \frac{1}{2}k_m(z_{eq} - z_u)^2 + \frac{1}{2}k_u(z_u - z_r)^2 \quad (4.24)$$

$$\mathcal{F} = \frac{1}{2}c_m(\dot{z}_s - \dot{z}_{eq})^2 + \frac{1}{2}c_{eq}(\dot{z}_{eq} - \dot{z}_u)^2 + \frac{1}{2}c_u(\dot{z}_u - \dot{z}_r)^2 \quad (4.25)$$

$$\delta W = F_a\delta(z_{eq} - z_u) + F_{lt}\delta z_s \quad (4.26)$$

Considering $Z = [z_s \ z_{eq} \ z_u]^T$, the equation of motions can be expressed in matrix form

$$[M]\ddot{Z} + [C]\dot{Z} + [K]Z = F \quad (4.27)$$

where

$$[M] = \begin{bmatrix} m_s & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & m_{eq} & -m_{eq} \\ 0 & -m_{eq} & m_{eq} + m_u \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.28)$$

$$[C] = \begin{bmatrix} c_m & -c_m & 0 \\ -c_m & c_m + c_{eq} & -c_{eq} \\ 0 & c_{eq} & c_{eq} + c_u \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.29)$$

$$[K] = \begin{bmatrix} k_s + k_m & -k_m & -k_s \\ -k_m & k_m & 0 \\ -k_s & 0 & k_s + k_u \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.30)$$

$$F = \begin{bmatrix} F_{lt} \\ F_a \\ k_u z_r + c_u \dot{z}_r - F_a \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.31)$$

Notably, the inertia matrix $[M]$ in Eq. (4.28) is characterized by two terms out of the diagonal due to inerter action and an additional mass term for the unsprung mass degree of freedom.

Validation

The validation and identification of the novel quarter-car model is carried out on the analysis of a real-world bump-crossing test with the D-SUV equipped with four RSAs on its corners, showcased in Section 4.1.1, by the industrial partner. The bump profile is characterized by a maximum height of 50 mm and a total width of 400 mm. Specifically, the test aims to measure the fail-safe behaviour of the vehicle in case of any electrical failure of the RSAs. In other terms, the RSAs are in OC configuration and the damping action in the corner is guaranteed only by the overall internal frictions of the suspension.

The vehicle measurements of interest are reported in Fig. 4.25. The bump is hit at 0.1 s by the front axle at a measured vehicle longitudinal speed of 21 km/h. Suddenly, the front suspension stroke undergoes to a strong compression peak of about -60 mm (Fig. 4.25b), hence a very high acceleration peak of about 11 m/s^2 exhibits on the front sprung mass (Fig. 4.25c). Actually, the compression end-stop is likely reached in this event, explaining the high front sprung mass acceleration peak. Instead, rear sprung mass exhibits a negative peak acceleration due to pitch

Fig. 4.25 Bump-crossing test of the D-SUV with OC RSA: (a) vehicle speed, (b) suspension strokes, (c) sprung mass accelerations, (d) unsprung mass accelerations.

Fig. 4.26 Updated parameters of the D-SUV case study from real implementation: (a) linkage kinematic ratio from multi-body analysis, (b) experimental primary spring characteristic.

motion. The front unsprung mass experiences larger accelerations soon after the bump crossing (Fig. 4.25d). Indeed, the compression end-stop contrasts the vertical wheel motion, but the first rebound phase, reaching -110 m/s^2 , proves the wheel detachment from the ground. As a consequence, the second positive peak stands out as the highest acceleration, about 130 m/s^2 , due to the tire impact in the following bounce. The rear corner hits the speed bump after about 0.5 s due to the delay linked to the wheelbase and the vehicle speed. A more limited rear stroke is measured, demonstrating a stiffer architecture. Overall, the trends are similar to the front bump hit. Figure 4.25a highlights the strong influence of the speed bump scenario over traction. As soon as the obstacle is crossed, the driver starts releasing the throttle pedal and the vehicle longitudinal speed starts a constant decrease. This driver's behaviour could stem from his discomfort with losing contact with the ground. This manoeuvre impacts more the rear wheel traction since higher speed oscillations appear at 0.6 s. A deviation of +4 km/h results as the rear corner overcome the speed bump. So, a good control of the speed bump scenario is mandatory to guarantee safe road conditions. Eventually, unsprung-mass oscillations stabilize faster than the one of the sprung mass due to the viscous action of the tire. Sprung mass is also affected by the undamped pitch motion due to the OC configurations of the dampers.

The novel quarter-car model parameters identification and validation takes the rear corner as reference. Quarter-car parameters are already listed in Table 3.3. The contribution of the RSA mass $m_{\text{rsa}} = 6.2 \text{ kg}$ is added to the sprung mass value $m_s = 573.7 \text{ kg}$. During an elasto-kinematic testing campaign, the industrial partner also characterized the real elastic feature of the suspension (Fig. 4.26b) and the

Fig. 4.27 Results of the model identification procedure: computed suspension velocity \dot{x} from the novel quarter-car model with identified parameters (blue) and estimated suspension velocity \dot{x}_{meas} during the bump test by the Kalman filter running in the vehicle control unit (orange).

realistic spring stiffness is $k_s = 39 \text{ kN/m}$. As the corner shows a very high stiffness, the actual 3D kinematic ratio of the linkage mechanism is computed by a rigid multi-body model of the whole suspension. This is carried out using the MATLAB Simscape add-on available for the CAD software SolidWorks, as it directly generates the multi-body model from a properly built assembly drawing of the rear D-SUV suspension with the RSA. Each suspension link has two spherical joints for the connection to the chassis and to the knuckle. Also the RSA pushrod present two spherical joints at its ends for the connection to the LCA and to the crank lever. The latter can just rotate about the RSA axis by means of a cylindrical joint. The 3D kinematic ratio is plotted in Fig. 4.26a; it shows the same trend as the 2D one (Fig. 3.9a) but slightly lower values, i.e., $\tau_{\ell, \text{nom}}^{3\text{D}} = 174 \text{ mm/rad}$. As a consequence, the crank lever spans a higher angular interval $\pm 27^\circ$ and a more realistic value of the equivalent inertia can be computed with Eq. (3.2); the result is $m_{\text{eq}} = 7.49 \text{ kg}$, that is 1 kg larger than the first estimation. The values of the compliant mount stiffness k_m and damping c_m are set equal to those determined in Section 4.2.1. This is justified by the fact that, on one hand, the vehicle installation, featuring welded steel flanges, is expected to be very stiff, and on the other hand, k_m represents an equivalent stiffness composed of multiple elements in series, hence the lowest one dominates. In this case, it is anticipated to be the bending stiffness of the gearbox HS stage. In the end, considering that in OC configuration $F_a = 0$, the main parameter for the identification procedure is the equivalent damping c_{eq} .

The identification procedure aims to minimize the following least-squares function to maintain consistency with the modelling approach of the actuator presented

Table 4.8 Parameters for the novel quarter-car model of the rear D-SUV suspension equipped with the RSA.

Parameter	Value	Unit
m_s	579.9	kg
k_s	39	kN/m
m_u	55	kg
k_u	255	kN/m
c_u	0	Ns/m
m_{eq}	7.49	kg
k_m	$1.22 \cdot 10^6$	N/m
c_m	50	Ns/m
c_{eq}	303.6	Ns/m

in Section 3.1.1, where the suspension speed is one of the inputs, along with the actuation force, that in this case is null as reported in the lines above

$$f_{id} = (\dot{x} - \dot{x}_{meas})^2 \quad (4.32)$$

where $\dot{x} = \dot{z}_s - \dot{z}_u$ is the suspension velocity computed with the model and \dot{x}_{meas} is the estimated suspension velocity during the bump test by a Kalman filter in the vehicle control unit. The inputs to the model are the measured suspension quantities shown in Fig. 4.25, i.e. the two accelerations of the masses and the suspension stroke. In particular, they are used to solve the equation of motion related to the degree of freedom z_{eq} in Eq. (4.27), in order to compute the suspension speed \dot{x} for the identification problem based on Eq. (4.32).

The minimum of Eq. (4.32) is reached with $c_{eq} = 303.6$ Ns/m. It also includes small contributions from suspension arms bushings. Figure 4.27 shows the resulting \dot{x} from simulation and the estimated during the real test $\dot{x}_{s,meas}$. They almost totally overlap validating both the model accuracy to catch the real suspension behaviour and the estimated parameters of the RSA equivalent model. The lumped parameters of the identified model are listed in Table 4.8 and they will be used for the following control design.

Fig. 4.28 Block scheme for the synthesis of the H_∞ controller for the quarter-car system equipped with a RSA.

4.3.2 H_∞ control

For control purposes, the model in Section 4.3.1 is arranged in state space representation with the following states $[z_s, z_{eq}, z_u, \dot{z}_s, \dot{z}_{eq}, \dot{z}_u]^T$.

As it results fully observable, the outputs of this multi-input multi-output (MIMO) system are then established specifically for the control design.

The proposed controller is designed to effectively handle both road disturbance rejection and low-frequency load transfer on the sprung mass. It is based on the formulation of a standard H_∞ synthesis problem, incorporating tunable weighting functions on both disturbances and outputs to appropriately shape the controller frequency response. This controller is quite widespread for the robust control of MIMO systems, particularly for the suspension control case study, as reported in 4.3. Robustness against parameter uncertainty and strong disturbances, as well as the multi-objective nature are the main advantages of this control approach. Taking the suspension control as reference problem, the sprung mass parameter is an extremely variable parameter because it depends on the number of passengers and on the luggage weight. Even the suspension stiffness varies during the suspension travel due to hysteresis and end-stops. However, H_∞ controllers presents difficult tunability and they are often high-order controllers that need to be properly managed for real-time deployment in automotive embedded electronics.

As well-known from the literature, the goal of H_∞ controller is to find a frequency-dependent closed-loop controller $K(s)$ that minimizes the H_∞ norm of the transfer function linking the plant disturbances and its output [152].

The proposed control synthesis scheme is depicted in Fig. 4.28. An augmented plant $P(s)$ incorporates tunable weighting functions to shape both disturbances influence and performance objectives in the frequency domain. Hence, the control problem can be formulated as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{e} &= T_{zw}(P, K) \mathbf{w} \\ \exists K(s) \text{ such that } \|T_{zw}(s)\|_{\infty} &< \gamma_H \end{aligned} \quad (4.33)$$

where $\mathbf{e} = [e_1, e_2, e_3]^T$ is the performance objectives vector, $\mathbf{w} = [w_1, w_2]^T$ are the disturbances, and $\gamma_H > 0$. The optimal controller $K(s)$ is the one among all the admissible solutions that minimizes γ_H .

This control synthesis problem aims to reduce sprung mass acceleration without deteriorating the road holding capability of the corner and with an affordable actuator effort. Furthermore, it feedbacks only the measured signals, i.e., the stroke x and the two accelerations \ddot{z}_s and \ddot{z}_u , to avoid any additional estimation algorithms that increase complexity and errors. Thus, the objective weighting functions are defined as

$$W_{o1}(s) = \frac{1}{a_{\max}} \frac{\frac{s}{2\pi}}{\left(\frac{s}{2\pi 10} + 1\right) \left(\frac{s}{2\pi} + 1\right)} \quad (4.34)$$

$$W_{o2}(s) = \frac{1}{x_{t,\max}} \frac{1}{\left(\frac{s}{2\pi 20} + 1\right)} \quad (4.35)$$

$$W_{\text{eff}}(s) = \frac{1}{F_{\max}} \frac{\left[\left(\frac{s}{2\pi 2}\right)^2 + \frac{s}{2\pi 2} + 1\right]}{\left[\left(\frac{s}{2\pi 30}\right)^2 + \frac{s}{2\pi 30} + 1\right]} \quad (4.36)$$

The weighting function $W_{o1}(s)$ prioritizes sprung mass acceleration \ddot{z}_s minimization in the frequency interval 1-10 Hz to reduce the sprung mass resonance and address the human-sensitive frequency range 4-8 Hz indicated by ISO 2631 [45]. The second function $W_{o2}(s)$ addresses the tire deflection $x_t = z_u - z_r$ until 20 Hz to cover the unsprung mass resonance and the third one W_{o3} penalizes actuation above 30 Hz to avoid RSA inerter-effect dominance. The value F_{\max} is set to 3000 N, as it is the maximum force deliverable by the RSA, and a_{\max} and $x_{t,\max}$ are tunable parameters to favour comfort or road holding, respectively. For the presented case study, $a_{\max} = 0.32 \text{ m/s}^2$ and $x_{t,\max} = 0.006 \text{ m}$ to remain within the most comfortable range defined by the ISO 2631 standard and to achieve a road holding index η_{rh} (see Eq. (3.28)) of approximately 0.25.

Fig. 4.29 H_∞ control magnitude transfer functions: output force over stroke input (blue), sprung mass acceleration input (orange), and unsprung mass acceleration input (yellow).

In the end, the disturbances weighting functions mimic their dynamics. For the first disturbance, the road disturbance is handled, so $W_{d1}(s) = G_{road}(s)$ as defined by Eq. (3.19) with the same road condition defined in Section 3.2.1. This choice is made because uneven roads represent the most common driving condition. However, speed bumps are excluded from this formulation, leaving a clear tuning gap that still needs to be addressed. The second disturbance accounts for load transfer due to sprung mass rigid body motion, so its weighting function W_{d2} is a first-order low-pass filter with a cut-off frequency at 2 Hz as the roll motion resonance.

$$W_{d2} = \frac{500}{\frac{s}{2\pi} + 1} \quad (4.37)$$

the gain of 500 is hand-tuned to avoid $\gamma_H > 40$, i.e., poor disturbance rejection.

The H_∞ control synthesis yields a controller $K(s)$ of order 13 with a dynamic response shown in Fig. 4.29. The controller operates effectively within the relevant suspension frequency range, with its force output attenuating beyond 10 Hz. The actuator resonant frequency introduces a mild anti-resonance in the transfer functions associated with stroke and sprung mass acceleration feedback, whereas the transfer function related to unsprung mass acceleration exhibits a small resonant peak. Additionally, a slight hump between 1 and 4 Hz in the response due to sprung mass acceleration feedback indicates force amplification in the frequency band targeted for comfort. Since all three transfer functions exhibit low-pass characteristics, model order reduction may be performed to facilitate implementation in the vehicle control unit.

Fig. 4.30 Open-loop (solid curves) quarter-car model and H_∞ controlled (blue dashed) quarter-car model transfer functions: (a) sprung mass acceleration over road displacement and over actuation in (orange), (b) tire deflection over road displacement and over actuation (orange), (c) sprung mass acceleration over load transfer and over actuation (orange), tire deflection over load transfer and over actuation (orange).

Ultimately, the vehicle dynamics evaluation is based on the closed-loop transfer functions of the controlled quarter-car model compared to the open-loop response of the uncontrolled system in Fig. 4.30. Specifically, Figure 4.30a presents the transfer function from road disturbance to sprung mass acceleration. The controller significantly reduces the resonant amplification up to approximately 6 Hz. Beyond this point, the magnitude increases toward the unsprung mass resonance, where the controlled system behaves similarly to the open-loop system, with only a slight attenuation observed around 11 Hz. Although the natural frequency of the unsprung mass is entirely included in the weighting function Eq. (4.35) as control target, Karnopp [153] showed that the body acceleration amplitude at the so-called *wheel-hop frequency* remains constant, regardless of the suspension force law. This invariant point is also reflected in the transfer function shown in orange, which relates body acceleration to actuation force; a discontinuity in magnitude appears at the wheel-hop frequency.

From a comfort perspective, effective attenuation is also achieved for load transfer disturbances, which predominantly affect low-frequency body motion below 4 Hz (Fig. 4.30c).

As for road holding, the transfer function between road disturbance and tire deflection (Fig. 4.30b) shows strong attenuation around the sprung mass natural frequency. However, minimal influence is observed at higher frequencies, indicating that comfort was prioritized in the controller design.

Attenuation at the sprung mass frequency is also visible in the load transfer-induced tire deflection response (Fig. 4.30d), although the controlled system exhibits increased amplification beyond 2 Hz compared to the open-loop plant. Nevertheless, such high-frequency excitations are unlikely to significantly affect the system, as they do not correspond to modes excited by sprung mass rigid-body motion.

Validation

As a way to validate the proposed control strategy, the quarter-car model introduced in Section 4.3 is extended to represent a non-linear plant. As illustrated in Fig. 4.31, the elastic force F_{el} generated by the primary spring depends on the suspension stroke x , following the relationship shown in Fig. 4.26b. Additionally, all parameters defining the RSA vary with the suspension stroke due to changes in the linkage kinematic ratio τ_ℓ , as depicted in Fig. 4.26a. To account for the possibility of

Fig. 4.31 Non-linear quarter-car model for the validation of the H_∞ controller.

Fig. 4.32 Speed bump disturbance: geometrical shape (blue) and filtered by means of the contact patch (orange).

tire detachment from the ground, an upper bound is imposed on the vertical tire force, defined as $F_{sat} = g(m_s + m_u)$. Lastly, a mapped motor block is integrated to reflect real actuator force and power limitations, thereby enabling preliminary energy assessments

The simulation scenarios are the same described in Section 3.2.1, i.e., an ISO-C road travelled at 35 km/h and a speed bump 3 cm high and 60 cm wide hit at 50 km/h. However, to introduce a higher degree of realism, a contact patch-based filter smooths the geometrical bump shape. Mathematically, it is a moving average based on the contact patch length l_{cp} , as the commercial vehicle dynamics software CarSim does

Table 4.9 Simulation results for the ISO-C at 35 km/h road scenario for control strategies comparison.

KPI	Passively	Sky-hook	H_∞
RMS \ddot{z}_w [m/s ²]	0.641	0.459	0.298
RMS η_{rh} [-]	0.113	0.129	0.197
Avg. P_e [W]	-44.4	-34.8	-8.49
Avg. P_m [W]	-57.4	-55.3	-55.1

[154]. Indeed, tire-ground real contact is not a point contact, as usually represented in quarter-car models [155]. The contact patch length l_{cp} can be calculated using the formula by Balakina *et al.* [156]

$$l_{cp} = 2k_h \sqrt{\Delta z (2R_0 - \Delta z)} \quad (4.38)$$

where R_0 is the undeformed wheel radius, Δz is the static tire deflection due to weight, and k_h is an experimental correction factor. The D-SUV mounts 235/55 R19 tires, as a consequence $R_0 = 370.55$ mm. The static tire deflection is $\Delta z = \frac{g(m_s + m_{sh})}{k_u} = 24.4$ mm and $k_h = 0.7$, as reported in [156]. In the end, $l_{cp} = 185$ mm. Figure 4.32 compares the geometrical bump with the filtered one. The contact patch slightly enlarges the bump geometry and flats its peak.

To properly assess the H_∞ control, two benchmark strategies are also simulated; a passively-controlled and a sky-hook strategy [157], the most widespread comfort-oriented strategy, formulated as follows, respectively

$$F_{a,des} = -c_p(\dot{z}_{eq} - \dot{z}_u) \quad (4.39)$$

$$F_{a,des} = -c(\dot{z}_{eq} - \dot{z}_u) - c_s \dot{z}_s \quad (4.40)$$

The use of the relative velocity ($\dot{z}_{eq} - \dot{z}_u$) instead of the usual suspension speed \dot{x} derives from preliminary closed-loop stability studies due to non-collocated control, already mentioned in Section 4.2.3.. The damping coefficients are set according to [158], i.e., $c_p = 2$ kNs/m, $c = 1$ kNs/m, and $c_s = 10$ kNs/m. Table 4.9 summarizes the simulation results based on the acceleration and road-holding KPIs introduced in Section 3.2.1. Average electrical and mechanical power values are also reported;

the former is extracted from the motor block, while the latter is computed as the product of the force at the two ends of the RSA assembly and the suspension velocity \dot{x} . The H_∞ controller clearly outperforms the benchmarks in terms of comfort, as its RMS weighted acceleration \ddot{z}_w is the only one below the ISO 2631 comfort limit of 0.315 m/s^2 [45]. Specifically, the H_∞ controller achieves a 35% reduction in acceleration compared to the sky-hook controller. Conversely, the road-holding index η_{rh} deteriorates, reaching an RMS value of 0.192; however, this remains acceptable, being comparable to the passive vehicle with minimum damping (0.17) and significantly better than the comfort-oriented LQR case (0.32) reported in Table 3.4. The LQR is not compared to the controllers in Table 4.9 because it is based on the simple two-degrees of freedom quarter car. The average electrical power of -8.49 W indicates that the electromagnetic shock absorber can achieve optimal comfort levels with very limited power consumption, or even small amounts of regeneration. It should be noted that only inverter and battery efficiencies, typically quite high, and non-linear mechanical losses are not included in the model. However, energy considerations must encompass the whole vehicle, even in terms of longitudinal dynamics. Meanwhile, the average mechanical power in Table 4.9 highlights the tendency of the system to act similarly to a mechanical damper, being comparable to the passively-controlled RSA configuration.

Fig. 4.33 Rough road scenario simulation results: (a) motor torque-speed envelopes within motor limits, (b) electrical power time history at the DC bus.

Similar observations can be drawn from Fig. 4.33. Specifically, the motor torque-speed envelope appears slightly tilted toward the passive quadrants and spans a wide area within the motor continuous duty envelope (Fig. 4.33a). The motor operates at higher speeds compared to the benchmarks, as comfort-oriented control strategies resemble a softer damper tuning. Figure 4.33b illustrates the previously mentioned power considerations, showing that the electrical power time history of the H_∞ controller is nearly symmetrical about the zero-power line. Lastly, although the sky-hook controller theoretically models ideal viscous damping behaviour, it also exhibits active working points.

Table 4.10 Simulation results for the speed bump scenario for control strategies comparison.

KPI	Passively	Sky-hook	H_∞
Peak-to-peak acceleration \ddot{z}_{pp} [m/s ²]	8.05	5.63	3.15
Acceleration settling time t_{acc} [s]	0.2	0.29	0.46
no. of tire detachments [-]	0	1	1
Road holding settling time t_{rh} [s]	0.17	0.26	0.69

Fig. 4.34 Bump scenario simulation results: (a) weighted sprung mass acceleration \ddot{z}_w time history, (b) road holding index η_{rh} time history.

For the bump scenarios, additional KPIs are introduced alongside the number of tire detachments from the ground, already discussed in Section 3.2.1. First, the peak-to-peak acceleration \ddot{z}_{pp} is defined as the difference between the first two peaks of the weighted sprung mass acceleration \ddot{z}_w , capturing the sharp impacts experienced by passengers when crossing a bump, often due to end-stops. Next, the acceleration settling time is defined as the time interval during which the weighted acceleration returns within the comfort bounds of ± 0.315 m/s². Finally, a road-holding settling time t_{rh} is introduced, representing the time required for the road-holding index η_{rh} to stabilize within ± 0.1 .

Table 4.10 summarizes the KPIs for the three controllers. The bump scenario further confirms the effectiveness of the H_∞ controller in significantly improving cabin comfort, as its peak-to-peak acceleration \ddot{z}_{pp} is 44% lower than that achieved by the sky-hook controller. Conversely, the acceleration settling time t_{acc} increases by 59%.

However, Figure 4.34a puts this into perspective, showing that only low-amplitude vibrations are present, due to the controller inherent limitations in managing unsprung mass dynamics. The main challenge remains the road-holding capability; the settling time t_{rh} is significantly higher than that of the benchmarks, more than twice that of the sky-hook controller, and the vibration amplitudes of the road-holding index are also relatively large (Fig. 4.34b). This behaviour is expected, as the closed-loop transfer function in Fig. 4.30b closely follows the open-loop response for frequencies above 8 Hz. Nevertheless, the tire detaches from the ground only once.

In conclusion, control design for electromagnetic shock absorbers remains highly challenging due to the conflicting nature of comfort and handling requirements, as well as the physical limitations stemming from the use of a single actuator to govern two interconnected masses with distinct dynamics. These limitations were already highlighted by Karnopp [153]; in particular, the sprung mass acceleration gain at the unsprung natural frequency represents an invariant point of the quarter-car model, and the two main transfer functions, sprung mass acceleration and tire deflection due to road disturbances, are mathematically coupled, making it impossible to optimize them independently. It should also be noted that electromagnetic actuators are constrained by force and power limitations, with packaging constraints playing a crucial role. Simulation results show that bump scenarios are the most critical, as they excite all the system natural frequencies similarly to an impact test. Therefore, to fully realize the benefits of active shock absorbers, more advanced control strategies must be explored, particularly those blending comfort and handling objectives based on road preview information, as well as a more precise tuning of the H_∞ , as also anticipated in Section 4.3.2 for the road disturbance weighting function.

4.3.3 Predictive bump control

A simple but effective control strategy specifically targeting the bump crossing scenario has been recently published by the research group [158]. It combines the propensity of comfort-oriented strategies in reducing sprung mass acceleration peaks at the impact and handling-oriented ones in managing wheel-hop vibrations when the vehicle passed the bump. The main goal is to guarantee the best vehicle handling for safety, as speed bumps are usually used as traffic calming devices before zebra crossing.

Fig. 4.35 Predictive control strategy as a function of the bump profile estimation in time domain.

By default, the vehicle operates using the sky-hook strategy to ensure comfort on rough roads. Upon detecting a bump crossing at the front axle, the control module switches to a ground-hook strategy on the front axle, maintaining it until the entire bump maneuver is completed on both axles. The transition between damping strategies is managed with a slew rate of 40 kN/m, resulting in transition times of 50 ms for damping coefficients associated with the unsprung masses, and 500 ms for those related to the sprung mass. This gradual gain scheduling approach helps mitigate undesirable transients that would otherwise arise from abrupt parameter changes.

The bump estimation module is also capable of approximating the time at which the bump reaches its peak height and when it ends. This allows the rear axle controller to schedule the transition from sky-hook to ground-hook control in advance. The optimal switching point occurs when the wheel reaches the bump maximum height, as this enables the controller to counteract the wheel tendency to lift off. As in the front axle case, the control reverts to sky-hook compensation during normal driving conditions—specifically, when the acceleration remains within $\pm 0.2 \text{ m/s}^2$ and the suspension has undergone two rebound cycles. Figure 4.35 illustrates the proposed predictive control strategy as a function of the bump timing.

In this study, bump detection is handled by an augmented Kalman filter based on a linear half-car model with simplified suspension actuators. To ensure affordability, the method relies solely on inertial and stroke sensors, which are commonly available on passenger vehicles and eliminate the need for additional estimation techniques. This Kalman filter is not described in the thesis since the author did not contribute

to its conceptualization and design. Road preview information can also be obtained from alternative estimators [159] or external sensors, such as cameras [160].

Eventually, vertical dynamics control force F_{di} is adapted to the considered model with ideal actuators and it adds to a pitch control strategy F_{pi} . They are computed for the i -th axle.

$$F_{i,des} = F_{di} + F_{pi} \quad (4.41)$$

The sky-hook control strategy mocks a passive damper c_{si} connected between the sprung mass and the reference [157],

$$F_{di} = -c_i(\dot{z}_{si} - \dot{z}_{ui}) - c_{si}\dot{z}_{si} \quad (4.42)$$

while the ground-hook emulates a passive damper c_{gi} connected between the unsprung mass and the reference [161],

$$F_{di} = -c_i(\dot{z}_{si} - \dot{z}_{ui}) + c_{gi}\dot{z}_{ui} \quad (4.43)$$

Instead, the pitch control module simulates a viscous rotational damping c_θ counteracting excessive pitch motion. The resulting torque is then allocated on the two axles based on their semi-wheelbase $a_r = 1.269$ m and $a_f = 1.549$ m,

$$F_{pr} = \frac{a_f c_\theta}{a_r \ell} \dot{\theta} \quad (4.44)$$

$$F_{pf} = -\frac{a_r c_\theta}{a_f \ell} \dot{\theta} \quad (4.45)$$

where $\dot{\theta}$ is the pitch rate, the subscripts "r" and "f" indicate the rear and front axles, respectively, and $\ell = a_f + a_r$ is the vehicle wheelbase.

4.3.4 Validation

The validation model of the bump-overcoming predictive strategy is illustrated in Figure 4.36.

The vehicle model is a half-car model that considers the pitch and vertical degrees of freedom of the sprung mass, and the two unsprung masses vertical degrees of freedom. The model accounts for the full vehicle mass and the two front and rear axles, lumping the two wheels [162, 163]. This vehicle model is shown in Figure

Fig. 4.36 Vehicle simulation setup for the bump predictive control validation. The subindex $i = f, r$ indicates the vehicle axle, front or rear.

Fig. 4.37 Half-car model including the vertical degrees of freedom of the sprung mass and the two unsprung masses of the axles, and the pitch motion of the sprung mass.

Table 4.11 D-class SUV half-car model parameters.

Description	Symbol	Value	Unit
Total sprung mass	$m_{s,tot}$	2087	kg
Unsprung mass	m_f, m_r	110	kg
Front semi-wheelbase	a_f	1.549	m
Rear semi-wheelbase	a_r	1.269	m
Total wheelbase	ℓ	2.818	m
Front spring stiffness	k_f	51	kN/m
Rear spring stiffness	k_r	66.8	kN/m
Tire stiffness	k_{tf}, k_{tr}	510	kN/m
Pitch inertia	I_z	4101.9	kgm ²

4.37 with blue arrows highlighting the degrees of freedom and cyan arrows the road disturbances. Active shock absorbers replace of the usual viscous dampers and their active force convention is highlighted by red arrows. The model is linear and described by the following system of equations:

$$m_f \ddot{z}_f = -F_{af} - k_{tf}(z_f - y_f) + k_f(z - z_f - a_f \theta) \quad (4.46)$$

$$m_r \ddot{z}_r = -F_{ar} - k_{tr}(z_r - y_r) + k_r(z - z_r + a_r \theta) \quad (4.47)$$

$$m_{s,tot} \ddot{z} = F_{af} + F_{ar} - k_f(z - z_f - a_f \theta) - k_r(z - z_r + a_r \theta) \quad (4.48)$$

Eqs. (4.46) and (4.47) express the vertical dynamics of the axles, indicated by the subscripts "f" and "r" for front and rear, respectively. Eq. (4.48) describes the vertical behaviour of the sprung mass. The parameters m_f and m_r denote the axles unsprung masses, $m_{s,tot}$ the whole sprung mass, z the vertical displacement of the sprung mass in its, z_f and z_r the vertical displacements of the axles, k_f and k_r the stiffness of the suspension springs, k_{tf} and k_{tr} the stiffness of the tires, a_f and a_r the two semi-wheelbases, and finally θ the pitch angle. This linear model holds validity only for small pitch angles θ to linearize the actual trigonometric functions involving θ . For the pitch degree of freedom θ , still considering small angles, the governing

linear equation is the following moment equilibrium around the vehicle body CoG

$$I_z \ddot{\theta} = -a_f F_{af} + a_r F_{ar} + a_f k_f (z - z_f - a_f \theta) - a_r k_r (z - z_r + a_r \theta) \quad (4.49)$$

where I_z is the vehicle body pitch moment of inertia. Vehicle parameters are referred to the D-SUV installing the RSAs already discussed in the previous section of the thesi and are reported in Table 4.11.

The bump profile is filtered by the effect of the tire contact patch, as illustrated in Section 4.3.2. In this case study, $l_{cp} = 80$ mm. With the aid of the road profile estimator, the timing of the obstacle is accurately determined. This information is then used to schedule the vertical dynamics control appropriately. Additionally, a basic pitch control contribution is superimposed on the active shock absorber force. The suspension actuator is modelled with a dynamic saturation constraint to limit its power output, and a low-pass filter is applied to restrict its bandwidth. Those limitations are based on the RSA technology.

To benchmark performance, the proposed predictive control strategy (Pre) is compared against several alternatives: a fully passive system without power limitations (Full pass.), a passively-controlled active damper (P. contr.) defined as $F_{di} = -c_i(\dot{z}_{si} - \dot{z}_{ui})$, both with and without pitch control, as well as sky-hook (SH) and ground-hook (GH) strategies combined with the pitch control module. The comparison is carried out in terms of weighted sprung mass acceleration, pitch angle, and tire forces.

Figure 4.38 presents the weighted accelerations of the sprung mass, calculated at the vehicle CoG. Focusing on Fig. 4.38a, the initial oscillations clearly correspond to the front axle encountering the bump, while the rear axle begins to oscillate at approximately 0.68 s. In the case of the fully passive benchmark, the lowest acceleration is observed, around -4 m/s^2 , during the rebound phase due to tire detachment, which causes high suspension velocities and, consequently, large damping forces. The passively-controlled strategies, both with and without pitch compensation, exhibit similar trends in sprung mass dynamics and more limited peak accelerations due to actuator power saturation. However, this leads to higher oscillations in the extension phases that follow. Notably, pitch control also helps suppress low-frequency oscillations that begin at around 1 s.

Figure 4.38b shows the results for the actively-controlled suspension strategies. The sky-hook controller does not effectively damp the unsprung mass dynamics, resulting

Fig. 4.38 Comparison among the weighted sprung mass vertical accelerations in the CoG: (a) fully passive (black line, abbreviation: Full pass.), passively-controlled (orange line, abbreviation: P. contr.), passively-controlled and active pitch damping control (dashed yellow line, abbreviation: P. contr. w/pitch), (b) sky-hook (violet line, abbreviation: SH), ground-hook (cyan line, abbreviation: GH), predictive (dashed green line, abbreviation: Pre).

in residual oscillations after the bump. However, it provides the best peak attenuation, reaching a maximum deceleration of approximately -2 m/s^2 during the rebound phase. In contrast, the ground-hook strategy exhibits the highest acceleration peak, about $+3.5 \text{ m/s}^2$, when the rear axle encounters the bump due to its focus on minimizing unsprung mass acceleration through a stiffer suspension tuning. While it successfully damps the unsprung oscillations after two full cycles, low-frequency waves persist as the ground-hook term excites the vehicle pitch motion. This issue arises from an unintended active force applied to the chassis by the ground-hook component in Eq. (4.43). The predictive control strategy achieves a compromise between the two approaches. It generates lower acceleration peaks than the ground-hook and effectively suppresses unsprung vibrations shortly after the bump. The first acceleration peak matches that of the sky-hook. However, the transition to ground-hook control on the front suspension amplifies the second compression peak to approximately $+2.5 \text{ m/s}^2$, slightly exceeding that of the pure ground-hook strategy. On the rear axle, the predictive controller nearly replicates the sky-hook response during bump impact and the ground-hook behavior during rebound. Power saturation impacts all controllers during the initial extension peak due to unavoidable tire detachment, but only the ground-hook strategy is further limited during the first compression phase.

Figure 4.39 shows the time histories of the pitch angle. A negative pitch (nose-up) occurs as the front axle begins to climb the bump, while a positive pitch (nose-down)

Fig. 4.39 Comparison among the pitch angles: (a) fully passive (black line, abbreviation: Full pass.), passively-controlled (orange line, abbreviation: P. contr.), passively-controlled and active pitch damping control (dashed yellow line, abbreviation: P. contr. w/pitch), (b) sky-hook (violet line, abbreviation: SH), ground-hook (cyan line, abbreviation: GH), predictive (dashed green line, abbreviation: Pre).

follows when the rear axle encounters the obstacle. In Figure 4.39a, both the full passive and the passively-controlled configurations fail to stabilize the pitch motion within 1.8 s after the manoeuvre starts. Notably, the passively-controlled reaches the highest pitch angle, peaking at $+0.8^\circ$, as a result of power saturation limits. The addition of pitch compensation significantly reduces the overall pitch response, cutting the RMS pitch angle by 45.68% compared to the full passive system and maintaining the pitch within $\pm 0.2^\circ$.

As depicted in Figure 4.39b, the sky-hook control improves pitch behavior by acting independently on the two axles, because it introduces additional damping into the pitch dynamics. Consequently, the pitch angle remains confined to the range $[-0.13^\circ, +0.09^\circ]$. In contrast, the ground-hook strategy compromises pitch performance due to its unintended actuation on the chassis, which excites pitch motion. In the proposed predictive control approach, when the front wheel encounters the bump at 0.2 s, the rear axle, still under sky-hook control, effectively counters the pitch motion. However, when the rear axle also reaches the bump, the simultaneous activation of ground-hook slightly degrades pitch suppression. Nonetheless, the predictive strategy keeps the pitch angle within the interval $[-0.14^\circ, +0.12^\circ]$, demonstrating a balanced and effective performance. However, the sky-hook control still performs slightly better in reducing the pitch motion after the bump, in particular in terms of settling time. In fact, the pitch angle returns to nearly zero 0.5 s before the predictive strategy.

Fig. 4.40 Comparison among the vertical tire force: (a) front corner with fully passive (black line, abbreviation: Full pass.), passively-controlled (orange line, abbreviation: P. contr.), passively-controlled and active pitch damping control (dashed yellow line, abbreviation: P. contr. w/pitch), (b) front corner sky-hook (violet line, abbreviation: SH), ground-hook (cyan line, abbreviation: GH), predictive (dashed green line, abbreviation: Pre), (c) rear corner with fully passive (black line, abbreviation: Full pass.), passively-controlled (orange line, abbreviation: P. contr.), passively-controlled and active pitch damping control (dashed yellow line, abbreviation: P. contr. w/pitch), (d) rear corner sky-hook (violet line, abbreviation: SH), ground-hook (cyan line, abbreviation: GH), predictive (dashed green line, abbreviation: Pre)

Figure 4.40 depicts the time histories of the vertical force on the two corners. Focusing on the front corner (Fig. 4.40a and Fig. 4.40b), all control configurations exhibit an unavoidable initial tire detachment as the front axle overcomes the bump, with the tire force saturating at 5146 N. The fully passive system effectively damps tire deflection and remains nearly unaffected by the rear axle impact, as illustrated in Fig. 4.40a. In contrast, both passively-controlled and passively-controlled with pitch show more pronounced force oscillations immediately following the detachment. This is due to power saturation limiting the damping force at high suspension velocities. Additionally, the front tire response in the passively-controlled with pitch configuration is slightly influenced by the rear axle encountering the bump. From Fig. 4.40b, the limitations of the sky-hook strategy for handling performance are evident. A second tire detachment occurs, and vibrations decay slowly. On the other hand, the ground-hook configuration outperforms the fully passive system by stabilizing the tire dynamic force shortly after the second extension. As expected, the predictive strategy offers a balanced compromise. Although a secondary detachment still occurs, it is brief, lasting only 0.002 s compared to 0.019 s with the sky-hook, and the tire dynamics are promptly stabilized through an additional compression phase. Moreover, the predictive control is less affected by pitch disturbances induced by the rear axle bump, as the initial sky-hook setting on the rear axle contributes to pitch mitigation.

Similar observations apply to the rear tires, as shown in Fig. 4.40c and Fig. 4.40d. Here, tire detachment is marked by saturation at 6170 N. Minor variations in tire force can also be observed due to pitch motion induced by the front axle bump in systems using active control strategies.

The main numerical results are summarized in Table 4.12 for comfort-related metrics and in Table 4.13 for handling performance. Overall, the proposed predictive control strategy improves ride comfort compared to all other strategies, except the sky-hook control. This outcome aligns with expectations, as the predictive approach is explicitly designed as a compromise between sky-hook and ground-hook control principles. In particular, the RMS value of the vertical weighted acceleration at the CoG is reduced by 21.33% compared to the full passive configuration. To also include the influence of pitch dynamics on comfort targets, the weighted accelerations at both axles are also evaluated. The rear axle shows an RMS reduction of 21.21% passing from the full passive configuration to the predictive strategy, while the front axle exhibits a slightly greater improvement of 22.60%. Regarding peak values,

Table 4.12 Bump-overcoming comfort results.

Control Strategy	RMS Value			θ [deg]	Peak Value		Settling Time
	\ddot{z}_w	\ddot{z}_{wf}	\ddot{z}_{wr}		\ddot{z}_{wf}	\ddot{z}_{wr}	\ddot{z}_w
	[m/s ²]	[m/s ²]	[m/s ²]		[m/s ²]	[m/s ²]	[s]
Full pass.	0.75	1.15	0.99	0.16	8.99	8.13	1.22
P. contr.	0.66	1.01	0.88	0.29	6.36	5.97	1.71
P. contr. w/pitch	0.65	0.99	0.86	0.09	5.71	5.30	1.33
SH	0.51	0.74	0.67	0.05	4.18	4.40	1.12
GH	0.76	1.15	0.99	0.12	6.63	5.91	1.43
Pre	0.59	0.89	0.78	0.05	5.54	4.99	1.18

Table 4.13 Bump-overcoming handling results.

Control Strategy	RMS Value		No. of Detachments		Settling Time
	F_{tf}	F_{tr}	F_{tf}	F_{tr}	F_{tr}
	[kN]	[kN]	[-]	[-]	[s]
Full pass.	0.88	0.92	1	1	1.81
P. contr.	1.05	1.14	1	1	2.30
P. contr. w/pitch	1.06	1.23	1	1	1.45
SH	1.30	1.44	2	2	1.12
GH	1.04	1.19	1	1	1.43
Pre	1.20	1.34	2	2	1.03

vertical weighted body accelerations decrease by 38.62% at the rear and 38.38% at the front when using predictive control. This slightly greater improvement at the front axle can be attributed to the control switching strategy. The front axle initially operates under sky-hook control during the entire bump encounter and switches to ground-hook only afterward, whereas the rear axle transitions to ground-hook only upon reaching the bump maximum height. As a result, the front axle benefits from a comfort-oriented strategy for a longer duration.

Another comfort-related KPI is the settling time of vertical acceleration. The predictive strategy shows a 3.28% improvement in this metric over the full passive system. When compared with the other passive approaches, the improvements are more pronounced, with reductions of 30.99% and 11.28%, respectively for the passively-controlled and the one with pitch. These findings are particularly relevant for real-world applications, where actuator power limitations are a constraint that significantly affects strategies not explicitly accounting for them.

For handling, the first KPI is the number of tire detachments. The initial detachment upon passing the bump peak is unavoidable across all strategies. However, road-holding-oriented strategies generally avoid a second detachment, whereas both the sky-hook and predictive strategies exhibit a second brief detachment. Despite this, comfort-oriented approaches provide faster settling of tire force oscillations, thanks to their ability to rapidly suppress low-frequency sprung mass vibrations.

Notably, the predictive control achieves the shortest rear tire force settling time among all strategies, offering a 43.09% improvement over the full passive setup and a 3.04% advantage over the sky-hook approach. This superior behavior results from the sequential application of both control philosophies: the sky-hook effectively damps sprung mass oscillations, while the ground-hook focuses on reducing unsprung mass motion. This coordinated dual-phase action mitigates the dominant harmonics of vertical vehicle dynamics, allowing the system to regain full road-holding capability in the shortest time.

In conclusion, even if mathematically simple, the proposed predictive strategy successfully strikes a balance between ride comfort and handling performance, optimizing vehicle response to lumped road irregularities, such as bumps and potholes. The improved tire force settling time also highlights the strategy effectiveness in quickly restoring vehicle stability after disturbance events.

Chapter 5

Conclusions

The growing push toward vehicle electrification is driving the adoption of advanced chassis actuators aimed at improving both efficiency and controllability. In particular, active suspension systems are receiving notable attention, as evidenced by the increasing number of industrial products, patents, and scientific publications. This doctoral dissertation aims to align academic research with industrial development by proposing a holistic design methodology for the development of optimal, vehicle-ready electromagnetic shock absorbers. Indeed, academia mainly focuses on regenerative potentialities and advanced control strategies at numerical level, while industry seeks for easy-installable actuators to mainly manage vehicle body motion.

Electromagnetic shock absorbers are mechatronic devices combining a controllable electric machine with an appropriate force transmission system, which can be either mechanical or hydraulic. Currently, rotary-based technologies are of particular interest, given the higher torque and power densities achievable with rotary electric machines, although a rotary-to-linear conversion mechanism is then required. In this work, two rotary electromagnetic shock absorber architectures are addressed: one featuring a fully mechanical transmission (RSA) and another employing an electro-hydrostatic transmission (EHA). The RSA integrates a two-stage planetary gearbox and a linkage mechanism, whereas the EHA couples a gerotor pump with a linear hydraulic actuator, typically a passive damper with closed valves.

The proposed design methodology provides tools for a preliminary evaluation of the key dynamic performance of the two electromagnetic shock absorbers and then studying their integration within the target suspension systems. Linear quarter-car

simulations are used to derive force-speed requirements for the actuator design: uneven road profiles supply continuous duty requirements, while speed bump simulations define peak duty requirements. Then, an optimization process sizes the electric machine and the gearbox of the RSA, followed by dedicated electromagnetic and mechanical design activities to get a manufacturable device. Due to the more stringent packaging and performance constraints of the EHA, its design focuses on finding the optimal trade-off between space allocation for the electric motor and the hydraulic pump. Ultimately, four fully operational RSAs are installed on all four corners of a D-segment SUV, while two EHAs are integrated into the front fork of a naked motorcycle.

An extensive experimental campaign was conducted to identify the RSA dynamic response, highlighting concerns related to its inerter-like impedance behaviour and non-linear friction effects. Nevertheless, the tests demonstrated the high bandwidth potential of such actuators. Both technologies were also characterized in terms of efficiency, particularly in the passive operating quadrant associated with energy regeneration. As expected, the RSA achieved higher performance, reaching a 66% regenerative efficiency, while the EHA peaked at 35%. Controlled damping tests were conducted to assess performance under alternating speed inputs, confirming that both technologies provide regenerative damping with nearly linear behaviour. Additionally, the EHA also demonstrated the capability to generate active forces. Lastly, NVH analysis of the RSA revealed significant vibrational spectra due to gear meshing, resulting in high noise levels at high-speed and high-torque conditions. Those are key considerations in modern electric vehicles.

Finally, vehicle-level performance was investigated. A novel quarter-car model incorporating RSA dynamics was formulated and validated through experimental bump tests on the D-SUV rear corner. Based on this model, an H_∞ controller was designed, simplifying the required feedback to only the directly measured quantities, i.e., the sprung and unsprung mass accelerations and the suspension stroke. Non-linear simulations demonstrated that the controller successfully maintains the sprung mass acceleration below comfort thresholds specified by standards. However, the comfort-oriented tuning decreases road-holding capabilities. Furthermore, the speed bump scenario stands out as a particularly critical challenge for the control strategy. To this end, also a simpler but predictive control strategy is studied. It combines the benefit of the sky-hook control in reducing the peak accelerations on the vehicle body with the capability of the ground-hook control of damping the wheel-hop vibrations

on the basis of the bump profile estimation using measurements on the front axle. Simulations demonstrated that the controller successfully reach a trade-off between the comfort and handling performance of the vehicle.

5.1 Future developments

As this research work sets the proof of concept for the use of electromagnetic actuators in active vehicle suspensions, several critical issues have emerged, establishing the starting point for future research efforts aimed at developing a mature, industrial-grade component.

From a mechanical design perspective, fatigue resistance emerges as the main challenge. In particular, the RSA gearbox requires a more robust design, which may necessitate either an increase in size or a relaxation of the reduction ratio requirements. Alternative speed reduction technologies, such as cycloidal drives, could also be considered to address this issue.

Regarding the experimental results, the RSA highlighted two major criticalities: the inerter effect and noise emissions. To address the inerter effect, given that actuator inertia is inherently linked to the diameter of the motor shaft and gearbox gears, and therefore power and strength requirements, a straightforward solution would be to compensate for actuator dynamics via a feedforward controller, once inertia, stiffness, and friction parameters are identified. On the other hand, noise reduction could benefit from a redesigned casing, tighter gear tolerances, and the implementation of rubber bushings for mounting the RSA to the vehicle chassis. Conversely, the EHA revealed efficiency limitations. Mechanical friction could be partially mitigated by introducing a ball bearing on the outer pump gear, although packaging constraints remain extremely challenging. Despite the adoption of very tight tolerances, hydraulic leakages can not be fully avoided and are also influenced by thermal effects and wear. In this regard, the introduction of a pressure-feedback controller could significantly improve overall force-tracking performance.

From the performance standpoint, more advanced control design is required to better balance comfort and road holding objectives. Predictive control strategies represent a promising direction, even including perception systems, enabling adaptive tuning based on anticipated road conditions. Additionally, hardware-in-the-loop

(HIL) testing is a fundamental step before vehicle testing, as simulations alone cannot capture all non-linear phenomena. Preliminary HIL studies have already begun [135].

With both vehicle demonstrators fully operational, preliminary road tests have confirmed effective control of sprung mass motion due to maneuvers load transfers, as well as improved comfort over uneven roads. However, crossing speed bumps remains a particularly challenging task.

Finally, Automotive Safety Integrity Level (ASIL) requirements define the necessary safety standards for automotive components according to ISO 26262 [164], ranging from grade A (lowest) to grade D (highest hazard level). Electromagnetic shock absorbers would be classified under grade D due to the risks associated with failure. Therefore, both the actuator and its associated power electronics must be designed with these safety requirements in mind. For instance, the back electromotive force generated when the motor is uncontrolled must not exceed the 60 V threshold for low-voltage systems, otherwise, higher safety standards for cabling and electronics would be necessary. This voltage limit must be respected under all possible operating conditions to prevent power electronics failure. This requirement was not considered during the design of the prototypes presented in this thesis, as the primary objective was to develop a working proof-of-concept vehicle. However, it is now being treated as a key design constraint in the current phases of the project with the industrial partners. Moreover, ensuring a sufficient level of open-circuit damping in case of electrical failure is crucial. Virtual testing, including driver-in-the-loop simulations, and extensive real-world vehicle testing, are essential to validate these safety aspects. In particular, the more efficient RSA design may require the addition of specific features to ensure safe behaviour in open-circuit failure mode.

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